

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
"RECENT TRENDS IN AQUACULTURE"
(ICRTA)**

25th March 2022

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

CONVENER

Dr. P. RAJA

ORGANIZING SECRETARIES

Dr. R. SANTHA KUMARI Dr. R. AZHAGU RAJ

PUBLISHED BY

**DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY
ST. XAVIER'S COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS)**

Recognized as "College with Potential for Excellence" by UGC
Accredited by NAAC at "A++" Grade with a CGPA of 3.66 out of 4 in IV Cycle

PALAYAMKOTTAI - 627 002

TAMIL NADU, INDIA

Website: www.stxavierstn.edu.in

International Conference on
RECENT TRENDS IN AQUACULTURE
(ICRTA – 2022)
25.03.2022

Organized by

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(DST - FIST sponsored)

St. Xavier's College (Autonomous)

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Palayamkottai - 627002

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MODE OF CONDUCT : BLENDED

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ABOUT THE COLLEGE

St. Xavier's College was established at Palayamkottai in 1923 by Jesuit Fathers of the Jesuit Madurai Province with an aim of preparing generations of students for a happy, healthy and harmonious life. The motto of the college is *Veritate Lumen et Vita* (Light and Life through Truth). It is a grant-in-aid institution recognized by the UGC Act under sections 2(f) and 12(B). The College is affiliated to the Manonmaniam Sundaranar University. In recognition of its service and excellence, the College was granted autonomy in 1987. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) in 2019 accredited at A++ grade with a CGPA of 3.66 out of 4 in IV Cycle. The UGC awarded the status of "College with Potential for Excellence" to our college in 2004 and again in 2010 and 2014. STAR College scheme has been awarded by DBT, Govt. of India. In the ranking conducted by the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF), our college got 50th rank in College Category in 2020. Today more than 4000 students study in 14 Postgraduate and 15 Undergraduate departments. Ph.D. Research is carried out in 12 departments.

DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY OF ST. XAVIER'S COLLEGE, PALAYAMKOTTAI was started in 1927 when the subject was taught to the intermediate students. Rev. Fr. Foreau S. J., was the first Lecturer and Mr. Krishnasamy Iyengar assisted him. B.Sc. Degree course was started in 1957 and was upgraded to M.Sc. in the year 1979. The Department was recognized as a Research Department in 1985 and M.Phil. course is being offered since 1986. In the year 2003 and 2018 the Department was recognized as DST-FIST sponsored Department. In 2014, the department was recognized and included under Star College Department Scheme offered by Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, Govt. of India. The Department celebrated its Diamond Jubilee in 2018. At present, the faculty members are concentrating on the basic and the applied aspects of Aquaculture Zoology, Agriculture Zoology [Pestiferous Insects, Phytopathogens and their management], Medical Entomology [Vector Biology and Management], Insect Immunology, Wild life Biology and Phytochemistry and Pharmacology.

ABOUT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

- ★ 'International Conference on Recent Trends in Aquaculture 2022 (ICRTA-22)' invites you to become a part of HYBRID EVENT – which is scheduled on March 25, 2022 at St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Tamil Nadu, India.
- ★ 'Aquaculture 2022' is conducted in Blended mode with both offline and virtual versions. We believe that our decision will enable broad participation.
- ★ This Conference enlightens on the theme "Recent developments in aquaculture" which acknowledges the recent advancements, newest updates, innovations and challenges that impact the field of fisheries, and aquaculture. In the post-pandemic era, feeding the world faces new impediments. This emphasizes the importance of fisheries and aquaculture as viable solutions for supplying high-quality food and nutrition to the world's growing population. Aquaculture continues to be the world's fastest-growing food production sector, despite the fact that capture fish production has remained largely stable in recent decades. However, increasing the scale of aquaculture intensification has resulted in a number of concerns that will require long-term solutions. As a result, it's critical to disseminate information on technological advancements and new modern approaches to sustainable fisheries and aquaculture around the world. This scientific gathering is a positive move in the right direction.
- ★ This prestigious conference will serve as an intuition for international researchers, scientists, academicians, aquaculture experts, marine biologists and industry giants to present their research findings to the international community. The environment will be vibrant, with open and cordial interaction between attendees, with representatives from academia and industry.
- ★ We hope to see you at 'Aquaculture 2022' with a firm belief that it will provide the most beneficial outcomes to the aquaculture and fisheries industry.

PAPERS ARE INVITED IN THE FOLLOWING TOPICS

- Algae technology
- Aquaponics
- Bio-floc technology
- Pond and water quality management
- Fish Diversity
- Fin fish and Shell fish Culture
- Fish breeding
- Aquafeed and Nutrition
- Live feed culture
- Fish Prebiotics and Probiotics
- Fish Genetics
- Fish diseases and management
- Fish toxicology
- Fish genomics
- Harvesting and Post harvesting technology
- Extension and Economics
- Aquaculture bioinformatics

ABSTRACT GUIDELINES

Abstract must be restricted to 200 words and typed in Times New Roman font style, 12 font size with 1.5 line spacing.

AWARDS

The best paper for oral and poster presentation will be awarded in the name of eminent professors and scholars in the field of Zoology-Aquaculture:

Rev. Fr. Foreau, S.J. Award, Rev. Dr. Stephen de Souza, S.J. award.
Dr.V.G.Jhingran award and Dr.M.A. Haniffa award

REGISTRATION FEE

Faculties / Scientists : Rs. 300/-

Research Scholars : Rs. 200/-

UG / PG Students : Rs. 150/-

The Registration fee includes registration kit, lunch and tea/coffee during conference.

The participants are requested to register online through **Google registration form**.

DATES TO REMEMBER

Last date for abstract submission: 20 March, 2022

Abstract acceptance : 21 March, 2022

REGISTRATION LINK

<https://forms.gle/ANaiRS1qR4tyMdoN7>

Soft copy of the abstract should be sent on or before 20th March 2022 to
E-mail: aquaconference2022@gmail.com

PUBLICATION

Papers presented in the ICRTA - 2022 conference will be peer-reviewed and published in Scientia Acta Xaveriana (NAAS Indexed Journal) ISSN 0976-1152, an International Research Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences, published by St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai.

ACCOMMODATION

Accommodation for the participants is available on payment basis. The participants are requested to separately apply for the same before 20th March to organizing secretary on aquaconference2022@gmail.com.

BANK DETAILS FOR FEE PAYMENT

Name : R. Santha Kumari
Account Number : **40823924655**
Branch : **St.Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai-627002 Tamil Nadu, INDIA**

IFSC Code : **SBIN0010482**

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RESOURCE PERSONS

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KEYNOTE SPEAKER

- ✿ **Dr. A. Palavesam**, UGC - Emeritus Professor, Department of Animal Science, M.S. University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, INDIA

PLENARY SPEAKERS

- ✿ **Dr. K. Marimuthu**, Professor, Faculty of applied Bio-Sciences, AIMST University, MALAYSIA.
- ✿ **Dr. Herald Antony**, Global Aquaculture consultant, TALA Aquaculture Division, SUDAN.
- ✿ **Dr. S. Raja**, Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, INDIA.

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Programme

INAUGURATION

- 9:30 am : Registration
10:00 : Prayer
10:00 : Lighting the lamp
10:10 : Welcome address – Dr. P. Raja, Convener & HoD
10:15 : About the Conference – Dr. R. Azhagu Raj, Organizing Secretary
10:20 : Words of blessing – Rev. Dr. V. Henry Jerome, S.J., Rector
10:30 : Felicitation – Rev. Dr. Alphonse Manickam, S.J., Secretary
10:40 : Presidential address – Rev. Dr. S. Mariadoss, S.J., Principal
10:45 : Vote of thanks – Dr. R. Santha Kumari, Organizing Secretary
10:50 : Keynote address – **DR. A. PALAVESAM**, UGC-BSR Fellow,
Department of Animal Science,
M.S. University, Tirunelveli.

11:30 : Tea Break

- 11:45 : **Plenary Lecture 1**
– Dr. S. Raja, Asst. Professor, Dept of Zoology,
Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.

- 12.15 pm : **Plenary lecture 2**
– Dr. A. John Paul, Asst. Professor, Dept of Zoology,
St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Bangalore.

1.00 pm : Lunch

- 2.00 pm : Parallel Online/offline –Oral / Poster presentation (Zoom/Google meet)
2.00 pm : **Plenary lecture 3 Online**
– Dr.K. Marimuthu Professor, AIMST University, Malaysia(Zoom portal)
2.45 pm : **Plenary lecture 4 Online**
– Dr.Herold Antony, Aquaculture expert, Sudan (Zoom portal)

- 2.00 pm : **Plenary lecture 5 Online (Parallel)**
– Dr. P. Stalin, Asst. Professor, Dept of Zoology,
Erode Arts and Science College, Erode (G-meet)

- 2.00 pm : **Plenary lecture 6 Online (Parallel)**
– Dr. A. Bharathi, Asst Prof., Dept. of Zoology,
Sir Theagaraya College, Chennai (G-meet)

VALEDICTION

- 4.00 pm : Welcome address – Dr. R. Santha Kumari, Organizing Secretary
4.05 : Valedictory address – Dr. B. Xavier Innocent, Deputy Principal, SXC
4.15 : Certificate distribution
4.20 : Conference report & Vote of thanks – Dr. R. Azhagu Raj, Organizing secretary

- Master of ceremony** : Inauguration – Dr. J. Ronald
Valediction – Dr. S. Mabel Parimala

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From the Rector's desk

Rev. Dr. V. Henry Jerome, S.J.

24 March 2022

My greetings to all of you!

I am happy to know that the Department of Zoology of our College is organizing an International Conference on 'Recent Trends in Aquaculture'. It is a timely topic that all of us need to understand and analyze and learn from others. It is in many ways relevant to the whole humanity. The World Water Day that we recently commemorated had the main theme on 'Ground Water: Making the invisible visible'. When it comes to water, many things are invisible. We need to make it visible. The academicians do the same through the enormous research into water and aquaculture, so that all that is invisible will be made visible. The conference in the Department of Zoology also paves an important area to be visible.

Nature is the logical investigation of how creatures communicate with each other and with their condition. This incorporates connections between people of analogous species, between various species, and among creatures and their physical and substance situations. Aquaculture is the fastest developing segment of animal protein generation and nowadays represents 47-50 percent of the world's aqua creature sustenance supply. Aquaculture creation lessens the weight on wild fisheries brought about by overfishing. Aquaculture is anticipated to be the prime wellspring of fish as interest develops from the worldwide labor and wild catch fisheries approach their most extreme take. Supportable aquaculture may be a dynamic idea and therefore the supportability of an aquaculture framework will shift with species, area, societal standards and the condition of information and innovation.

I am delighted to appreciate the Head and the Organising Secretaries and all others who are involved in this Conference. Let this International Conference be yet another hallmark of the department.

God bless you!

In solidarity,

Jesuit Residence, St. Xavier's College, Palayamkottai - 627002

Rev. Dr. Alphonse Manickam, S. J.,
Secretary

Message

To
The Staff and Students
Department of Zoology
St. Xavier's College (Autonomous)
Palayamkottai 627 002

I am happy to know that the Department of Zoology of our College has planned to organise an International conference on “Recent Trends in Aquaculture”. It is a golden opportunity to the staff, research scholars and students to listen to experts in the field of aquaculture and get motivated. It is a good occasion for the entrepreneurs in aquaculture to get practical exposure from the experts. I find the topic a relevant one to one and all.

Aquaculture is presently playing and will keep on playing, a serious part in boosting worldwide fish generation and in gathering rising interest for fishery items. Expanded open interest for fish and diminishing normal marine living spaces have urged researchers to think about ways that biotechnology can build the generation of marine sustenance items, and to make aquaculture as a developing field of creature to investigate. Biotechnology enables researchers to recognize and consolidate characteristics in fish and shellfish to expand efficiency and improve qualitatively. Researchers are exploring qualities that will build generation of distinguishing fish development factors that are used to fight microbial infections.

I wish Dr. P. Raja, Convenor and Head, Dr. R. Santha Kumari and Dr. R. Azhagu Raj, organising secretaries and all other staff and students of the Department of Zoology a grand success and a deep sense of satisfaction of the conference.

Rev.Dr.Alphonse Manickam, S.J.,
Secretary

Rev. Dr. S. Mariadoss, S.J.,
Principal

Message

I am happy to know that the Department of Zoology of our College has planned to organise an International Conference on “Recent Trends in Aquaculture”. Aquaculture Conference 2022 unites an International blend of specialists like academicians, researchers, and business experts, the overall population, momentum, and imminent fish ranchers to share data and thoughts regarding the improvement of aquaculture and aqua life science. Participants will find out around a few points important to aquaculture and aqua life science, and get some answers concerning the ebb and flow aquaculture hardware and items by perusing the ongoing exhibition. Everybody with an enthusiasm for aquaculture, aqua life science, including imminent producers, specialists, educators, understudies or organization people with employments identified with aquaculture and aqua life science can go to the gathering.

I wish Dr. P.Raja, Convenor and Head, Dr. R. Santha Kumari and Dr. R. Azhagu Raj, rrganising secretaries and all other staff and students of the Department of Zoology a grand success and a deep sense of satisfaction of the Conference

Rev. Dr. S. Mariadoss, S.J.,
Principal

Dr. A. Palavesam
UGC-BSR Faculty Fellow
Former Professor & Head
Department of Zoology
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University
Tirunelveli

Foreword

It gives me immense pleasure to learn that Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai is organizing an International Conference on "Recent Trends in Aquaculture" on 25th March 2022. The Department of Zoology is an age-old, reputed Department of St. Xavier's College, which has shown a path to many people in this country to reach their desired destination effectively. Furthermore, "Aquaculture" is the prime industry to support the production of protein rich food materials for the malnourished population of our country, apart from earning foreign exchange through export. However, this industry needs refined modern techniques to address the issues such as disease outbreaks, low production, non-availability of eco-friendly cost effective feed, SPF broodstock / seeds and the lack of easily adoptable post harvest technology. Considering this, aquaculture scientists all over the world are focusing their attention on solving the above mentioned issues. In this scenario, organizing scientific meetings in the form of conference is a welcome approach.

As an aquaculture researcher and alumni of this esteemed institution, I very much appreciate the effort made by the Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College, Palayamkottai for organizing this International Conference on "Recent Trends in Aquaculture". I strongly believe that the proceedings of this conference will certainly enlighten the young minds to formulate hypothesis oriented towards the establishment of "sustainable aquaculture". I wish the conference all success.

Message

I am pleased to convey my message on the occasion of the International Conference on "Recent Trends in Aquaculture (ICRTA 2022)" organized by the Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai, Tamil Nadu, India held on 25th March 2022.

The diversification of agriculture with a focus on land and water management, farm mechanisation, animal husbandry, fisheries and aquaculture and other allied activities are important food production sectors in India. Aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing production sectors besides sharing about 20% of the agricultural exports and India has reached the status of the second-largest producer of fish in the world. The aquaculture sector has the potential to contribute many of the Sustainable Development Goals covering poverty elevation, hunger and food security, economic growth, employment and decent work, consumption and production in India. To meet the food demand with ecological importance, the technology up-gradation and modern aquaculture can be undertaken in harmony with the environment thus fulfilling ecological criteria of sustainable development. However, cutting edge technology development for successful technical research and outreach are essential prerequisites to the development of livelihood options based on aquaculture for the development of a nation. The conference papers have brought out various issues that need to be addressed to realise the full potential of the aquaculture sector and it is an attempt to revive the knowledge on the current status of the research responsible in the light of the Blue Revolution in India.

I am sure that the research discussion at this international conference would play a vital role in updating the knowledge and skills for the benefit of academicians, scientists and other stakeholders, especially in the field of Aquaculture.

I would like to express my wholehearted wishes to the organizers for their efforts in organising this international conference and wish the event grand success.

S. Raja

Dr. S. RAJA
Kongunadu Arts and Science College,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu.

Message

It is my honour and privilege to convey a message on the occasion of the International Conference on "Recent Trends in Aquaculture (ICRTA 2022)" organized by the Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai, Tamil Nadu, India to be held on 25 March 2022.

In the post-pandemic era, feeding the world faces new impediments. This emphasizes the importance of aquaculture as a viable solution for supplying high-quality food and nutrition to the world's growing population. Aquaculture continues to be the world's fastest-growing food production sector, despite the fact that capture fish production has remained largely stable in recent decades. Aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing production sectors besides sharing about 20% of the agricultural exports and India has reached the status of the second-largest producer of fish in the world. The aquaculture sector has the potential to contribute many of the Sustainable Development Goals covering poverty elevation, hunger and food security, economic growth, employment and decent work, consumption and production in India. However, increasing the scale of aquaculture intensification has resulted in a number of concerns that will require long-term solutions. As a result, it's critical to disseminate information on technological advancements and new modern approaches to sustainable fisheries and aquaculture around the world. This scientific gathering is a positive move in the right direction.

This prestigious conference serves as a global colloquy for international researchers, scientists, academicians, aquaculture experts, marine biologists and industry giants to present their research findings to the international community. The environment will be vibrant, with open and cordial interaction between attendees, with representatives from academia and industry belonging to all of the major countries. The conference papers have brought out various issues that need to be addressed to realise the full potential of the aquaculture sector and it is an attempt to revive the knowledge on the current status of the research responsible in the light of the Blue Revolution in India.

I am sure that the scientific discussions held at this International Conference would play a vital role in the empowerment of the knowledge and skill development for the benefit of academicians, scientists and other stakeholders, especially in the field of Aquaculture.

I would like to express my wholehearted gratitude and wishes to the organizers for their efforts in organising this International Conference and wish the event a grand success.

Dr. A. John Paul

Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, St. Joseph's College (Autonomous)
36 – Langford Road, Bengaluru – 560027, Karnataka, India.

Message

India inhabits one-fifth of the world population, more than 65% of them are below the age of 35, besides 72.2 percent of the total population reside in these rural areas, in which nearly about 25 % of them are living under the poverty line, facing many challenges, especially malnutrition, unemployment underemployment. Sustainable agriculture and aquaculture practices could only pave the way to an environmentally sustainable society without depleting or degrading natural resources. Intensified agriculture production by the inclusion of improper usage of inorganic fertilizers had a number of potential direct and indirect effects on biodiversity. The uncertainty, insecurity in agriculture could lead to the frustration and switching over of farmers from agriculture to other areas for meeting their exigency, which demands them to the exploration of other food-producing avenues. Blue revolution by the improved fisheries and aquaculture is one of the important sources of food production, nutritional security, employment, and income in India. The fisheries sector is a direct source of livelihood for more than 20 million fishers and fish farmers. The aquaculture industry could meet the protein demands of the people; it is an environmentally responsible source of foods and other commercial products, increasing jobs for the emerging unemployed population, additional livelihood activities that are essential to our society's future prosperity and growth. The sustainability of any sector depends on the continuous implementation of advanced techniques and skills, sharing of experience and knowledge to face the upcoming challenges. Due to global warming and subsequent climate change and contamination of water bodies, farmers are facing a lot of problems, especially the outbreak of disease, poor quality products, which eventually end with ecosystem damage and economic loss. The pandemic period is a wake-up call to put people and the environment first. Aquaculture and fisheries are the only cheapest source of protein, and they deserve our care and respect. Fish production through aquaculture should be increased substantially as the wild catch is declining. We are aimed at the commercial development of new aquafarming technologies for food, and other products such as pharmaceuticals and ornamental purposes, in a way that does not harm the environment. The conference is being organized by the Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), against this backdrop envisaging to provide an ideal platform for students aspirants, researchers, academicians, farmers, industrialists, and policymakers to take forward the concept of sustainability, which can multiply the income of the farming community in a sustainable way, a major step in empowering young minds and promoting the move towards acting responsibly in regards to all aquatic resources and their ecosystems.

P. Raja

Dr. P. Raja

Head of the Department of Zoology
St. Xavier's College (Autonomous)

Dear Participants

We feel happy by organising an International Conference on “Recent Trends in Aquaculture”. Pleasant welcome to all around the globe to attend blended Conference on Aquaculture Research that is venerable for the past, precious for the present and innovative for the future field of Aquaculture.

ICRTA 2022 provides researchers worldwide with the rare opportunity to meet, network and experience new scientific novelties. The conference highlights the theme “Recent Trends of Aquaculture” aimed to provide an opportunity for the professionals to discuss the technological advancements in the field of aquaculture and fishery and enlightens the recent advancements, newest updates, innovations and challenges that impact the field of fisheries biology and aquaculture.

ICRTA 2022 has been planned in an interdisciplinary manner with promotion of dialogue and sharing of knowledge on emerging technologies and approaches, innovations by optimizing interactions, partnerships and networking opportunities for Invited speakers, aquaculture and fisheries practitioners, industry experts, academics, global delegates, scientists mainly emphasis on large-scale study methods and innovations in the session tracks will provide a rare opportunity to join us in this extraordinary occasion.

We thank and acknowledge **Dr. S. Mabel Parimela**, Assistant Professor of Zoology, SXC, for her dedicated work in proofreading this ICTRA-2022 conference abstract book.

Mr. B. Samuel, Mr. Dunston Richard, and Ms. Angelin Gracia II, M.Sc. Zoology, and R.M. Petchiyammal, I M.Sc ., Zoology, are student volunteers who deserve special recognition. The contribution of Vinothini G., Shunmuga Priya N., Raja Pavithra P, Nanthini Devi, M. Nangamuthu, Sarath Kumar R., Piyatrus J. and K.Ellamuthu of M.Sc Zoology students for their help is commendable.

We would like to express our gratitude to the college administration and the members of the organising committee for their assistance with this conference.

We would like to express our wholehearted wishes to the Resource persons and Participants for sending their abstracts for this international conference and wish the event grand success.

Dr. R. Santha Kumari
Dr. R. Azhagu Raj
Organizing Secretaries (ICRTA-2022)

DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai – 627 002, Tamil Nadu

Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University

(Recognized as “College with Potential for Excellence” by UGC)

(Accredited with “A⁺⁺” Grade with a CGPA of 3.66/4 in IV cycle)

DEPARTMENT PROFILE

The Department of Zoology was started in 1927 when the subject was taught to the intermediate students. Rev. Fr. Foreau S.J. was the first Lecturer and Mr. Krishnasamy Iyengar assisted him. B.Sc. Degree course was started in 1957 and was upgraded to M.Sc. in the year 1979. The Department was recognized as a Research Department in 1985 and M.Phil. course is being offered since 1986. In the year 2003 the Department was recognized as DST-FIST sponsored Department. In 2014, the department was recognized and included under Star College Department Scheme offered by Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, Govt. of India.

The B.Sc. programme of the Department provides a strong foundation in the fundamental concepts of various branches of Zoology like Invertebrata, Chordata, Biochemistry, Biostatistics and Introduction to Computer Science, Physiology, Ecology, Genetics, Aquaculture, Molecular Biology, Immunology and Microbiology, Evolution, Bioinformatics, Environmental Science, Development Biology and Insect Diversity and Pest Management are being offered. Moreover, in collaboration with the Department of Chemistry, we offer Biomolecules as an inter-disciplinary course and Sericulture and Aquaculture as Certificate Courses. The M.Sc. programme provides an in-depth study in Cell and Molecular Biology, Biochemistry, Genetics and Animal Biotechnology, Techniques in Biology, Ecology and Environmental Biology, Immunology and Microbiology, Evolutionary Biology, Animal Physiology, Developmental Biology, Aquaculture and Insect Pest Management. The curriculum also includes dissertation work. The M. Phil. programme offers specialized courses on Research Methodology, Aquaculture Biotechnology and Applied Entomology and a project work in Basic and Applied aspects in Aquaculture or Entomology.

To promote research activities in our department six research units / centers have been established and successfully run by our faculty members like Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose [Entomology Research Unit (ERU)], Dr. M. A. Haniffa [Centre for Aquaculture Research and Extension (CARE)], Dr. K. Sahayaraj [Crop Protection Research Centre (CPRC)], Dr. M. Narayanan [Aquatic Biodiversity Centre (ABC)], Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam [Centre for Aquafeed and Nutrition (CAFen)] and Dr. B. Xavier Innocent [Fish Immunology Lab.]. At present these research centers are headed by Dr. K. Sahayaraj (Zoology Research Centre and Crop Protection Research Centre), Dr. P. Raja and Dr. J. Ronald (Centre for Aquaculture Research and Extension), Dr. P. Selvaraj and Dr. T. Pushpanathan (Entomology Research Unit) and Dr. J. Babila Jasmine (Centre for Medical Entomology and Pharmacology).

Our faculty members tapped research grants worth nearly Rs. 10 crores from regional (MK University, Madurai; TNSCST, Chennai; MEA Trust, Chennai), and national [University Grants Commissions (UGC), Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR), Department of Science and Technology (DST), Department of

Biotechnology (DBT), Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), Ministry of Environment & Forests (MoEF), Ministry of Earth Sciences (MOE), Govt. of India] and also from International (IFS, Sweden)] funding agencies.

Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose and Dr. K. Sahayaraj have earned Doctor of Science (D.Sc.) in Zoology from Madurai Kamaraj University and University of Madras in 1999 and 2017 respectively. Dr. M.A. Haniffa (CSIR-2008-2013 and UGC-2013-2015) and Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose (CSIR) (2012-2015) have been honored as UGC/CSIR- Emeritus Professors. Our faculty members have brought out more than 1000 research papers and 15 books during this period and have produced more than 147 Ph.Ds. Research activities of our research centers is a boon to our department and to the college that brings more laurels and fetches maximum grade points in the NAAC accreditation processes.

At present, the faculty members are concentrating on the basic and the applied aspects of Zoology, Aquaculture, [Aquatic biodiversity, Marine Biotechnology, and Fish Larviculture], Agriculture Zoology [Pestiferous Insects, Phytopathogens and their management], Medical Entomology [Vector Biology and Management], Insect Immunology, Wild life Biology and Phytochemistry and Pharmacology.

MILESTONE OF THE DEPARTMENT

- 1957- B.Sc. Course started
- 1979- M.Sc. Course started
- 1985- Recognized as a Research Department and offered Ph.D. programme
- 1986- M.Phil. Course started
- 2003- Affiliated as FIST sponsored department (Fund for Improvement of S&T Infrastructure in Universities and Higher Educational Institutions) by the Department of Science and Technology, Govt. of India
- 2004- Girls were admitted into B.Sc. Zoology Course
- 2005- B.Sc. Zoology course renamed as Advanced Zoology and Biotechnology
- 2012- Generic name Zoology reintroduced in B.Sc.
- 2013- Crop Protection Research Centre recognized by the MS University
- 2014- DBT selected the department as Star College Department
- 2015- Interdisciplinary paper Biomolecule offered for B.Sc along with Department of Chemistry.
- 2015- Certificate Courses offered by the department
- 2017- Zoology Research Centre registration extended up to 2020.
- 2018- Interdisciplinary paper Plant and Animal Biotechnology offered for M.Sc. along with Department of Botany.

ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE FACULTIES

- Rev. Fr. Stephan de Souza, S.J. – Principal (1992)
- Mr. M. Thomas Punithan – Governing Body Member (2005-2007), Vice Principal (2007-2009), Deputy Principal (2011-2012, 2013-2014)
- Dr. M. A. Haniffa –Professor of Emeritus (CSIR-2008-2013) (UGC-2013-2015)

- Dr. B. Victor – Dean of Sciences (2004 to 2007), Coordinator of Internal Quality Assurance Cell (2005 to 2007), Assistant Controller of Examinations (2000 to 2004), Controller of Examinations (2016-2019)
- Dr. M. Narayanan – Vice Principal (2007-2011)
- Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose - Periyar University Member of Syndicate (2007- 2010), earned Doctor of Science by Madurai Kamaraj University (1999), Professor Emeritus (CSIR) (2012-2015)
- Dr. B. Xavier Innocent - Governing Body Member (2015-2016)
- Dr. K. Sahayaraj – Dean of Sciences (2013-2015), Overall coordinator of DBT Star College Scheme (2014-2015); earned Doctor of Science by University of Madras (2017).
- Dr. R. Azhagu Raj – IQAC-Assistant Director (2020 onwards), Governing Body Member (2021 onwards)

RESEARCH CENTRES ESTABLISHED BY THE FACULTIES

- 1982- Entomology Research Unit by Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose
- 1996- Centre for Aquaculture Research and Extension (CARE) by Dr. M.A. Haniffa
- 1998- Crop Protection Research Centre (CPRC) by Dr. K. Sahayaraj
- 1998- Aquatic Biodiversity Centre (ABC) by Dr. M. Narayanan
- 2000- Centre for Aquafeed and Nutrition (CAFen) by Dr. T.A. Sethuramalingam
- 2012- Fish Immunology Lab by Dr. B. Xavier Innocent
- 2017- Centre for Medical Entomology and Pharmacology by Dr. J. Babila Jasmine

HEADS OF THE DEPARTMENT

- Prof. Lazarus (1958-1959)
- Prof. S. Raman (1960-1961)
- Prof. M. V. Rajendran (1962-1974)
- Prof. Selvaratnam (1974-1987)
- Rev. Fr. Stephen De Souza, S.J. (1987-1996)
- Prof. M. Thomas Punithan (1996-2008)
- Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam (2008-2013)
- Dr. B. Xavier Innocent (2013-2016)
- Dr. S. Maria Sebastian (2016-2017)
- Dr. K. Sahayaraj (2017-2020)
- Dr. P. Raja (2020 onwards)

RETIRED FACULTY MEMBERS

- Prof. Lazarus (1959)
- Prof. S. Raman (1961)
- Prof. M. V. Rajendran (1974)

- Prof. R. Selvaratnam Fernando (1987)
- Rev. Fr. Stephen De Souza, S.J. (1987-1996)
- Dr. J. P. Arockiam (2002)
- Prof. P. Ramakrishnan (2003)
- Prof. M. Thomas Punithan (2008)
- Dr. M. A. Haniffa (May 2008)
- Dr. B. Victor (May 2008)
- Dr. M. Narayanan (May 2009)
- Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose (May 2012)
- Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam (May 2013)
- Dr. B. Xavier Innocent (June 2016)
- Dr. S. Maria Sebastian (May 2017)

SEMINAR / CONFERENCE / SYMPOSIUM / TRAINING ORGANIZED BY THE FACULTIES

- 1987- National symposium on Environment Biology on 2-4 April 1987 by Dr. M.A. Haniffa, Dr. M. Narayanan and Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam.
- 1990- IAS/IPS preliminary coaching classes conducted by Mr. P. Ramakrishnan.
- 1992- Workshop on Curriculum Development and Resources Utilization in 1992 by Dr. M. A. Haniffa.
- 1992- DST Sensitization Programme for USERS in 1992 by Dr. M. A. Haniffa and Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam.
- 1992- Regional Seminar & Workshop in Environmental Education on 20 April 1992 by Dr. M. Narayanan.
- 1993- National symposium on Environment and Education on 21 April 1993 by Dr. M.A. Haniffa.
- 1994- Regional Workshop/Refresher Course on Aquaculture for College Teachers in 1994 by Dr. M. A. Haniffa and Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam.
- 1994- In-service training cum demonstration programme for Post graduate assistants in Higher Secondary Schools, 26-30 December 1994 by Dr. B. Victor.
- 1995- Symposium on Biological and cultural control of Agricultural and medicinal pests on 22-24 February 1995 by Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose.
- 1996- CONFAQUA-'96 from 18-20 December 1996 by Dr. M. A. Haniffa.
- 1998- UGC Question Bank Workshop - Phase II in Zoology in November 1998 by Dr. B. Victor and Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam.
- 2005- National seminar on technology and management of bioresources on 21-22 March 2005 by Dr. M. Narayanan.
- 2006- National conference on Aquaculture CONFAQUA 2006 on 15-17 February 2006 by Dr. M. A. Haniffa and Dr. T. A. Sethuramalingam.
- 2007- Biopesticide International Conference (BIOCICON-2007) on 28-30 November 2007 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2009- National Seminar on Environmental Toxicology (Entox-2009) on 26-27 February 2009.
- 2009- Second Biopesticide International Conference (BIOCICON2009) on 26-28 November 2009 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2010- Environmental protection and awareness programme among school children and college students on 08 March 2010.

- 2011- International Symposium on Insect Pest Management on 23-25 February 2011 by Dr. Dunston P. Ambrose.
- 2011- Third Biopesticide International Conference (BIOCICON2011) on 28-30 November 2011 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2013- National seminar on Biodiversity and Bio-resource: A Fragile balance on 25-26 February 2013.
- 2013- Fourth Biopesticide International Conference (BIOCICON2013) on 28-30 November 2013 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2013- DBT sponsored Short term training programme (STPP) on Bio-nonmaterials for Pest and Disease Management for college teachers on 14-30 May 2013 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2014- National seminar on recent trends in Endocrinology on 24-25 February 2014 by Dr. S. Maria Sebastian.
- 2014- Regional Seminar on Environmental Management on 7 March 2014 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2014- Workshop on Nanobiotechnology on 13 December 2014 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2014- Workshop on Virtual dissection on 16 December 2014 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2015- National seminar on Biodiversity conservation: Present status and future perspective on 12-13 February 2015 by Dr. A. Jeyaseeli and Dr. T. Pushpanathan.
- 2016- National seminar on Life on fragile: concern, causes and conservation on 18-19 February 2016 by Dr. J. Ronald and Dr. P. Raja.
- 2017- Bio-pesticides and plant growth promoters' preparation and usage under Creation of Scientific Awareness programme for self help group supported by TNSCST, Chennai by Dr. K. Sahayaraj and Dr. R. Azhagu Raj.
- 2018- Zoology Congress on 10-12 January 2018 by Dr. K. Sahayaraj.
- 2019- International conference on Vectors: Menance and Management – VECMAN 2020 on 28-29 January by Dr. K. Sahayaraj, Dr. P. Selvaraj and Dr. T. Pushpanathan.
- 2020- National level Zoology webinar Series on 22-24 July 2020 by Dr. P. Raja, Dr. S. Mabel Parimala and Dr. T. Elizabeth.
- 2021- National level Zoology Webinar on 03.08.21 by Dr. P. Raja, Dr. J. Babila Jasmine and Dr. S. Mabel Parimala.
- 2022- International Conference on Recent Trends in Aquaculture (ICRTA) on 25 March 2022 by Dr. R. Santha Kumari and Dr. R. Azhagu Raj.

DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

St. Xavier's College (Autonomous),
Palayamkottai – 627 002, Tamil Nadu

Affiliated to *Manonmaniam Sundaranar University*

(Recognized as “College with Potential for Excellence” by UGC)

Accredited with “A⁺⁺” Grade with a CGPA of 3.66

International conference on Recent Trends in Aquaculture

OFFLINE ORAL PRESENTATION -1

25/03/2022 Time :2.30 PM

Venue: Dept. of Zoology (Smart Class Room)

Chairperson : Dr.S.Raja, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Zoology,
Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore

Co-Chairperson: Dr.L.Joelri Michael Raj , HoD, Assistant Professor
Dept. of Botany,St.Xaviers College,Palayamkottai

1. STUDIES ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS & PHYTOPLANKTON DIVERSITY OF POIGAI RESERVOIR IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT. Ramisha S, JuwairiyaNasreen J, Mathevan Pillai M and Iren Amutha S
3. EFFECTS OF PROBIOTIC *LACTOBACILLUS* ON THE GROWTH PERFORMANCE AND HEMATOLOGICAL PROFILE OF *CATLA CATLA JUVENILES*. A.Shajahan and M.I.ZahirHussian
4. BIODIVERSITY ON FRESHWATER ROTIFERS IN RELATION TO PHYSICO- CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF VEINTHANKULAM POND AND PALAYAM CANAL. K.Ajitha, Dr. J.Shifa vanmathi, Dr. R. Santhakumari, Dr. A. Mohaideen
11. EFFECT OF FRUIT PEEL WASTE ON GROWTH OF THE COMMON CARP (*Cyprinus carpio*) FINGERLINGS M.Karthika and M.I.Zahir Hussian
12. PROXIMATE COMPOSITION OF SELECTED GREEN ALGAL *CODIUM* SPECIES. Anusathya Priya, P. and John Peter Paul J.
15. ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF SOME GUT ASSOCIATED BACTERIA FROM *CHANNA STRIATUS* G.Mallika, BabilaJasmine.J and Sumathi. G
17. ISOLATION, SCREENING, AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GUT PROBIOTICS FROM ESTUARINE FISH. C. Ajith, R. Sathishkumar, G. Uma, R. Shyam kumar, T. Citarasu

- 20.EFFECT OF SEAWEED EXTRACTS ON *CYPRINUS CARPIO* AND THEIR IMMUNE RESPONSE AGAINST *FLAVOBACTERIUM SPS*. Dr. A. Mohaideen, Dr. J.Shifa vanmathi, G. Carolin priya stepin
23. REEF FISH ABUNDANCE, DIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONAL GROUPS ON A SHALLOW REEF PATCH IN TUTICORIN REGION OF GULF OF MANNAR. Jonathan Samuel Emmett and K. Diraviya Raj
24. HEALTH MANAGEMENT IN SHRIMP CULTURE PONDS *PENAEUS VANNAMEI*. VINAYAGAMOORTHY B, MARIMUTHU A, AJITHKUMAR M, SUGESH S AND MEGAVANNAN R
28. DIVERSITY OF PHYTOPLANKTON AND HYDROLOGICAL STUDIES OF PUTHERI PARAYADI POND, KANNIYAKUMARI DISTRICT Juwairiya Nasreen J1 ., Ramisha S ., M. Mathevan Pillai and A.Iren Amutha
39. BIODIVERSITY OF AQUATIC INSECTS OF THREE PONDS IN RAMANATHAPURAM., TAMILNADU.K. Prathap Mathan, Dr.J. Babila Jasmine

OFFLINE ORAL PRESENTATION -2

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Venue: Dept. of Zoology (UG Lab)

Chairperson : Dr.A. John Paul, Asst.Professor,

Dept. of Zoology, St.Joseph College, Bengalru

Co-Chairperson: Dr.M.Johnson Gritto, Assistant Professor ,Dept. of Botany

St.Xaviers College, Palayamkottai

43. POLYCHAETES OF THE AROCKIAPURAM COAST WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THEIR INTERTIDAL HABITAT. Balasubramanian, S., Citarasu, iT., Lazarus, S., and Renu, A.
50. A PILOT STUDY ON THE FISH DIVERSITY OF THAMIRABHARANI RIVER IN SELECTED AREAS OF TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT. Dr.S. Mohamed Ramlath Sabura , M.Balasaraswathi and Dr. M.I. Delighta Mano Joyce
- 53.Antifungal ACTIVITY OF THE FRESH WATER FISH (*Heteropneustes fossilis*) M.Umamageshwari, Dr. S. Umarajeswari
- 58.GC-MS ANALYSIS AND PREDICTION OF BIOACTIVITIES IN THE PETROLEUM ETHER EXTRACT OF *Nitophyllum marginale* (Kutzing) J.Ag. Athi lakshmi, S. and John peter paul, J.
- 71.ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF ENDOPHYTIC BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM THE ROOT NODULES OF *Nelumbo nucifera* AGAINST FISH PATHOGENS. Muthukrishnan S, Ramkumar R, Micheal Antony Packiam T, Raja P, and Ronald. J.
- 73.ANTAGONISTIC ACTIVITY OF PROBIOTIC BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM THE GUT OF *Dawkinsia filamentosa* (Valenciennes, 1844) AGAINST FISH PATHOGENS. Rajeswari S, Muthukrishnan S, Ronald J and Raja P

- 74.A PRELIMINARY SURVEY OF WETLAND BIRDS AT POND, SUTHAMALLI, TIRUNELVELI, TAMILNADU. M.Thilagavathi., J. Babila Jasmine and S.Mabel Parimala
86. BACTERICIDAL ACTIVITY OF EPIDERMAL MUCUS EXTRACTS OF FRESH WATER SPINEY EEL FISH (*Mastacembelus armatus*). R. Sivasakthi and Dr.S.Umarajeswari
- 87.BIOINFORMATICS-THE NEXT BIG THING IN AQUACULTURE. Cannon Fernandes
95. CHLORPYRIFOS INDUCED STRESS MEDIATED PROTEIN EXPRESSION, ELEVATED METABOLIC ENZYME CHANGES AND MORTALITY IN RAINBOW FISH, POECILIA RETICULATE. Dr.M.Subakaran, S.Kiruthiga
- 105.GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF WHITE MOLLY, POECILIA SPHENOPS FED WITH NATURAL SOURCES OF CAROTENOID PIGMENTS FROM TAGETES ERECTA. A. Jeyaseeli and B. Madhubala
106. STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE, PH, DETERGENT AND PESTICIDE ON THE OPERCULAR BEAT ON THE RESPIRATORY RATE OF ORNAMENTAL FISH WHITE MOLLY, *POECILIA SPHENOPS* R.Sivagnanam, Joe Rini.E , Saranya.S and A.Jeyaseeli

OFFLINE POSTER PRESENTATION (PG LAB)-3

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Chairperson: Dr.Ezhilmathi Sophiya,
Assistant Professor, Dept. of Zoology,
St.John's College, Palayamkottai

32. A RAPID SURVEY ON AIR BREATHING FISHES OF THAMIRABARANI RIVER, TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT. W. Michael Isaac V. Rayen, Muthukrishnan S, Raja P.
- 49.STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE, PH, DETERGENT AND PESTICIDE ON THE OPERCULAR BEAT ON THE RESPIRATORY RATE OF ORNAMENDAL FISH WHITE MOLLY,*Poecilia sphenops* . R. Sivagnanam, Joe Rini. E , Saranya. S and A. Jeyaseeli
- 51.A STUDY OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *Indigofera glandulosa* J.C.WENDLAGAINST SELE **bio-stimulator** CTED FISH PATHOGENS. Balagangatharan P, Lakshmi Bhaarathi E, Raja P
- 97.STUDIES ON GROWTH AND MANAGEMENT OF INDIAN MAJOR CARPS IN PERIYAKULAM THOOTHUKUDI DISTRICT. Samuel. B, and Azhagu Raj. R*
98. ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF SEAWEED COLLECTED FROM PERUMANAL, TAMILNADU AGAINST HUMAN AND FISH PATHOGENIC BACTERIA. Ramkumar.R, Muthu Krishnan.S, and Raja. P.
- 104.COMPARATIVE STYDY ON UNSATURATED FATTY ACID IN FRESH AND MARAINE WATER FISHES. Angelin gracia M and Raja P.

111.NOXIOUS EFFECTS OF HERBAL SYRUP [NIVARAN90] ON ORNAMENTAL FISH COMMON MOLLY *Poecilia sphenops*. Antony sahaya meldes .A and Azhagu Raj.R.

112.A SHORT EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF DETERGENTS ON COMMON MOLLY *POECILIA SPHENOPS*. Ari karan.M and Azhagu Raj.R

113.A SHORT EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON IMPACT OF HAIR DYE IN ORNAMENTAL FISH. Arunkumar S. and R. Azhagu Raj

114. ADVERSE RESULTS OF COCONUT OIL [VVD] STUDIED ON ORNAMENTAL FISH COMMON MOLLY *Poecilia sphenops* .Hemalatha.E and Azhagu Raj.R

115.EFFECT OF BODY SOAP ON OXYGEN CONSUMPTION IN ORNAMENTAL FISH *Poecilia sphenops*. Jeya murugan E and Azhagu Raj.R

116.DELETERIOUS EFFECT OF FABRIC SOFTENERS [COMFORT] ON *POECILIA SPHENOPS*. Naveen kumar.V and Azhagu Raj.R

117.STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF SHAMPOO ON OXYGEN CONSUMPTION IN ORNAMENTAL FISH *POECILIA SPHENOPS*. Sudha kani.B and Azhagu Raj.R

ONLINE POSTER PRESENTATION -4

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Google Meet Link:

Chairperson : Rev.Fr. Arun Vijay S.J.

Dept. of Zoology,

St.Xavier's College, Palayamkottai

10. DETECTION OF VIBRIO SPECIES IN THE DISEASED *PENAEUS VANNAMEI* ALONG THE COASTAL SYSTEM OF TAMILNADU. ALMAS.R, PAVITHRA.B, SUGANTHI.R, VINAYAGAMOORTHY. B, SUGESH. S AND MEGAVANNAN. R

14. COBITID FISHES IN THE BRAHMAPUTRA AND THE CHINDWIN RIVER BASINS OF NORTHEASTERN INDIA .
Kangjam Velentina Devi , Bidangshree Basumatary, Wimarithy A Marak & Yumnam Lokeshwor Singh

18.BIOTECHNOLOGY IN THE AREA OF AQUA LIFE CONSERVATION: IS AN INNOVATIVE TOOL TO PROTECT FISHES FROM EXTINCTION & EXPLOITATION. Monalisa Sahu,.

25. BIO- PLASTIC MATERIALS FROM CULTIVABLE FRESH WATER FISH WASTE AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE FOR SYNTHETIC PLASTICS. S.Jaya Suriya, S.Vishnu Priyaa, D.Menaga Devi, M.Usha and S.Raja.

26. STATUS OF FRESHWATER CATFISHES AND THEIR COMMERCIAL IMPORTANCE IN THE CAUVERY RIVER BASIN. Yaswanthkumar S, Raja S and Kannan K
31. HYDROGEL-ALGAE TECHNOLOGY IN AQUACULTURE. M.Reshma Anjum, M.Sankari, D.Kundana Sai, M. Keerthana, A.Mouni
33. THE EFFECT OF FORMULATED AQUAFEED ON SELECTED ORNAMENTAL FISH. E.Jagadeeshwari, M.Balachandar
37. PREBIOTIC AND PROBIOTIC SHRIMP LARVAL FEED. Ajas Mohamed K, Kavi Varadha Raja A K, Vignesh M, Ramabhai V
38. PROBIOTIC SHRIMP LARVAL FEED. Anisha Theres Cherian, Nivedya D, V. Ramabhai
48. Probiotic Properties of Bacillus subtilis Isolated from Dried Anchovies. Thejaswi Bhandary,
55. EXTENSION AND ECONOMICS. T. Mahesh, G. Dhanush, S. Vijay, S. Arun, N. Kishore, J. Selvanathan
62. A STUDY OF FISH SPECIES DIVERSITY IN PECHIPARAI RESERVOIR, NAGERCOIL, KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA. C. Mercy and A. Kohila
64. IMPACT OF MOBILE PHONE RADIATION IN IRIDESCENT SHARK, Pangasianodon hypophthalmus (Sauvage, 1878). Robin Joseva T and M. Raja
65. FRESH WATER ICTHYOPHIS DIVERSITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO A POND IN VATANAPPALLY, THRISSUR, KERALA. Sreeshna Binoy V and Dr. Praseeja Cheruparambath
68. IMPACT OF CHLORPYRIFOS TOXICITY ON EARLY EMBRYONIC DEVELOPMENT AND BEHAVIOR IN ZEBRAFISH (DANIO RERIO). C. Justin David and G. Adaikala Raj
69. LARVIVOROUS FISHES CONTROLLING MOSQUITO LARVAE. P.A.C.Kamatchi
76. OBSERVATION OF CHANGES IN BODY COLOURATION AND IMMUNE RESPONSE USING CUCUMBER AND GARLIC EXTRACT IN AQUARIUM FISH *Pethia conchonchius* (Rosy barb). Jeevitha lakshmi, S., Jeyavarshini, R., Monisha., R., Selvaraju Raja., Kalamani Velmurugan., Samynathan M.
89. SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FISH MUCUS NANOPARTICLES AND ITS ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY. Nukshitula Jamir
91. IDENTIFICATION OF VIBRIO SPECIES IN THE DISEASED *PENAEUS MONODON* ALONG THE COASTAL SYSTEM OF TAMIL NADU. Pavithra.B, Suganthi.R, Almas.R, Sugesh.S and Megavanan.R

92. STUDIES ON SUITABILITY OF ORNAMENTAL FISHES AND SPINACH IN THE AQUAPONICS SYSTEM. Karthika.E and Raja.S

93. FISH TOXICOLOGY- HAZARDOUS PHENOMENON. Sneha D.K

108. INVESTIGATION OF INVIVO TOXICITY ANALYSIS OF REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE NANOMATERIALS IN ZEBRAFISH. R.Monica,K.Sandhiya ,S.T.Nandhini

110. FRESH WATER ICTHYOPHIS DIVERSITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO A POND IN VATANAPPALLY, THRISSUR, KERALA. Sreeshna Binoy V and Dr. Praseeja Cheruparambath.

118. EFFECTS ON HEMATOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS TO AMMONIA EXPOSURE IN *PANGASIANODON HYPOPHthalmus* OF AQUARIUM FISHES .Navaneethan M and Raja Selvaraju*

ONLINE ORAL PRESENTATION -5

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Google Meet Link:

Chairperson : Dr.A.Bharathi, Assistant Professor, Department Of Zoology, Sir Theagaraya College, Chennai.

Co-Chairperson: Prof.M.Balachander, Assistant Professor, Department Of Zoology, Loyola College, Chennai.

SESSION-1

List of papers

2. NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF FOOD FISHES IN PECHIPARAI RESERVOIR, NAGERCOIL, KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT,TAMILNADU, INDIA. C. MERCY and A. KOHILA

5. GLOBAL DIVERSITY OF CLADOCERANS (CLADOCERA: CRUSTACEA) IN FRESH WATER WITH SPECIAL RELEVANCE TO FISH CULTURE. Renu, A., Rinaldin Aroma, S.,

6. ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL PROBIOTIC BACTERIA FROM THE INTESTINE OF *OREOCHROMIS NILOTICUS*, AND THE ASSESSMENT OF ITS ANTIBIOTIC AND ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTY. Sreelakshmi. K ,V. Ramasubramanian,Praseeja cheruparambath

7. A STUDY ON THE DIVERSITY OF MARINE FISHERIES AT MANAKUDY AND PALLAM COAST IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT C. Esaivani and R. Esani
8. ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICO - CHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN NAINARKULAM POND, TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA. B. Bindu Bennet and T.Deepakani
9. STUDIES ON THE BIVALVES DIVERSITY IN TUTICORIN, KAYALPATTINAM AND TIRUCHENDUR COAST OF TUTICORIN DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU. B. Bindu Bennet and T.Deepakani
13. A STUDY ON TRANSFORM OF FISHING HARBOUR BASED WASTE INTO POULTRY FEED: M.BALACHANDAR
- 16.MICROPLASTICS POLLUTION IN THE DIFFERENT TYPES OF AQUACULTURE SYSTEM WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SOURCE WATER . Ephsy K. Davis and S. Raja
19. EXPLORATION OF UNTAMED CATFISH (*Sperata aorides*) IN CAUVERY RIVER FROM ERODE DISTRICT . Yaswanthkumar S, Raja S and Kannan K.
21. POTENTIAL AND THERAPEUTIC VALUES OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN AQUACULTURE. Ashitha Raghu P K , Dr V. Krishnakumar
22. ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF AQUEOUS *CHAETOMORPHA ANTENNINA* EXTRACT ON GROWTH, BIOCHEMICAL, HAEMATO-IMMUNOLOGICAL, ANTIOXIDANT, IMMUNE RELATED GENES EXPRESSION IN TILAPIA, *OREOCHROMIS MOSSAMBICUS* AGAINST *AEROMONAS HYDROPHILA* . Sattanathan G, Padmapriya S.S and Balamuralikrishnan. B
27. CIRCUMONCHOBOTHRIUM HEMLATAE (REDESCRIBE) CESTODE PARASITE IN FRESHWATER FISH FROM PARBHANI (M.S) INDIA. Deshmukh Shaziya Sultana K.A
30. IMMUNOMODULATION OF CANTHAXANTHIN ENRICHED DIET TO LACTOCOCCOSIS IN FLATHEAD GREY MULLET, *MUGIL CEPHALUS* . Ramasamy Harikrishnan, Gunapathy Devi, Hiram
34. A STUDY ON DIVERSITY AND SEASONAL VARIATION OF HILL-STREAM FISHES IN LONGNIT RIVER, KARBI ANGLONG, ASSAM Dr. Susmita Dey, Jyoti Agrahari

35. DIVERSITY OF THE DIMINUTIVE SISORID CATFISH OF THE GENUS *PSEUDOLAGUVIA* (TELEOSTEI: SILURIFORMES) IN THE NORTHEASTERN INDIA. Yumnam Lokeshwor Singh

36. OCCURENCE OF THE AMAZON SAILFIN CATFISH *PTERYGOPLICHTHYS PARDALIS* (SILURIFORMES: LORICARIIDAE), AN ALIEN AQUARIUM FISH INVASION IN KERALA WATERS . V. Veena , G. Sasikala and Selvaraju Raja

40. FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PLANT, ANIMAL, AND PROBIOTIC BASED FISH MEALS AND EVALUATING THEIR EFFICACY ON GROWTH AND PERFORMANCE IN ZEBRAFISH (*DANIO RERIO*). Riya Ann Samuel, Suravi Sasmita Dash, Riyaz Ali.L, Kuppusamy Alagesan Paari

41. TROUT FARMING: POTENTIAL IN UTTARAKHAND STATE WITH EMPHASIS ON HARVESTING AND POST HARVESTING TECHNOLOGIES. Anuharika Chauhan

ONLINE ORAL PRESENTATION -6

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Google Meet Link:

Chairperson : Dr.P.Stalin, Assistant Professor, Erode Arts College, Erode

Co-Chairperson: Dr.Chitra Assistant Professor, Erode Arts College, Erode

SESSION – 2

42. EFFICACY OF PROBIOTIC BACTERIA *BACILLUS MEGATERIUM* ON GROWTH, SURVIVAL AND DISEASE RESISTANCE IN WHITE SHRIMP *LITOPENAEUS VANNAMEI* POSTLARVAE. Vennila Jayaprakash and Arulvasu Chinnasamy

44. FISHERY RESOURCES, FEEDING HABITS OF *Gerres erythrourus* FISH FROM PUDUCHERRY ESTUARY THENGAITHITTU. D.Muruganandam, V.Muthuviveganandavel, A.Premkumar

45. ENHANCEMENT OF INNATE IMMUNE SYSTEM, SURVIVAL AND YIELD IN *Oreochromis sp* USING FERMENTED SEA WEEDS ISOLATED FROM COASTAL REGIONS OF MANDAPAM CAMP. Christine Kurian, Paari K A
46. ASSESSMENT OF AQUATIC MACROPHYTES IN DAKKARKULAM, KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, SOUTH INDIA. Iswarya . S., Mary kensa V. and Kavitha. A.
47. INVESTIGATION OF MICROPLASTICS IN THE COMMON FISHES OF RIVER GANGA (UTTARAKHAND). Dr. Jaspal Singh Chauhan
54. BIOSYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, ANTIMICROBIAL AND FREE RADICAL SCAVENGING APPLICATION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES USING MARINE MACRO ALGA, *Caulerpa racemos* .Adaikala Raj G, Justin David Clifton and Gnana surya
56. OPTIMIZATION OF PH AND TEMPERATURE FOR AQUAPONICS . Stella Bai D., Mary Mettilda Bai S., Vinoliya Josephine Mary J. & Citarasu T
57. AQUAPONICS - AN ALTERNATIVE ENTERPRISE FOR PRODUCTION OF GENETICALLY IMPROVED FARMED TILAPIA *Oreochromis niloticus* and Spinach. JoeRini, Sandhiya.S, M.Balachandar, E. Hino Fernando
59. DISTRIBUTION AND EFFECT OF ALGAE ON FRESH WATER AND MARINE WATERS OF KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU. Satheesh Kumar, B., Renu, A., BalaSarada
60. COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY DURING FALL SEASON AT UKKADAM AND KURICHILAKES, COIMBATORE. M. Nalini
61. IMPACT OF MONOCHROTOPHOS ON HAEMOGLOBIN LEVEL IN ANABAS SCANDEN .A. Bharathi
63. WATER QUALITY STATUS OF PERUNGULAM PONDS IN TUTICORIN DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU. Viji Margaret I and Babitha R
66. ICHTHYOFAUNAL BIODIVERSITY OF VILLAGE POND KHERTHADISTT. BALOD CHHATTISGARH. Yaser Qureshi
67. IMPACT OF ASPARTAME ON GILL TISSUE TRANSAMINASE ACTIVITY IN *Labeo rohita*. Muthuviveganandavel .V , Arsha.B , Premkumar. A
70. STUDY OF BIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF FRESHWATER COPEPODS AND CYCLOPOIDS. Manikandan Kumaresan and A. Bharathi

- 72.OBSERVATION OF AQUATIC ORGANISMS IN THE RELATION TO BIRDS' POPULATION IN THE NILGIRIS RESERVOIRS. Ranjitha Jayaraman, Selvaraju Raja, Ramakrishnan Balasundaram, Babu. S and Samynathan. M
75. THE EFFICIENCY OF REVERSE OSMOSIS AND BAMBOO FILTRATION SYSTEMS FOR THE AQUARIUM FISHES MANAGEMENT. Navaneethan M and Raja Selvaraju
77. STUDY ON THE ICHTHYOFAUNAL DIVERSITY OF CHETTUVA BACKWATERS, THRISSUR, KERALA. Savitha nandan & Famil.A.V

ONLINE ORAL PRESENTATION -7

25/03/2022 Time :2.00 PM

Google Meet Link:

Chairperson : **Dr.M.Samynathan**, Asst.Professor, Dept. of Zoology
Kongundau Arts and Science College, Coimabtoe.

Co-Chairperson: Dr.Yamuna Ramakrishan ,Asst.Professor,
Dept.of. Zoology, PSGR Krishnammal College,
Coimbatore

SESSION-3

78. WATER QUALITY AND SOIL MANAGEMENT OF FISHPONDS. J.Selvanathan ,S. Vincent
80. STUDIES ON AQUATIC FLORAL DIVERSITY IN THREE PERENNIAL PONDS OF MIDALAM PANCHAYAT AT KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT.. Santhiya and R. Mahesh
81. TAXONOMIC FEATURES OF COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE SELECTED ORNAMENTAL FISHES. Sandhiya.S, Joe Rini.E, M.Balachandar.
82. A STUDY ON THE EXISTENCE OF *Artemia parthenogenetica* IN THE SALTPANS OF KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT. S.Soniya, M. Michael Babu, Dr. R.AnanthaRajan and S. Mary Josephine Punitha.
83. TYPES OF FISH BREEDING AND THEIR IMPORTANCE. Bhawna Srivastava
84. ACUTE TOXICITY OF HEAVY METAL, ZINC CHLORIDE IN INDIAN MAJOR CARPS. BlessyGraciah and Viji Margaret I
85. EFFECT OF DIFFERENT DIETARY INCLUSION LEVELS OF BLUE GREEN ALGAE SPIRULINA (*Spirulina platensis*) ON THE FOOD UTILIZATION *Cirrhinus mrigala Fingerlings* . Dr.A.S.Santhalakshmi, Dr.P.Kombiah

- 88.A STUDY ON THE DIVERITY OF BRACHYURAN CRABS IN TIRUCHENDUR COAST. C.Esaivani and C.M.Muthuselvi
90. AEROMONAS INFECTION AND ITS PREVENTIVE MEASURES IN FISH FARMING. L.Mohanasundari and G.B.Brindha Devi
94. COPEFLOC BASED NURSERY REARING OF P.VANNAMEI AND ITS COMPARATIVE GROWTH PERFORMANCE DURING GROW-OUT FARMING. R.Aravind, P.S.Shyne Anand, I.F.Biju, N.S.Sudheer, A.Panigrahi, S.Rajamanickam and C.P.Balasubramanian
96. ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF PROBIOTIC BACTERIA *BACILLUS* SPECIES FROM GUT OF INDIAN MAJOR CARP *LABEO ROHITA* (HAMILTON, 1822) . Dr. S. Jayaprakash¹ Dr. K. Parvathi.
99. EFFECT OF DIETARY SUPPLEMENTATION OF AQUATIC WEED *PISTIA STRATIOTES* ON SPECIFIC AND NON-SPECIFIC IMMUNITY IN TILAPIA, *OREOCHROMIS MOSSAMBICUS* AGAINST *Aeromonas hydrophila* .Palesinuo and Sattanathan G.
100. ASSESSMENT OF ZOOPLANKTON DIVERSITY AT SETTI LAKE, IDAPPADI IN SALEM DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA. S.uthirasamy and T.chitra,
101. ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BACTERIA FROM TANNERY EFFLUENT TREATMENT PLANT AND THEIR TOLERANCE TO HEAVY METALS. S. Ravichandiran*¹, T. Chitra² and S.Uthirasamy³
102. A STUDY ON PHYSICO CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND BIO DIVERSITY OF THE VANIYAR DAM AT VENKATASAMUTHIRAM, DHARMAPURI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU. S.Suresh*¹ and T.Chitra², And S.Uthirasamy
103. ASSESSMENT OF PHYTOPLANKTON DIVERSITY AT PERIYA SADAYAMPALAYAM POND, IN ERODE DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA. T.Chitra¹, T.Ashok kumar^{2*} and S.Uthirasamy
107. ICHTHYOFAUNAL BIODIVERSITY OF VILLAGE POND KHERTHA DISTT. BALOD CHHATTISGARH .Yaser Qureshi
109. A STUDY ON COLLECTED SEAWEEDS FROM RASTHAKADU COAST NEAR KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA. D. C. Anushiya , M. Mathavan pillai and R. Mahesh.

International Conference on “Recent Trends in Aquaculture”

Keynote address

Palavesam A

*UGC-BSR Faculty, Former Professor & Head, Department of Animal Science,
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli*

Abstract

Aquaculture has become a popular subsector, complement to agriculture and has become the fastest growing food industry in the world with the greatest potential to meet the growing demand of aquatic food. During the past decade, this industry has witnessed rapid development and plays an important role in the national economy through providing protein rich materials to the undernourished population, employment to the skilled and unskilled labourers and also earning foreign exchange through export. Available statistics on world fisheries and aquaculture production indicated that inland and marine aquaculture altogether contributes 43% in total fisheries production. Aquaculture production alone is considered, China stands first followed by India, Vietnam, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Norway and Thailand. The success of aquaculture depends on environmental and biological factors inclusive of health status of the farmed animals. Globally aquaculture is expanding into new directions of intensifying and diversifying. However, with the adaptations of intensive and super-intensive farming of aquaculture, stress is imported on the farmed animals. Stress from the immediate environment is being considered as the major causative factor for both primary and secondary infections, which will alternatively led to disease outbreak. In aquaculture industry, bacterial and viral diseases are considered as the major death blow for its sustained production. Furthermore, the economic loss due to disease outbreak is immeasurable and also unbearable. Considering its impact on sustainable aquaculture farming, search towards identifying appropriate technologies is proposed as the prime area of the aquaculture research all over the world. The more recent techniques which are being implemented in aquaculture industry for its sustainability and optimal production are: functional feed formulation, immune modulators, probiotics and prebiotics, synbiotics, innovative disease diagnostic methods, aquaponics, Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) and Biofloc Technology. To add further, biotechnological innovations such as Nanotechnology, Metabolomics and Nutrigenomics are also in pipeline to boost the aquaculture industry towards sustainability. Additionally in recent time attention is also being focused on the production of climate change resistance organisms, algal oil production (microalgal oil), kelp farming, sea urchin production and open ocean aquaculture with main aim of enhancing aquaculture production in a sustainable way.

Breeding and Seed production of Snakehead fishes, (*Channa striatus*, *Channa punctatus*) and African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*)

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Abstract

World aquaculture has been growing steadily in many countries, mainly due to the advances in the management of fish cultivation to cope with the increasing worldwide demand for fish as well as the economic and environmental sustainability of fish farming. During the past decade, the culture of air-breathing fish species has been increased dramatically and is now a significant global source of protein for human consumption. Several species of air-breathing fish species are now farmed extensively including snakehead fishes *Channa spp*, striped catfish *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*, pangas catfish; *Pangasius pangasius*, catfishes; and *Clarias spp*. Among the air-breathing fishes, Snakehead fishes, (*Channa striatus*, and *Channa punctatus*) and African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) is highly prized freshwater fishes. They are well known for taste, high nutritive value, recuperative and medicinal qualities. Still, the culture of snakeheads is not common due to the lack of seed production and knowledge of larval rearing, feeding, and breeding techniques among the farmers in India and Malaysia.

The most important criteria for successful propagation of any cultivable fish species in aquaculture is the availability of sufficient quantity larvae of uniform size, quality, and free of diseases, parasites, and pests at the time of stocking in culture ponds. Traditional methods of induced spawning for fish are based on the injection of gonadotropic hormones from different sources, including extract of carp pituitary gland, partially purified fish gonadotropic hormones, and mammalian gonadotropic hormones, especially human chorionic gonadotropin (HCG). Several synthetic analogues of gonadotropin-releasing hormones (GnRH) and preparations have been used in fish breeding and seed production in different fish species.

GnRH and its super-active analogues have been used in snakeheads and catfish breeding. Such treatment results in the release of the fish's gonadotropin. The use of natural and synthetic hormones in the induction of spawning and seed production in air-breathing fishes is well documented. The present review will highlight the published results of breeding and seed production methods of snakehead fishes, (*Channa striatus*, *Channa punctatus*) and African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) using natural and synthetic hormones used in India and Malaysia.

Keywords: Breeding; Snakehead fishes; *Channa striatus*; *Channa punctatus*; and African catfish; *Clarias gariepinus*

Tilapia culture: Global view

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Abstract

The total population of the world is expected to be 9.3 billion by 2050. In the over populated world, it will be a major challenge to full fill the basic human needs for animal protein sources. Fish is the prominent source of animal protein supply for humans but there is a rapid decrease in wild fish stocks due to overfishing. Therefore, the future fish supply will depend only on sustainable aquaculture. Currently, tilapias are one of the most widely introduced fish in the global market for future aquaculture. These fish are of great interest in the field because of their high growth rates, adaptability to a wide range of environmental conditions, ability to grow and reproduce in captivity and feed on low tropic levels. Strikingly these fish have become an excellent candidate for aquaculture, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. Tilapia is also the second most farmed fish worldwide and its production has increased four times over the past decade because of its suitability for aquaculture, marketability and stable market prices. Tilapia culture has been expanding rapidly and is now practised in more than 140 countries worldwide. Moreover, in 2020, the production grew to 6 million tonnes at a growth rate of above 7% and the global tilapia market reached a value of US\$ 7.9 Billion. In my talk, I'll focus on the global view of tilapia production, tilapia cultivation techniques.

Keywords: Fish, Tilapia, Cultivation techniques

Aquaponics: sustainable production system for food security

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Abstract

Worldwide the human population are facing one of the greatest challenges to meet nutritional needs in future. To meet the food demands imposed by the nearly 30% population increase, global food production has to increase by as much as 50% (FAO, 2017). Food production will be challenged by factors such as climate change, pollution and degradation of agricultural lands. Aquaponics emerges as a key technology with the potential to transform agriculture and enhance food security in the wake of climate change, particularly in dry regions. Aquaponics in one form or another has been practised for centuries in several countries but the technology still remains less popular compared to traditional food production methods and is largely practised by individuals. The "zero waste" system, can be considered one of the major trends for the future development of integrated culture. It greatly reduces the use of water (90% of water is recycled by the plants and returned to the fish tank) and soilless culture system, yields fresh and highly nutritious crops like vegetables, fruits and fish. Aquaponic systems in an urban environment will provide the residents with fresh fish and vegetables with more sustainable and compensate for the local food needs. Along with liquid fertilizer of seaweeds, significant results attained with expected growth in various plants at our experimental lab when the lower concentration of micro and macronutrients, this recirculatory system will support to produce a different layer of high-quality edible foods for all. This promising technology may be suitable for sustainable agriculture food productions when uncertain climatic factors. Recently, the Marine and Brackishwater aquaponics systems significantly increases the potential fish species that could be raised, and many of the potential species have huge demand in the marketplace. Further, marine aquaponics reduces the reliance on freshwater resources. This technology is usually preferred as a solution for efficiently using marginal lands in urban and rural areas for food production. Hence, widely the people need to adopt for an eco-friendly and sustainable food productions aquaponics system are needed to reduce rural poverty and enhance food security.

Keywords: Food security, Aquaponics, Fishes, Plants and Nutrients

β -1,3 glucan binding protein (β -GBP) mediated cellular immune responses in the marine mussel, *Perna viridis*

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Abstract

Innate immune system of invertebrates plays a vital role in defense against pathogens. In higher invertebrates such as arthropods and molluscs, circulating blood cells or hemocytes are the primary effector cells of cellular immune reactions leading to hemolymph coagulation, phagocytosis, encapsulation, nodulation and extracellular cytotoxicity. The circulatory system of bivalve molluscs contains almost three distinct types of hemocytes namely, agranular, semi granular and granular hemocytes known to perform various defense functions. The molecules that enhance the phagocytic activity performed by the circulating blood cells or hemocytes are called as opsonins. The lectin/agglutinin that mediate the recognition and enhanced engulfment of foreign substances is called opsono-phagocytosis. β -Glucan Binding Protein (β -GBP) is a multifunctional protein capable of specific binding to the polymers of β -1, 3 Glucans. The opsonin mediated cellular immune reactions potentiate the recognition of non-self and one such opsonin is the β -1,3 GBP. We have recently shown, *for the first time* in a bivalve mollusc, the detection, isolation and purification of β -1,3 GBP in the plasma of the marine mussel *P. viridis* and demonstrated its role in a non-self-induced activation of plasma prophenoloxidase system (*proPO*). There, are also evidences provided for its ability to function as an opsonin during phagocytosis of trypsinized yeast cells by the hemocytes of *P. viridis*. In a previous study from our very own laboratory (Laboratory of Pathobiology, Department of Zoology, University of Madras), we have purified β -1, 3 GBP from the plasma of marine mussel *P. viridis* and indicated that it may serve as an opsonin by facilitating hemocyte-mediated phagocytic and encapsulation responses. However, the presence of receptors for β -GBP on hemocyte surfaces remains to be demonstrated not only in molluscs but also in most of the other invertebrates. Molluscs possess different types of cells or hemocytes, and they exhibit variations based on surface receptor characteristics and cytoplasmic granularity. However, it is not known whether all types of hemocytes possess receptors for β -GBP or phagocytic effect or it is restricted to any specific morphotype. Hence, we hypothesize that hemocyte – mediated cellular immune responses in molluscs are facilitated by interaction of β -GBP with various hemocyte morphotypes that can possibly be defined by the presence and abundance of β -GBP-receptors on each hemocyte surface.

Keywords:

**Morphometric studies and Nutritional composition of Indian saltwater rotifer,
Brachionus species (Rotifera: Monogononta)**

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Abstract

The rotifer (*Brachionus plicatilis* Muller) was cultured by feeding on phytoplankton monocultures (*Nannochloropsis* sp. and *Isochrysis galbana*), mixed algal cultures (*Nannochloropsis* sp. + *Isochrysis galbana*; at 1:1 ratio), and a probiotic culture (*Nannochloropsis* sp. + *Bacillus licheniformis* MTCC 6824 at 1:1 ratio). Morphological potential studies revealed that taxonomic characters were constant enough to recognize and well-defined with regard to ecological preferences these rotifers. The tropical marine *Brachionus* strains are distinguished by their lorica size and shape Based on morphological features the morphometric data revealed that taxonomic characters were constant enough to recognize and well-defined morphologies. In the present study the rotifer species, maximum lorica length of $96.13 \pm 7.7 \mu\text{m}$ was measured. Biochemical compositions of rotifers fed on different diets were determined on day 4 of the culture.

Protein and total lipid levels were the maximum when fed with *I. galbana* ($46.02 \pm 0.226\%$ and $36.1 \pm 0.07\%$ respectively). Though dry matter content was the highest in the probiotic culture ($5.4 \pm 0.1\%$), ash free dry weight was the highest for those fed with *Nannochloropsis* sp. Carbohydrate was the highest ($14.62 \pm 0.1\%$) in rotifers fed with *Nannochloropsis* sp. Total amino acids excluding tryptophan was found to be 28.93 g 100 g rotifer-1 when fed with *Nannochloropsis* sp. The maximum energy content per gram dry rotifer sample was 17.61 Kcal when fed with *Nannochloropsis* sp. Rotifer density, lipid, carbohydrate and protein content of rotifers fed with *I. galbana* and *Nannochloropsis* sp. indicate that these are the most suitable diets for the rotifer.

Keywords: *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Brachionus* sp, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., Natural diets

Advanced technologies in aquaculture

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Abstract

Aquaculture also includes the production of shellfish, crustaceans and algae. Both of these are important sources of human nutrition and molecular constituents for the pharmaceutical industry. Increasing demand for fish puts pressure on resources and sustainable practices in the fishery industry, requiring innovative use of existing and new technologies. Fortunately, especially with the advent of technology, there is great potential for the sustainable production of this protein source. The aquaculture industry has been around for 4,000 years and the industry is still young and growing. She has a lot to learn from livestock and has some challenges to overcome. Examples: disease control, mild production, feed and nutrition. But advanced technology has helped. The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) has opened up favorable opportunities for improving efficiency and maintaining the health of aquatic life. In addition to the IoT, five key innovations are ready to revolutionize the aquaculture industry. As with other agricultural industries, the technology introduced in aquaculture is the focus of interest for farmers and their investors. Offshore aquaculture and land recirculation aquaculture system (RAS). There are many techniques for offshore aquaculture production, including cage aquaculture (A). Diving cage (B); Ship farming (C); Fish farm permanently fixed in the deep sea (D).

Studies on physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton diversity of Poigai reservoir in Kanyakumari District

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Abstract

The study was conducted at the experimental sites of Poigai Reservoir in Kanyakumari district at a period of four months (December 2019 to March 2020). The study encompassed collection of data pertaining to various aspects such as physico-chemical parameters of the water samples and phytoplankton analysis. In the present study the pH values ranged from a minimum of 6.9 in December month (S₂) to the maximum of 7.8 in February (S₁). The water temperature varied from 27.5 °C to 31 °C in the experimental sites. Dissolved oxygen content showed that highest peak value was recorded during the month of December in S₂ (5.07 mg/L) and least in the month of March (1.40 mg/L) in S₁. The low concentration of biological oxygen demand was reported in the month of December (1.97 mg/L) and the level reached maximum of (7.04 mg/L) during the month of March. High temperatures do play an important role by increasing rate of oxidation. In the present investigation diatoms (Bacillariophyta) dominated over green algae (chlorophyta), blue greens (Cyanophyta) and euglenoids (Euglenophyta). Among the two sites, contributed maximum percentages of diatom members and monthly observation highlighted that the contribution was maximum during rainy season in both the ponds. It was mainly because of high dissolved oxygen and maximum temperature in the water bodies. A total of 63 algal taxa were observed in the study periods. Out of the total species 26 belonging to Bacillariophyta, 18 species belonging to Chlorophyta, 14 species belonging to Cyanophyta and 5 species belonging to Euglenophyta.

Keywords: Poigai Reservoir, Green algae, Cyanophyta, Euglenophyta

Nutritional value of food fishes in Pechiparai reservoir, Nagercoil, Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

The proximate composition of fish nutritional value of food fish species in Pechiparai reservoir was investigated from June – November 2021. Estimation of nutrition profile of edible fishes is essential and thus a bio-monitoring study was carried out to find out the nutritional composition of commonly available fishes in Pechiparai reservoir. Moisture, protein, fat and ash composition in the muscle of six edible fish species were studied. Proximate analysis revealed that the moisture, protein, fat and ash contents were high in *Oreochromis niloticus* (82.33%), followed by *Mystus gulio* (76.22%), *Ctenopharyngoden idella* (74.98%), *Cirrhinus mrigala* (74.02%), *Etroplus maculatus* (69.40%) and *Etroplus suratensis* (62.78%). The maximum protein was found in the species of *Etroplus suratensis* (24.30%). The highest fat content was noticed in grass carp (5.90%), the highest ash content found in *Etroplus maculatus* (6.88%). Hence, the fishes of Pechiparai reservoir are highly recommended for consumption and so these fishes are highly enriched with nutrition. The results can be used as a baseline data for comparing the various nutritional profiles of fishes in future.

Keywords: Nutrition profile, Edible fishes, Pechiparai reservoir, Fish diversity, consumption.

Effects of probiotic *Lactobacillus* on the growth performance and haematological profile of *Catla catla* juveniles

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Abstract

Fish nutrition plays an important part in aquaculture which stimulate fish growth and health benefit. Feeding of enriched diet with all nutrients has assumed most importance in fish culture. The high-quality feeds, contain various additional compounds are incorporated into fish feed. The supplements diet with nutrient are keep the fish healthy. Probiotics is new technique to utilize the maximum fish feed ingredients and improve water quality, growth and healthy fish. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) have been used as probiotics due to their properties of anti bacterial activity against pathogens. In general, Indian major carp *Catla catla* were mostly affected by motile *Aeromonas* group, especially *Aeromonous hydrophila*. In this study the role of selected microorganism on fish growth and water quality as well as to find out the hematological responsiveness of *Catla catla* treated with the pathogenic bacteria *A. hydrophila*. The sixty-day feeding trial of *C. catla* with a *Lactobacillus* probiotic mixture feed showed excellent outcomes in growth performance as well as enhanced hematological parameters.

Keywords: *Catla catla*, *Aeromonous hydrophila*, Probiotics, hematological parameters

Biodiversity on freshwater rotifers in relation to physico-chemical parameters of Veinthankulam pond and Palayam canal

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Abstract

The research work carried out to identify the diversity, morphology, species richness of the fresh water rotifers. Zooplankton are the free floating and microscopic animal found in aquatic ecosystem. The zooplankton are important for fishes as they are used as source of food. Zooplankton community fluctuates according to physicochemical parameter of the environment especially rotifer species change with biotic factors. It may serve as indicators of water quality. They are globally recognized as pollution indicator organisms in the aquatic environment. The Veinthankulam pond and Palayam canal were selected for the present day study and belong to lentic and lotic freshwater in Tirunelveli District. Zooplankton collections were made from litoral surface water column in different stations of each freshwater habitat. Identification of zooplankton species were done by under light microscope. Water samples were collected in the chosen study area in a clean iodine treated polyvinyl chloride container. The collected water samples were analysing the following physical and chemical parameters such as turbidity, pH, total dissolved oxygen, electro conductivity and total alkalinity using standard methods. The collected rotifer species were subjected to diversity analysis using different indices like Shanon – Weiner index and Simpson's index. A total of the occurrence of 11 genera belonging to 8 families have been identified. Among the collected species, Brachionus was most abundance in Veinthankulam pond and Palayam canal during the study period besides the species *Keratella*, *Filinia*, *Lecane*, *Conochilus*, *Rotaria* and *Philodina* species. The maximum temperature was recorded during February and lower temperature was recorded during December. The highest pH value was recorded during January and the lowest pH value was recorded in February. The chlorinity and salinity values are high during February and lower during January. The amount of dissolved oxygen is more in Veinthankulam pond and Palayam canal during February.

Keywords: Rotifer species, Veinthankulam pond, Palayam canal, water quality analysis, Diversity indices.

Global diversity of cladocerans (Cladocera: Crustacea) in freshwater with special relevance to fish culture

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Abstract

Cladocerans are well represented in freshwater plankton, but only a few species are found in brackish waters and fewer still in the sea. Cladocera is a primarily-freshwater monophyletic organisms, and also an important component of micro crustacean zooplankton. Our knowledge of this group from the Indian waters is less when compared globally. They reported more abundantly in both temporary and permanent stagnant waters. Although cladocerans are among the commonest of freshwater micro crustaceans, their taxonomy is not adequately studied and more particularly that of tropical Cladocera. Cladocera is an ancient most group of Palaeozoic origin. About 1000 species are currently known, many more species are unidentified but we analyse that the reported number of species is 2–5times higher than older studies and are drawn by using camera lucida. A number of currently-recognised widespread species can be expected to climatic diversity.

Keywords: Cladocera, Microcrustaceans, taxonomy, global diversity, camera lucida.

Isolation and identification of potential probiotic bacteria from the intestine of *Oreochromis niloticus*, and the assessment of its antibiotic and antibacterial property

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Abstract

Probiotics are defined as the live microbial supplement that improves the host intestinal microbial balance. So here, the aim of the study is to screen and identify potential lactic acid bacteria from *Oreochromis niloticus*. The strain was cultured on De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe agar at 37 °C. Identification were done based on the morphological and biochemical analysis such as Gram's staining, catalase test, oxidase test, Motility test, citrate utilization test, methyl red test, starch hydrolysis test etc. Molecular identification were done after DNA isolation followed by PCR, and 16S rRNA sequencing. *Weissella confusa* strain is obtained from the gut region of the fish after phenotypic and genotypic identification. When the antibiotic susceptibility of isolated LAB were evaluated using ampicillin, gentamicin, penicillin, vancomycin and cefadroxil, *Weissella confusa* shows higher resistance to ampicillin, gentamicin, penicillin, cefadroxil but sensitive to vancomycin. And also it shows high spectrum of antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* and *K. pneumoniae*.

Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria, Probiotic, *Weissella confusa*, antibiotic susceptibility

A study on the diversity of marine fisheries at Manakudy and Pallam coast in Kanyakumari district

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to find the diversity and abundance of fishes in the selected coastal areas namely Manakudy and Pallam in Kanyakumari district for a period of 4 months that is from August 2021 to November 2021. A total of 30 species belonging to 17 families were observed family Carangidae contained highest number of species (10) followed by Serranidae (3), Scombridae and Sphyraenidae containing (2) each respectively. Highest number of species were recorded in Manakudy (21 species) and the least number of species were recorded in Pallam (17 species). Shannon index showed the similar trend and ranged from 2.15 to 2.61 and Simpson index ranged from 0.83 to 0.89. The highest diversity was observed during the month of August and the lowest diversity was observed during November. The study thus reveals that decrease in the diversity of species may be due to human interference and pollution which should be prevented.

Keywords: Marine fisheries, fish diversity, conservation.

Assessment of physico-chemical parameters in Nainarkulam pond, Tirunelveli district, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

Water quality parameters analysis is essential and this information is highly helpful to aware about the contamination of water. The study period was started from May 2018 to October 2018. Water samples were collected from the Nainarkulam Pond during the study period. Depending upon the availability, water samples were collected from the pond with clean plastic bottles at 6.00 am and brought to the laboratory for further Physical and chemical analysis. The aim of the present investigation is to determine the quality of water. Water parameters like temperature, free CO₂, pH, EC, alkalinity, hardness, chloride, TDS, DO and BOD were analyzed and found variations throughout the study period, most of the physico-chemical variables were within the criteria prescribed by BIS and WHO. Parameters like DO and TDS exceeds the maximum permissible by WHO. So the pond water is not used for drinking purpose and is only suitable for irrigation. Anthropogenic activities are the prime source for this change.

Key words: Physico –chemical parameters, Water Quality, Analysis and Maximum.

Studies on the bivalves diversity in Tuticorin, Kayalpattinam and Tiruchendur coast of Tuticorin district, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The present investigation was started from August 2021 to November 2021 to find out the diversity and abundance of bivalves shell in three stations namely Kayalpattinam, Thiruchendur and Tuticorin coast. Bivalves species were collected by hand picking method. During the study 26 species 8 families with 2,699 individual numbers of bivalves mollusca were recorded. In Tuticorin coast 3 families with 9 species were recorded, In Kayalpattinam 6 families with 11 species were recorded. In Tiruchendur 4 families with 6 species were recorded. Maximum number species were recorded in Kayalpattinam coast and minimum were in Tiruchendur. Out of 8 families Veneridae family are common in all the three stations. Diversity was calculated by using Shannon wiener diversity index. Maximum diversity was recorded in Tuticorin and Minimum diversity was recorded in Tiruchendur due to beach area. The molluscs have a tremendous impact on Indian traditional and economy. So conservation of molluscs shell is very important.

Keywords: Mollusca, Species diversity, Gastropods, Conservation, Thiruchendur coast.

DETECTION OF VIBRIO SPECIES IN THE DISEASED *PENAEUS VANNAMEI* ALONG
THE COASTAL SYSTEM OF TAMILNADU

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Shrimp culture is the fast growing sector in food production. Various biological and non-biological agents are responsible for causing disease outbreaks in shrimp culture industry. Vibriosis has been considered as the severest and causes 100% mortalities. Hence attempt has been made to survey the pathogenic *Vibrio*'s in natural *Penaeus Vannamei* collected from the coastal system of Tamilnadu. The samples were collected from 10 places of coastal system of Tamilnadu. The diseased region was plated on TCBS agar and subjected to various biochemical tests. The result of biochemical tests were compared with Bergey's manual of determinative bacteriology identification of *Vibrio* species. The isolate were characterized out of two different places surveyed, Portononva was founded to be the dominant place of *Vibrio* infection in *Penaeus Vannamei* and was followed by Muthupettai, Samiyarpettai and Pudukkuppam. Out of 43 isolates *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* was found to be the dominant flora (21%) and was followed by *Vibrio cholera* (13.9%).

KEY WORDS: *Vibrio* sp, *Penaeus Vannamei*, portonova, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*

Effect of fruit peels waste on growth of the common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) fingerlings

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Abstract

India is one of the leading fruits production country in the world. Fruits produces more amount of fruit peel waste as solid waste in the environment. The biodegradable municipal waste (BMW) of India represents 60–70% of municipal solid waste which has 40–50% of degradable organic waste contains food and garden waste. Nowadays, the fruit peel wastes used as animal feed is an alternative one which reducing the cost of animal production. The main drawbacks of using fruit peel waste in animal diets is extremely variable depending on the area of production and season on animal production. The fruit peel waste has enormous amount of carbohydrate, protein, minerals, lipid and vitamins. This may be utilized in the aquaculture for fish production. In this study, it is planned to incorporate the high energy giving fruit peel waste in the fish feed and enhance the growth of fish. The common carp *Cyprinus carpio* L. is one of the most important culturable freshwater fish all around the world. In the present study, the pomegranate, orange, lemon and banana peel waste is used as supplementary feed for growth kinetics of fish. The growth response to the various concentration of fruit peel waste on the growth performance of *Cyprinus carpio* fingerlings is analysed. The optimal replacement levels of pomegranate, orange, lemon and banana peel in diets of *Cyprinus carpio* fingerlings is assessed and find out the best fruit peel waste as supplement feed among pomegranate, orange, lemon and banana peel in diets of fingerlings.

Keywords: *Cyprinus carpio* L, fry feeds, biodegradable waste, optimal replacement levels, growth enhancement.

Proximate composition of selected green algal *Codium* species

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Abstract

Population growth combined with increasingly limited resources in arable land and water has led to a need for alternative protein sources. Marine algae are the important sources of biologically active compounds and have a nutritive potential. This study was determine the proximate composition of *Codium arabicum* Kuetzing, *Codium decortdatum* (Woodward) M.A.Howe and *Codium tomentosum* Stackhouse collected from the intertidal region of Ramanathapuram coastal region in the south east coast of Tamil Nadu, India. The proximate analysis includes the content of total protein, total carbohydrate, total fiber and total lipid. Among these three species, *Codium tomentosum* had the maximum Carbohydrate content (38.70%) and *Codium arabicum* had rich in protein content (5.86%), fiber content (3.48%) and lipid content (4.36%) for 100 mg of dry weight analysis. *Codium decortdatum* had the minimum carbohydrate content (36.43%) and protein content (5.17%) and *Codium tomentosum* had the least amount of lipid content (2.35%) and fiber content (2.48%) for 100 mg of dry weight analysis. This study can assist algae growers and processors in selecting the most suitable algae species for food or feed applications.

Keywords: Proximate composition, Macro algae, Ramanathapuram Coastal Region

A study on transform of fishing harbour based waste into poultry feed

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Abstract

The world's population is projected to grow from about 7 billion in 2012 to 9.6 billion people by 2050. An increase in consumption of eggs, meat, growing demand for other products, and an increase in oilseed production factors are driving the global animal feed industry these trends will lead to higher requirements for processed dairy, aqua, and poultry products; in turn leading to a trigger for higher feed requirement. Fish waste is very rich in protein we can make it into supplements for animal feed. "Low value/trash fish" is a loosely used term that describes fish species with various characteristics but they are generally small in size, have low consumer preference and have little or no direct commercial value. Many countries report that some low value/trash fish are used as direct feeds for livestock and aquaculture. In this study we investigated quantity and the types of fish used as trash and feed for poultry. Chickens fed with fish supplement make much richer eggs. This product can also be used as fish feed in fish farms. It can be added to smoked cow bones, oyster shells, palm nut, groundnut, maize and semolina to make high-protein animal feed. In this present study, we surveyed Kasimedu fishing harbour Chennai, the fish trash garbage and calculated the fish waste conversion into poultry feed. Complete fish or unwanted fish pieces have dried and grind in the form of powder to obtain Fish meal. Hence, we found that the formation of animal feed from unwanted products of seafood is very beneficial for reducing environmental pollution and for providing cheap production of animals.

Keywords: Kasimedu, fishing harbour, fish waste, poultry feed

Cobitid fishes in the Brahmaputra and the Chindwin river basins of northeastern India

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Abstract

The cobitid fishes, often called spined loaches, are freshwater fish with both ornamental and food values. They are easily distinguished due to the presence of a sub-orbital spine and represent a total of 18 genera and 227 species globally, out of which the Northeastern India harbours 10 species under 5 genera. They show a great diversity and polymorphism in the number of barbels, the blotches on the body, and the presence and absence of ocellus on the caudal fin. Some of the species under this group are facing taxonomic ambiguity due to lack of evidence of the representative species, polymorphic forms and increasing threats to the species due to habitat degradation and fragmentation. In view of this, the current study has been taken up in the year 2021-2022 in two river basins in the Northeastern India viz. the Brahmaputra River basin and the Chindwin River basin. It has been revealed that the Chindwin River basin in the northeastern India is harboured with five cobitid loaches under three genera *Acantopsis*, *Lepidocephalichthys*, and *Pangio* whereas the Brahmaputra River basin has been represented by five species under four genera *Lepidocephalichthys*, *Canthophrys*, *Neoecirrhichthys*, and *Pangio*. A great polymorphism has been observed under the genus *Lepidocephalichthys* collected from different sites.

Keywords: Spined loaches, freshwater, Brahmaputra River basin, Chindwin River basin, Northeastern India

Isolation and identification of some gut associated bacteria from *Channa striatus*

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Abstract

The present study aims to isolate and identify some gut associated bacteria from *Channa striatus*. *Channa striatus*, or snakehead murrel, is an obligate air-breathing freshwater fish which inhabits all types of water bodies from small ditches to rice fields, rivers and lakes. *Channa striatus* gut is inhabited by a wide variety of bacterial flora, including both gram negative and gram positive strain. The gram positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Enterococcus* species and gram negative bacteria like *E. coli*, *Corynebacterium* and *Shigella* species were found. From this study it can be concluded that these isolates were found to be associated with the diseases, enzyme production in the host and both bacteria and the host may benefited from this association.

Keywords: *E. coli*, *Corynebacterium* and *Shigella*

Microplastics pollution in the different types of aquaculture system with special reference to source water

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Abstract

Aquaculture is the controlled cultivation of aquatic organisms such as fish, crustaceans, algae, and other organisms of value such as aquatic plants in freshwater, brackish water, and saltwater play an important role in the global economy and the products contaminated with microplastics directly affect food quality and safety. Microplastics are commonly defined as plastic particles less than 5mm such as polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate, polystyrene, and polyvinyl chloride directly or indirectly ingested by organisms and also carry other toxicants that are mistaken for food and consumed by aquatic organisms. Plastic products are essential for aquaculture fields, including nets, ropes, boats, pipes, cages, water resistant materials, air pumps, and fish packaging and transport materials. All plastic products above could be potential sources of microplastics. Plastic products in aquaculture fields are directly exposed to sunlight radiation and biodegradation, thermal, catalytic action, and mechanical abrasion for long periods of time, which are favourable conditions for microplastic production. The microplastics originated from the river, lakes were directly transferred to aquaculture without any effective filtration and it may accumulate in aquaculture systems. Various culture species may influence the occurrence of microplastic in the fish culture field affecting their growth and production level. Therefore, the state of microplastics in the aquaculture industry requires attention and need to be strengthen adequate filtrations system while using open-source water to produce healthy fishes for human consumption. However, compared with microplastic studies on marine aquaculture, freshwater aquaculture is still limited, especially in artificial water bodies. Therefore, it is important to understand the microplastic pollution in aquaculture and their impact on the world aquaculture fields.

Keywords: Aquaculture, Aquaculture products, Open source water, Microplastics, Impact.

Isolation, screening, and characterization of gut probiotics from estuarine fish

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Abstract

Probiotics play significant roles in controlling diseases, enhancing specific and non-specific immunity, and stimulating growth in the successful aquaculture practice. In the present study, a total of 27 bacterial strains were isolated from the digestive tract of estuarine fish such as *Mugil cephalus* (Mullet), *Mystus gulio* (Catfish), and *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Tilapia) in Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu. The probiotic potential of 27 selected strains was investigated. Among the 27 bacterial strains, 3 strains of AJCMST1 AJCMST2 and AJCMST4, were selected as the candidates based on digestive enzymes production (protease, amylase, and lipase), resistance to gastric acid and bile salts, rapid bacterial growth phase, and antagonistic activity against pathogenic bacteria *Aeromonas hydrophila*. The potential probiotics were identified and confirmed based on their colony morphology, biochemical characteristics, and 16S rRNA sequencing. The probiotic strains were identified as *Bacillus cereus* (OM714831), *Priestia megaterium* (OM714832), and *Exiguobacterium mexicanum* (OM714834) respectively. Thus, this preliminary study showed gut micro-flora of different estuarine fish species and the microbes from the marine environment may be useful in the development of novel probiotics, drugs, and also in industrial enzyme production.

Keywords: Probiotics, Estuary fish, Enzyme production, *Aeromonas hydrophila*

Biotechnology in the area of aqua life conservation: Is an innovative tool to protect fishes from extinction and exploitation

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Abstract

Enormous varieties of fish indicate a healthy aquatic biodiversity highlighting upon the fact that the specific environment is stress free or is in tolerance level. But waterbodies that were once a huge treasure trove of various species of fishes, have recently lost many of the species because of one or other reasons that is directly or indirectly based on anthropogenic activities. As per the reports published by IUCN Red List in year 2021, approximately 1616 species of fishes are at verge of extinction, 989 species are in endangered and 627 are in critically endangered list. Overfishing accompanied with climate change and degradation of habitat has led to extinction of above 37% of world's sharks and rays species. Some critically endangered indigenous fishes include Pondicherry Shark (*Carcharhinus hemiodon*), Ganges Shark (*Glyphis gangeticus*), Knife Tooth Sawfish (*Anoxypristis cuspidate*), Karnataka Labeo (*Labeo calbasu*), etc. As per the studies published by journal Current Biology in September 6, 2021, approximately 181 out of 1041 Chondrichthyes species have got extinct. Conservational strategy across the world is more dedicated towards land species, leaving behind the aqua species. Equal importance should be given in terms of maintaining balance in ecosystem. Detailed studies are required to save a species from extinction. Earlier method involved human interference that caused impediment in animal's habitat. In the era of Advanced Technology, implementation of Artificial Intelligence and Biotechnological Methodologies has eased down the process of conserving which includes tools like SMART Hook, SnotBot, Fish Spotter, Clever Buoy, etc. and methodologies like introduction of AFP proteins and GnRH, etc.

Keywords: *Carcharhinus hemiodon, Labeo calbasu and Anoxypristis cuspidate*

Exploration of untamed catfish (*Sperata aorides*) in Cauvery river from Erode district

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Abstract

India incorporates a rich diversity of fish fauna with nearly 11% of the entire fish species of the planet and one among the most important fish-creating nations it offers 7.58% to the worldwide creation. Teleost fishes like 'catfishes' are a very important part of the ichthyofauna in wetlands and plenty of them are economically important. The catfishes are one in all the large-sized families and its more commercial value, especially family Bagridae, commonly found throughout fresh and brackish water bodies, consists of 244 species in 19 genera and includes last one decade one new genus, 23 new species was documented. Its one of the biggest catfish families presently recognized. Among the 19 genera, the genus of *Sperata* is important food fish with fewer studies group of this family. The fishes in *Sperata* also are called giant catfish. This fish has good market demand as fish because of its distinctive feature with high nutritional value. Fishes of the genus *Sperata* are large-growing Bagrid catfishes found in major river systems in the mainland of South Asia. There are five species found in Indian rivers, they're *Sperata aorides* from the Cauvery river basin and *Sperata seenghala* from the Krishna river basin. Most literature records of *S. seenghala* from the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river basins likely check with *S. lamarrii*, a species that appears to even be present within the Indus basin. Some genetic data reported as *S. seenghala* from the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river basins check with *S. aorella*. Separate *aor* is widespread within the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Surma river basins in India and Bangladesh, extending southwards to the Godavari River. We collected the *Sperata aorides* with length 45 cm and 1.2 kg from the Cauvery River in between the Poolampatti and Konaripatti barrage in Bhavani Taluk of Erode District. A mixture of huge adult size, good meat quality, and comparatively few intramuscular bones make the species valuable fish throughout their range. Small numbers of juvenile *Sperata* also make their way into the ornamental fish trade. The habit and habitat is favours and efforts should be made to develop captive breeding protocols and introduce them into aquaculture although current fisheries production is sort of entirely capture-based due to their economic importance.

Keywords: Catfish, Bagridae, Cauvery River, *Sperata aorides*, valuable fish, capture-based, aquaculture

Effect of seaweed extracts on *Cyprinus carpio* and their immune response against *Flavobacterium* sp.

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Abstract

Seaweeds are the source of biomedical compounds and are potential source of antibiotics, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory. In the present study seaweed extract as immuno stimulants of non-specific immune response in *Cyprinus carpio* were studied. *Cyprinus carpio* (weight 10 ± 5 g) were collected from a local fish in Vellanguli Tirunelveli District. Live samples of the seaweeds like *Gracilaria corticata*, *Ulva lactuca*, *Stocheospermum marginatum* were collected by handpicking during low tide from Hare Island in the Gulf of Mannar of Tuticorin coast and powdered samples were extracted by using soxhlet apparatus. Ethanol was taken as the solvent for extraction. Bacterial strain, *Flavobacterium* sp., was obtained from Microbial Type Culture Collection and Gene Bank (MTCC) Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh, India. After infection the fish were divided into five groups and injected intraperitoneally in seven days interval, namely control group injected only saline, second one was standard group injected with 0.20 mg cyproflaxin suspended in saline and the third test group ethanol extracted seaweed like *Gracilaria corticata*, *Ulva lactuca*, *Stocheospermum marginatum* injected at 0.20 mg of each extract suspended in saline solution. Immune response in common carp was studied by analysing various parameters like RBC, WBC, HB, Hematocrit values, MCV, MCH, MCHC. In the present study, immunostimulant effect of Red, Brown and Green seaweeds were performed at the dose of 20 mg/1 ml through intraperitoneal administration and the immunological parameters were measured. In our study seaweed extract act as an immune stimulant and improved the immune system of fishes and suggest that seaweed as a Good immune stimulatory agent in the aquaculture industry.

Keywords: *Cyprinus carpio*, *Gracilaria corticata*, *Ulva lactuca*, *Stocheospermum marginatum*, *Flavobacterium* sps.

Potential and therapeutic values of medicinal plants in aquaculture

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Abstract

Herbal therapy has immense significance since its medicinal potential has been revealed. The research on medicinal herbs in the health care industry is still ongoing. The presence of enormous amounts of active compounds contributes to their medicinal property and has proven successful against different microbial infections. The inclusion of traditional medicinal plants as dietary supplements to treat and prevent human diseases has also been included in the aquaculture industry. The research is ongoing on the practical and safe applicability of a wide variety of medicinal plants in aquaculture. The lack of studies on the genetic and molecular level of the effect of active compounds on the fish immune system and poor knowledge about the *in vivo* and *in vitro* toxic effect of these phytochemicals restrict the safe use in the aquaculture industry. This review describes the role of medicinal plants and their products used to improve the immune response, growth and disease resistance in the aquaculture industry.

Keywords: Herbal Therapy, *in vivo*, *in vitro* toxic effect

Oral administration of aqueous *Chaetomorpha antennina* extract on growth, biochemical, haemato-immunological, antioxidant, immune related genes expression in tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila*

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of aqueous extract of *Chaetomorpha antennina* on *Oreochromis mossambicus* growth, biochemical, haematological, antioxidant, and immunological responses, as well as immune associated gene expression and resistance to *Aeromonas hydrophila*. For eight weeks, 400 adult tilapia fish were divided into 12 tanks and fed four different experimental diets containing 0 percent (control), 0.5 percent (T1), 1 percent (T2), and 2 percent (T3) extract per kg diet. The fish were subsequently exposed to *A. hydrophila*, and their death was tracked for 30 days. The extract had a significant impact on the growth parameters of weight gain and specific growth rate, according to the findings. In fish fed extract-incorporated diets, the feed conversion ratio was considerably lower. When challenged with *A. hydrophila*, *C. antennina* extract boosted antioxidant and immunological responses, resulting in less oxidative stress sensitivity and a greater survival rate. The biggest results were shown in people who consumed 1 percent of the extract in their diet. These findings imply that the plant extract *C. antennina* has a lot of promise for usage in the aquaculture industry, and that tilapia is a good model for nutrition research.

Keywords: *C. antennina*, *Oreochromis mossambicus*, immunity, gene expression

Reef fish abundance, diversity and functional groups on a shallow reef patch in Tuticorin region of Gulf of Mannar

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Abstract

Assessing the reef fish diversity and feeding groups are key to understand the reef dynamics as reef fishes play a key role in coral reef ecosystems. The present underwater study was carried out at Pattinamaruthur patch reef in Tuticorin region during October 2021. Five 50X2 m belt transects were used to assess the fish diversity on the reef involving scuba diving. A total of 58 fish species belonging to 19 families were recorded at Pattinamaruthoor patch reef during this assessment. The average density of fishes within five belt transects was 230.2 no.100 m and the most abundant fish species was *Pempheris vanicolensis* with 18.2 m. Major functional groups identified were herbivores (10.34%), carnivores (41.38%), spongivores (8.62%), omnivores (27.59%) and planktivores (12.07%). Results of the study give us a better understanding on various feeding groups of fishes on the reef which can be used for developing reef conservation measures in the context of global climate change and increased anthropogenic disturbances.

Keywords: Reef fish diversity, *Pempheris vanicolensis* , Pattinamaruthur patch reef

Health management in shrimp culture ponds *Penaeus vannamei*

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Abstract

Aquatic animal health is a global issue since the outbreak of diseases in shrimp culture ponds. Reducing the incidence of diseases significantly improves production efficiency and profitability. While, the solution of this problem is to practice for various ways such as, the disease-free stocks, maintenance of sensible stock densities, stress management methods, proper nutrition, proper storage and use of feeds, probiotics and the maintenance of good water quality. The present investigation revealed that, the temperature was ranged from 28-30 °C, salinity was varied from 30-35 psu, pH concentration was varied from 7.4 to 9, dissolved oxygen level was ranged from 3.50 to 5.5 mg⁻¹ and transparency was varied from about 20-45 cm. The total *Vibrio* counts was recorded from 3 to 95 x 10³ CFU ml⁻¹ in water and in sediment, it was varied from 11 to 35 x 10⁴ CFU g⁻¹. Present study also was observed five types of *Vibrio* species. Among them, *Vibrio alginolyticus* and *Vibrio harveyii* was found to be more dominant than other species.

Keywords: Animal health, Water quality parameters and *Vibrio*.

Bio-plastic materials from cultivable freshwater fish waste as an alternative source for synthetic plastics

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Abstract

India is one of the global leading country for fish production in which, it reached about 11.5 lakh tonnes in 2015-2016 for fish exports which is roughly about 50% of it has been disposed as waste. Fishing generates large quantities of waste daily in fish processing industries. To secure from pollution and to scale back wastes, it's important to process a comprehensive understanding about the recycling and conversion of those fish wastes into useful products. Plastics are materials which are inexpensive, light weight, strong, durable, and corrosion resistant, with high thermal and electrical insulation properties. Due to these versatile properties plastics made from petro chemical based plasticizers such as Poly ethyl terephthalate (PET), Poly butylene terephthalate (PBT) , Polypropylene (PP), Polystyrene (PS), Poly vinyl chloride (PVC), are widely used. Petrochemical plastics are not eco-friendly because of their high content of carbon foot print and toxic components. Excessive use of these plastics have caused severe impact to the environment. The incineration and burning of those plastics leads to toxic emissions. Greenhouse gases are also liberated, which affect the climate worldwide drastically. Bio-plastics which are degradable, are not harmful to the environment. Bio-plastics are large chain of monomers linked to each other by ester bonds. A number of bio derived materials and their innovative applications in food related packaging has gained much attention over the past several years. Bio-plastics can also be manufactured from economically available sources like fish scales, skins and waste materials etc. Approximately about 17.9-39.5 million tonnes of whole fish is discarded each year by commercial fishery operations. Those waste products can be used an alternative source over synthetic plastics. Indian major carps (Rohu, Catla, Mrigal) make up nearly 90% of India's freshwater aqua cultured fish. Bio-plastics can be developed from different types of fish waste powders that are prepared from catla, rohu and mrigal. These powders were transformed into bioplastic by using polymerization technique along with glycerol plasticizers, like Polyethylene glycol (PEG), Triethylene glycol (TEG) and Glycerol. They are found to be the most effective plasticizers, possibly because of their characteristics such as low molecular weight, high solubility in water and large protein miscibility. Thus bioplastics from fish wastes acts as a renewable and harmless alternative source over synthetic plastics.

Keywords: Fish waste, Bio-plastics, Waste management, Degradable plastics, Non-toxic plastics.

Status of freshwater catfishes and their commercial importance in the Cauvery river basin

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Abstract

Freshwater is critical to human society and sustains all terrestrial ecosystems. While India incorporates a large spread of freshwater resources, most systems are threatened because of anthropogenic activities resulting in serious threats to fish diversity. The catfish group is one of the biggest groups of freshwater fishes, with quite 2000 species. Catfish have a cosmopolitan distribution. Catfish are a very important group because they serve many alternative roles, including as ornamentals, like fish in aquaculture as research animals, and for sport fishing. Catfish is low in calories and jam-choked with lean protein, healthy fats, vitamins, and minerals. It's particularly rich in heart-healthy omega-3 fatty acids and vitamin B12. It may be a healthy addition to any meal, though deep frying adds much more calories and fat than dry heat cooking methods like baking or broiling. This study had done to review the economic importance of catfish within the fish market in poolampatti village in Salem district. The result shows that the order Siluriformes, includes three families Bagridae 40% with five species includes *Hemibagrus punctatus*, *Mystus cavasius*, *Mystus montanus*, *Mystus vittatus*, *Sperata arodies*, family Pangasiidae 28.2% with one species *Pangasius pangasius* and fish family 31% with two species *Ompok bimaculatus*, *Ompok malabaricus*.

Keywords: Fish diversity, Catfish Families, Freshwater, Cauvery River

***Circumonchobothrium hemlatae* (redescribe) cestode parasite in freshwater fish
from Parbhani (M.S.) India**

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Abstract

The present paper deals with the redescription of cestode parasites of genus *Circumonchobothrium* in cultivable freshwater fish *Cirrhina mrigala* from Yeldhari reservoir of Parbhani district (M.S) India. The cestode parasite was identified on the basis of their taxonomic study. After going through the comparative study it is found that the present *Circumonchobothrium* species is somewhat nearer to *Circumonchobothrium hemlatae* with 12 characters. These characters are considered as key character for the identification of species level of any parasite. Therefore it is redescribed as *Circumonchobothrium hemlatae*.

Keywords: *Circumonchobothrium hemlatae* red sp., *Cirrhina mrigala*, Yeldhari reservoir

Diversity of phytoplankton and hydrological studies of Putheri Parayadi pond, Kanniyakumari district

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Abstract

Diversity of planktons and physico-chemical parameters are the important criteria for evaluating the suitability of water for irrigation and drinking purposes. The present investigation studied the monthly variation between the physico-chemical parameters and the phytoplankton diversity. The samples were collected on the monthly basis from October 2019 to March 2020 at Putheri Parayadi pond. During this period various physico-chemical parameters such as alkalinity, BOD, DO, pH, temperature, chloride, nitrite were analysed. High values of physico-chemical parameters were noticed in the month of March. A total of 72 species belonging to 34 genera were observed. Occurrence of algae varied in different months. Among this, the class Chlorophyceae members showed maximum population with 35 species belonging to 15 genera followed by Cyanophyceae, Bacillariophyceae and Euglenophyceae.

Keywords: Cyanophyceae, Bacillariophyceae and Euglenophyceae.

Immunomodulation of canthaxanthin enriched diet to lactococcosis in flathead grey mullet, *Mugil cephalus*

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Abstract

Efficacy of canthaxanthin (CX) enriched diet at 5, 10, and 15 mg/kg diet was studied on growth, and immune-physiological variables in flathead grey mullet (*Mugil cephalus*) against *Lactococcus garvieae* infection. The unchallenged fish fed control diet or diet contained 15 mg CX exhibited a significant difference in weight gain (WG) between weeks 6 and 8 of feeding, while WG was changed in both challenged and unchallenged groups at 10 mg CX between weeks 4 to 8. Survival rate (SR) was 100% in unchallenged groups fed 5 or 10 mg CX and in challenged fish fed 10 mg CX. The SR was higher in challenged fish fed 5 or 15 mg CX than challenged group fed control diet. Leucocytes (WBC) and total protein (TP) values were significantly improved in both groups at 10 mg CX between weeks 4 to 8 of feeding. The superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity was significant in both groups at 10 mg CX from weeks 4 to 8 whereas this value changed in unchallenged group fed 5 or 15 mg CX on 6th and 8th week. Malondialdehyde (MDA) activity was significant in unchallenged group fed 5 or 10 mg kg⁻¹ CX on weeks 6 and 8 of feeding and challenged group fed 15 mg CX. The phagocytic index (PI) and respiratory burst (RB) activities were significant of both groups at 5 or 10 mg CX on week 6 whereas all CX diets on week 8. The alternate complement (AC) activity was significant in both groups fed 10 mg CX on 2nd and 4th weeks, whereas that of 5 and 15 mg CX trials on 6th week and all CX inclusion diets on 8th week. The skin mucus and serum lysozyme (Lyz) activity was significant in both groups fed 10 mg CX on 4th week, trial of 5 and 15 mg CX on week 6 and all CX trials on week 8. The IL-1 β mRNA expression was found two fold changes in unchallenged group fed 10 mg CX and both groups fed 10 mg CX on week 6 and 8. The IL-8 gene expression was two-fold high in both groups fed 10 mg CX where IL-10 gene expression was one-fold high in both groups fed 5 mg CX trial. The TNF- α gene expression was significant one-fold change in fish fed 10 mg CX on weeks 6 and 8 of feeding. The present results suggested that inclusion CX 10 mg/kg diet can improve growth, hemato-biochemical, antioxidant ability, innate immunity, and modulation of immune associated gene expression against *F. columnaris* in flathead grey mullet.

Keywords: Antioxidant; Canthaxanthin (CX); Innate-adaptive immune response; *Lactococcus garvieae*; *Mugil cephalus*

Hydrogel – algae technology in aquaculture

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Abstract

Hydrogels are industrially exploited in many ways as they have a significant role in contact lens production, hygiene products, wound dressing, drug delivery, tissue engineering, agriculture and many more. It was in recent days these were implemented in aquaculture too. Algae, when free in an aquaculture system, impact negatively. But, when they're immobilised, they act as biosorbents of excess nutrients (TAN, TP), heavy metals, organic pollutants; probes for toxicity measurements, etc. Calcium alginate immobilisation of algal species is the most commonly employed technique, which carries potential risks. Risks like leakage of contents into aquaculture systems with increased time present inside water, the toxicity of polyacrylamide and alginate because of their mechanical instability. Some research projects done in the field of hydrogels suggested integrating silicon with traditional alginate proved to have increased mechanical stability and durability. Hybrid hydrogels with a mixture of calcium silicate and sodium alginate matrix; silicon membranous alginate beads are some of these. Silicone also improves diatoms in aquaculture systems, which are of good nutritional value to aquaculture species. The present work focuses on algae immobilisation techniques involving silicone hydrogels, and their application in aquaculture as a better feasible option compared to traditional alginate immobilisation methods.

Keywords: Calcium alginate, sodium alginate, Silicone

A rapid survey on air breathing fishes of Thamirabarani river, Tirunelveli district

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Abstract

The freshwater air breathing fish community in Thamirabarani River, Tirunelveli District was investigated from November 2021 to February 2022. Nine species belonging to 5 families (Channidae, Clariidae, Bagridae, Heteropneustidae, and Anguillidae) and 5 genera; including 2 species of *Channa* and *Clarias*, 3 species of *Mystus*, 1 species of *Heteropneustus* and *Anguilla* were identified. Among them 8 species were found to be native and under least concern in IUCN status list and the *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish) was the exotic species to India which is considered to be most harmful species due to the accumulation of mercury content in the body which is toxic to human body and it also consume large amount of live feed (predatory) which leads to the depletion of our native fish species. This present study clearly illustrates that air breathing fishes are one of the richest fish community in the ecosystem of Thamirabarani river.

Keywords: Thamirabarani river, Tirunelveli District, Air breathing fish

The effect of formulated aquafeed on selected ornamental fish

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Abstract

Most aquarium maintainers' especially ornamental fish hobbyists procure the bulk of their feed from commercial manufacturers. Small ornamental fish farms with the range of fish require small amounts of various diets with particular nutrients. It is not cost effective for commercial manufacturers to produce very small quantities of specialized feeds. Formulation of low cost, low polluted, nutrition rich high quality feeds are required for production of good quality fishes some of the nutrition which are required by the aquatic organisms which includes protein, carbohydrate, fatty acids, vitamins, minerals, growth factors and other energy sources essentially for maintaining growth, reproduction and other normal physiological functions. The variation in the nutritional requirements can be identified with warm water or cold water, finfish or shell fish and marine water or freshwater species. In this study five fishes are selected in same species and fed with different nutritionally balanced feeds (plant based and artificial) the weight and growth of the fish (nutrition and feeding will influence the growth of the fish) will recorded continuously. Fish which weighs more at the end of this experiment is selected with that specific feed given to them. The aim of this paper is to formulate species specific diet formulation that support aquaculture industry as it expands to satisfy the demand for affordable, safe, high-quality fish feed.

Key words: aquaculture, feeding, protein, seafood, high quality fish

**A study on diversity and seasonal variation of hill-stream fishes in Longnit river,
Karbi Anglong, Assam**

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Abstract

The present study deals with the documentation of fish diversity and seasonal variation carried out in the Longnit River of Karbi Anglong district. It joins the Jamuna River, a tributary of Brahmaputra. During the present study of Longnit River, a total number of 23 species belonging to 14 families and 6 orders have been reported. Dominant species is found to be *Neolissochilus hexagonolepis* and least dominant species is *Anguilla bengalensis*. Important hill stream fishes include genera: *Botia*, *Crossocheilus*, *Garra*, *Glyptothorax*, *Labeo*, *Psilorhynchus* etc. The highest numbers of fish were reported during the pre-monsoon season due to increased rainfall, followed by winter, however the species composition remained nearly constant throughout the seasons. It has been found that over the last few years, fish catch has decreased, which can be linked to anthropogenic pressures such as habitat degradation and overexploitation. Sand mining and the removal of instream stones and boulders have expanded substantially in recent years, possibly contributing to the degradation of fish habitat.

Keywords: Fish diversity, Seasonal variation, Pre-monsoon, Anthropogenic pressure

Diversity of the diminutive sisorid catfish of the genus *Pseudolaguvia* (Teleostei: Siluriformes) in the northeastern India

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Abstract

The Northeastern India, a part of the Indo-Burma megabiodiversity hotspot of the world, is blessed with five different drainage systems viz. the Brahmaputra, the Barak-Surma-Meghana, the Chindwin, the Kaladan, and the Karnaphuli. The colourful diminutive catfishes of the genus *Pseudolaguvia* are one of the representative freshwater fish fauna of the region. The routine studies on the collected fishes from various rivers of the northeastern India since 2017 to till date, have revealed with the distribution of 15 species under the genus *Pseudolaguvia*. It has been found that *Pseudolaguvia* species can be characterized into two groups based on the presence or absence of serrations on the anterior edge of the dorsal spine. Of the 15 species of *Pseudolaguvia* in the region, 11 species are categorized under the group of fish with smooth face on the anterior edge of the dorsal spine whereas the remaining four species are under second category of fish with serrated edge on the anterior dorsal spine. The Brahmaputra River has maximum diversity of *Pseudolaguvia* with 10 species. The Barak-Surma-Meghna River harbours three species while the Karnaphuli and the Kaladan Rivers are with one species each. Applications of modern integrated taxonomic tools are much needed for proper understanding of the species identity.

Keywords: Diminutive catfish, *Pseudolaguvia*, freshwater, Meghabiodiversity hotspot, Northeastern India.

Occurrence of the amazon sailfin catfish *Pterygoplichthys pardalis* (Siluriformes: Loricariidae), an alien aquarium fish invasion in Kerala waters

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Abstract

Amazon sailfin catfishes (Loricariidae), invasive alien species are recently introduced to the aquatic environments outside their native distribution range and continue spreading and proliferating massively throughout Indian inland aquatic ecosystems such as rivers, streams, reservoirs and lakes etc., and world, causing competition for space and food, including economically valuable native and endemic species. This paper documents the occurrence of the exotic South American suckermouth armoured catfishes (Loricariidae) of the genus *Pterygoplichthys* spp. in the main tributary of Bharathapuzha River (Gayatripuzha River) Palakkad, Kerala. Invasion occurred through aquaculture farms and trading, and is intensified by the dispersal through rainstorm flooding and irrigation canal. The identified fishes range in length (9.50 - 31.75 cm) and weight (8.16 - 129.80 g). Invasion of non-native fish species threatens native biodiversity of the aquatic ecosystem services and their communities which is the subject of concern currently. Distribution leads to understand the changes and disturbances in fish species composition and the negative impact of riverine ecosystem. Through this study, *P. pardalis* is found in the study area as a new geographic location in Kerala.

Keywords: Freshwater, Invasive alien fish, *Pterygoplichthys pardalis*, Gayatripuzha River

Prebiotic and probiotic shrimp larval feed

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Abstract

Prebiotic help in the growth and development of gut microflora. Prebiotics are dietary fibers that act as substrate for beneficial bacteria in gut microflora, whereas probiotics colonize the intestine and protect the cells against invasion by pathogens. In recent years inadequate feeds lead to the low survival and poor post larval quality. So the need of formulated larval feed to be developed to overcome the nutritional deficiency and other diseases. The tasks of national reference laboratories include the improvement of detection methods and to promote their further development. Various detection approaches, such as in the medical field or for allergen detection in fish products. *L. lactis* and alginate or the combination of both treatments (Isa) could improve the survival rate by upregulating their innate immune response. Describes the microbial composition during *M. rosenbergii* ontogeny.

Keywords: Prebiotic, Probiotics, pathogens, larval quality, microbial composition.

Probiotic shrimp larval feed

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Abstract

Probiotics protect their host from pathogens by producing metabolites that inhibit the colonisation or growth of other microorganisms or competing with them for resources such as nutrients or space. Owing to the problem of antibiotic resistance and subsequent reluctance of using antibiotics, the use of probiotics in larva culture is becoming increasingly popular. During early stages of development, manipulation of larval digestive system seems possible through the addition of probiotics through feed. The use of gram negative, non-spore forming probiotics, which makes scaling of the process difficult. The fact that methods of delivering the probiotics to the larvae have not been optimized. Potential effects of the probiotics on the fish health during grow-out. Although there are many examples of microorganisms used for biocontrol, typically used in shrimp or pond culture, there are currently only a few commercial intestinal probiotics used specifically during the larval stages of aquatic organisms. Novel intestinal probiotics need to be identified and optimized in feed.

Keywords: Probiotics, pathogens, antibiotics, resistance, aquatic micro organisms.

Biodiversity of aquatic insects of three ponds in Ramanathapuram, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The aquatic insects perform several critical roles in ecosystem functioning by virtue of their numerical abundance, taxonomic diversity and trophic significance. Insects are the largest group among animals and plants in the world. There are about 7,51,000 known species of insects, which is about three-fourth of all species of animals and plants. Most importantly, aquatic insects are very good indicator of water quality since they have various environmental disturbance tolerance levels. The present study deals with the diversity and distribution of aquatic insects of three ponds in Ramanathapuram, India. Aquatic insects were collected using D-Frame dipnet (0.3 m width and 0.3 m height) having mesh size 500 μ and kicknet (1 m x 1 m) having mesh size 500 μ for a period of four month during Sep 2021 to Dec 2021. A random sampling of a 50 m reach was taken collecting insect samples at each site. Samples preserved in 95% ethyl alcohol and brought to the laboratory for further analysis. In the present investigation total 23 species have been recorded belonging to 2 orders and 10 families. Aquatic insects are probably best known for their ability to indicate the water quality of a particular environment. Most of the insect species act as an important bio indicator, but it also have its role in (food sources) food chain, pollination and also stabilizes the streams of ecosystem.

Keywords: Species Diversity, Bio monitoring, insect biodiversity, Aquatic insects.

Formulation and characterization of plant, animal, and probiotic based fish meals and evaluating their efficacy on growth and performance in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)

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Abstract

A comparative analysis on the effects of plant based (PD), animal based (AD) and probiotic based (Pr) diets on growth performance in *Danio rerio* was investigated. Different diets were administered as either single or combination diet (CD) containing PD, AD and PrD exhibited varying effects on growth and development. The probiotic bacteria isolated from Indian prawn (*Penaeus indicus*) was identified as *Bacillus* sp using 16s rRNA sequencing and phylogenetic analysis. The isolate was characterized by evaluating its ability to survive at different pH, temperature and simulated artificial gastric environment and was further subjected to varying concentrations of salt and organic solvents. Antibiofilm activity of the isolate was evaluated against fish pathogens; *Vibrio harveyi* (96.1±2.7%), *Escherichia coli* (96.2±1.5), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (95.3±3.0%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (96.7±2.8%). After the end of trial, growth parameters were evaluated. Weight gain percentage was significantly higher in PrD (15.7±0.08%) compared to other treatments ($p < 0.05$). Feed conversion ratio was least in CD (0.35±0.09) feed efficiency (2.7±0.08) in CD was numerically high compared to other treatments ($p > 0.05$). The study promotes sustainable aquaculture by the use of alternative aquafeeds derived from plant or animal based sources. The study also highlights the usage of probiotics in improving growth performance, disease resistance in aquatic animals.

Keywords: Alternative feed, Feed formulation, Growth performance, Probiotics, *Bacillus* sp.

Trout farming: Potential in Uttarakhand state with emphasis on harvesting and post harvesting technologies

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Abstract

Uttarakhand state of India is generously bestowed with water resources. Rivers originating from Uttarakhand Himalaya quench the thirst of larger population of Northern part of India and play a vital role in its agricultural productivity, socio-economy, cultural and religious life. River Ganga and Yamuna both originate in Uttarakhand State. Several rivers in the state viz. Alaknanda, Nandakini, Pindar, Bhagirathi, Mandakini, Kosi, Kali, Ramganga, Dhauliganga, Saryu, Bhilangna, etc. are repository of many species of fish and a total of about 125 fish species thrive in these waters. Exotic trout; the rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* and brown trout *Salmo trutta* are also found in the cold waters of Uttarakhand Himalaya and commercial production of these exotic trout is increasing in the state owing to their market demand, especially of rainbow trout. This trout thrives in cold waters and its commercial production is done in concrete raceways on commercial lines. Optimization of physico-chemical parameters such as temperature, optimal DO, low NH₄-N levels and appropriate feed can further enhance trout productivity as the fish grow in a slow rate in cold waters. Many of the river waters and lakes in Uttarakhand state provide optimal conditions for trout farming and can generate lucrative avenues for livelihood and employment generation in the areas situated above 2,000 m ASL, having high potentialities for trout fisheries. Since its production is being done in remote areas of Uttarakhand where the demand is meagre while it grows slowly in cold waters and require a year to reach marketable size of 250 grams and to get a good price it needs to reach urban settlements and thus require boost in its productivity and post harvesting technologies to reach its consumers in fresh conditions. The paper elaborates potential of trout fisheries in Uttarakhand, optimization of its productivity in cold water conditions with special emphasis on harvesting and post harvesting technologies.

Keywords: Cold water Fisheries, Trout farming, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*, *Salmo trutta*.

Efficacy of probiotic bacteria *Bacillus megaterium* on growth, survival and disease resistance in white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* postlarvae

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Abstract

In the last few decades, the occurrence of multi resistant antibiotics of pathogenic bacteria in aquaculture have led to the development of effectiveness of probiotic species. This study was to evaluate the effect of *Bacillus megaterium* on growth, survival and disease resistance of white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* postlarvae. The probiotic *B. megaterium* enriched to the *Artemia* nauplii with three different concentrations (5×10^7 , 5×10^9 and 5×10^{11} cfu /mL) was fed to the white shrimp *L. vannamei* postlarvae. Shrimp postlarvae (PL) were fed with four different diets: control (without probiotic enriched *Artemia* nauplii) and other three diets with probiotic enriched *Artemia* nauplii. After 30-days of experiment, the result showed that postlarvae fed with probiotic enriched *Artemia* nauplii were significantly better growth performance (length and weight) and survival when compared to control. The levels of biochemical constituents, such as protein, lipid and carbohydrate contents were found to significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in experimental PL, particularly at 5×10^9 cfu cells. In the challenging study, results showed a significant decrease in the cumulative mortality of postlarvae fed with enriched *Artemia* nauplii. Therefore, it is evident that 5×10^9 cfu cells of *B. megaterium* can be considered and used as a suitable concentration for growth and survival of *L. vannamei* postlarvae in aquaculture hatcheries.

Keywords: Live feed, enrichment, *Artemia*, *Bacillus megaterium*, bioencapsulation

Polychaetes of the Arockiapuram coast with special reference to their intertidal habitat

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Abstract

Intertidal polychaetes are exposed to a highly active environment, as related to tidal state and amplitude, current velocity and sediment morphodynamics. Intertidal areas are under increasing pressure from urbanization as 50% of the world's population lives near the coast. Polychaetes in the intertidal zone possess a variety of adaptations to survive with the effect of physical variables, including changes caused by moving sediment and feeding behavior. Of fifteen species of polychaetous annelids collected from the intertidal zone of Arockiapuram coast, Kanyakumari, eight were new records for the study area. Keys are given to the recorded species of Nereidae, Amphinomidae, Cirratullidae, Aphroditidae and Syllidae of the "Southern Bay of Bengal Ecoregion". Map of the study area and photos of samples collected were all taken then and there. Microscopic photos and camera lucida drawings were used to describe the morphometric and meristic characters of the species. Collected species were identified using standard keys and described with figures and photos to make them suitable for the publication of research papers.

Keywords: Intertidal Polychaetaes, Ecoregion, Feeding behavior, New records, Morphometric and meristic characters

Fishery resources, feeding habits of *Gerres erythrourus* fish from Puducherry estuary Thengaithittu

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Abstracts

The knowledge of the food and feeding habits of a fish helps in finding out the distribution of a fish population. So the present study is an attempt to investigate the estuarine fishery resources (*Gerres erythrourus*) potential, food and feeding habits in Puducherry estuary (Thengaithittu) and indicates their relationship with the fishing resources followed by neighbouring region (Tamil Nadu). In the present study our result clearly finds that in the year 2019-20. *G. erythrourus* fish catching during the month of May was 32 kg and in the month of November it was noticed and recorded as 67kg. The food items were observed in plankton algae (28%), Protozoans (5%), amphipods (11%), crustaceans (17%), bivalve (21%), sediments detritus parts (18%). The overall findings thoroughly indicate to understand the qualitative and quantitative connection between the nutritive values associated with the food organisms particularly fishes.

Keywords: Pondicherry, Estuary, Food and Feeding, *G. erythrourus*

Enhancement of innate immune system, survival, and yield in *Oreochromis* sp using fermented seaweeds isolated from coastal regions of Mandapam camp

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Abstract

The development of alternative natural immunostimulants such as those found in seaweeds is of great importance for aquatic health and holds considerable commercial potential. Because of the reported side effects of commercially available immunostimulants, researchers have turned their attention towards natural substances. Prima facie, our investigation will represent a prelude approach to characterize the antibacterial activity of non-fermented and fermented sea weeds isolated from the coastal regions of mandapam against marine and human pathogens. Antioxidant potential, anti-inflammatory effect on peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs), chemical constituents of fractions will be analyzed. Furthermore, host defense system will be studied through challenge experiments against common aquaculture pathogens. Alteration in Immune response to the supplied fermented sea weeds will be evaluated at cellular and molecular level. This study will determine the bioavailability of nutrients with respect to sea weed fermentation and their role in the improvement of *Oreochromis* sp.

Keywords: Probiotics, Aquaculture, Bacteriocins, Fermentation.

Assessment of aquatic macrophytes in Dakkarkulam, Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu, south India

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Abstract

Aquatic plants are key components for the well functions of wetland ecosystem for biological productivity and support diverse organisms and provide lots of goods and services for the dependent people. They are valuable sources, sinks and transformers of a multitude of chemical, biological and genetic material and are considered the “Kidneys of the Earth” for the cleaning function they platform through biogeochemical cycles. Detailed survey of aquatic macrophytes in Dakkarkulam, Kottara panchayat, Agastheeswaram taluk of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu was made for 6 months. Total 53 aquatic macrophytes belonging to 33 families and 48 genera were recorded from the study site. Out of these, 48 were angiosperms, 3 were pteridophytes and only one algae and bryophyte each. Convolvulaceae was the most dominant family with 6 species. Aponogetaceae, Azollaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Malvaceae, Apiaceae, Sapindaceae, Rubiaceae, Ceratophyllaceae, Cyperaceae, Pontederiaceae, Acanthaceae, Boraginaceae, Lemnaceae, Marsileaceae, Marchantiaceae, Nelumbonaceae, Salviniaceae, Typhaceae, Talinaceae, Scorophulariaceae, Apocynaceae and Characeae had only one species. There are 22 marginal, 10 floating, 16 emergent and 5 submerged aquatic macrophytes. Raunkiar’s life form classification has been followed. The presently observed species include 3.8% Chamaephytes, 24.5% Phanerophytes, 1.9% Cryptophytes, 5.6% Hemicryptophytes and 64.2% Therophytes. The Biological spectrum of the study area showed divergence when compared with Raunkiar’s normal spectrum depicting the theophanerophytic plant climate of the region. The biodiversity of aquatic macrophytes distribution and population of the species depend upon the physico-chemical parameters of the water and environment factors. It is clear from the results that the study area was mesotrophic to going towards eutrophication, therefore, aimed to evaluate the study area on the basis of various community features of macrophytes. The uses of aquatic macrophytes and traditional practices will continue to play a significant role in the socio-cultural life of these village communities. But the trend of decline of the abundance of some very useful native species, increase of unsustainable anthropogenic practices, encroachments and spreading of invasive species show that conservation is urgently needed. Therefore, priority should be given to implement conservation activities with integrated approach for sustainable development.

Keywords: Agastheeswaram, classification, macrophytes, submerged, Raunkiar’s life form.

Investigation of microplastics in the common fishes of river Ganga (Uttarakhand)

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Abstract

Microplastics (MPs) have become the most significant emerging contaminants of the present decade globally. Its presence has been confirmed in almost every range of aquatic and terrestrial environment including water, soil, sand, ice, salt, fish and even in human placenta. The organisms of various trophic levels interact with MPs and their exposure leads to a variety of adverse effects on aquatic biota from primary producers to top predators and even human beings. The common source of MPs is wastewater from domestic and industrial sites that ends up in an aquatic ecosystem. In the present study, we investigated the presence of MPs in the common fishes of River Ganga in Uttarakhand stretch. Guts of fishes were collected from the local market of Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand. The sample were digested with KOH (10%) and filtered to observe under microscope. The SEM and XRD analysis were performed to enhance the clarity of plastic present in sample. On visual inspection and microscopical study we found presence of microplastic in all the fish sample. The presence of thread/fibre were found dominant in the samples. Hence, it is concluded that the fishes were able to engulf different size of MPs in their bodies which could be potentially harmful to them.

Keywords: Microplastics, River Ganga, SEM, XRD.

Probiotic properties of *Bacillus subtilis* isolated from dried anchovies

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Abstract

This study was carried out to isolate and characterise a potential probiotic bacterium from dried anchovies (*Stolephorus indicus*) and to evaluate its antibacterial, antibiofilm and growth enhancing potential. 16S rRNA sequencing of the isolate identified it as *Bacillus subtilis*. Probiotic properties were characterised based on the ability of the isolated strain to survive in simulated gastric juice and trypsin. Isolated strain was further subjected to varying pH, temperature, different concentrations of organic solvents to evaluate its potential to tolerate stress. Biofilm inhibition against *Vibrio harveyi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* was noted. Adhesion assays were also performed on HT-29 human adenocarcinoma cell-lines as adhesion to the intestinal mucosa is considered important for immune modulation (the intestine is the largest immune organ of the body), pathogen exclusion, enhanced healing of damaged mucosa and prolonged transient colonization which is important for probiotic activity.

Keywords: *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*

Studies on the effect of temperature, pH, detergent and pesticide on the opercular beat on the respiratory rate of ornamental fish white molly, *Poecilia sphenops*

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Abstract

An attempt has been carried out to determine the influence of temperature, pH, detergent and pesticide on the opercular beats and oxygen consumption of an ornamental fish white molly, *Poecilia sphenops* fingerlings of average weight of 2.85 ± 0.30 g. Pollution of the water bodies will create physiological stress on the aquatic fauna. Among various forms of pollution in water bodies temperature, pH, detergent and pesticide has an immediate and detrimental effect. The detergents are household chemical cleaning compounds required in wide range for diverse purposes. In some rivers the concentration of detergent and pesticide required is quite high. The major components of detergent and phosphate make adverse effects on the aquatic life at very low levels of exposure. Fish have long been valued as excellent indicator of water quality. Each type of fish has its own fatal temperature. Rapid temperature changes produce thermal shock or stress. This study demonstrated that opercular beats significantly ($F=3.473$; $p<0.05$) increased as increasing the range of temperature, different pH level, different level of detergent and different concentration of pesticide. This investigation also demonstrated that there will be significantly increased ($F=2.737$; $p<0.05$) changes in the dissolved oxygen consumption of experimental fish, *P. sphenops*. This is due to stress caused by the environment (temperature, pH, detergent and pesticide) on the normal physiological activities of the fish. The findings from this study revealed that the information is useful in calculation of oxygen requirement of *Poecilia sphenops* species for live transportation and other experimental purpose.

Keywords: Water bodies, Fauna, Temperature, pH, Detergent, Pesticide, Opercular beats

A pilot study on the fish diversity of Thamirabharani river in selected areas of Tirunelveli district

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Abstract

Fresh water is critical to human society and sustains all terrestrial ecosystems. Even though India has a large spread of fresh water resources, most systems are threatened due to anthropogenic activities leading to serious threats to fish diversity. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the diversity of freshwater fish and its distribution in Thamirabharani river in Vagaikulam and Seevalaperi area, Tirunelveli district. The study was conducted from the month of January to March 2019 and a total of 9 fish species belonging to 6 families were identified. Among them, Cyprinidae which constitute the major carps were found to be dominant and show high species richness, whereas Cichlidae and Cichlidae are positioned in second and third places respectively.

Keywords: Ecosystem, Freshwater resources, Cyprinidae, Cichlidae, Cichlidae, Anthropogenic activity.

A study of antibacterial activity of *Indigofera glandulosa* J.C. Wendl. against selected fish pathogens

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antibacterial activity of *Indigofera glandulosa* against fish pathogens. *I. glandulosa* were shade dried, powdered, and extracted using solvents such as benzene, ethyl acetate, ethanol, and aqueous extract. The crude extract was tested for its antimicrobial activity against five fish pathogens, namely *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Escherichia coli* which were primarily isolated from diseased fish. The ethanol extract showed a wide spectrum of activity followed by ethyl acetate extract, aqueous extract, and benzene extract with a zone of inhibition ranging from 2 to 8mm. The result confirms that *Indigofera glandulosa* has promising anti-bacterial potential, especially against dangerous *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Hence *I. glandulosa* can be considered as an eminent source for the isolation of effective alternative natural products to commercially available synthetic antibiotics.

Keywords: *Aeromonas hydrophila*, Antibacterial activity, *Indigofera glandulosa*

***In-vitro* studies on therapeutic competence of green and brown seaweeds against lung cancer cell line**

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Abstract

Cancer has become one of the biggest challenges to the scientific community over the world, and despite the development of drugs and other modalities for the treatment of cancer, however, there are complexities at every level of treatment. Cancer chemotherapy is associated with many unwanted side effects. Natural products from seaweeds play a dominant role in the discovery of such new drugs. In this context, seaweeds contain powerful antioxidant and anti-cancer properties to arrest the proliferation of cancer cells. Antitumor Activities of brown algae crude extracts of various brown algae isolated from different marine environments against different cancer cell lines shows promising brown algae against human cancer cells, brown algae signified the importance of the in vitro anticancer potential of these seaweeds for cancer therapy. In the present study, the anti-cancerous activity of two seaweed extracts was assessed by the method of MTT assay. A high level of anti-cancerous activity was noted in seaweed *T.conoids*, absorbance can be read using a spectrophotometer. The effective activity was observed in methanol extract of *T.conoids* and *C.racemosa* at 6,12,25,55 and 85 concentrations. The methanol extract of *T.conoids* was expressed effective activities even at a lower concentrated 12 (0.619). On evaluating the anti-cancer property of *Turbinaria conoides*, the alga proved to be a potent anti-cancer agent. The findings of this study also pave the way for further research to identify the specific active compounds that are responsible for its claimed anti-cancer activity. The results clearly indicated that the anti-cancer compound that the seaweed (*T.conoids* and *C.racemosa*) possesses anti-cancer activity against lung carcinoma. This preliminary study points to a possible role of green and brown seaweeds in the treatment of Lung carcinoma, although further studies are required to isolate and characterize the active compounds.

Keywords: *Turbinaria conoides*, *C.racemosa*, Lung cancer, Cell line and anti-cancer property

Antifungal activity of the fresh water fish (*Heteropneustes fossilis*)

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to identify the presence of antifungal activity in different organs/tissues (gills, liver, intestine, muscle, ovary and venom gland) extract of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. The screening of antifungal activity for all the fractions were tested against five fungal pathogens (Nustatin-resistant) - (*Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus flaves*, *Candida parapsilosis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*) using the standardized disc susceptibility test method. The highest antibacterial activity was detected against *Aspergillus flaves*, *Aspergillus niger* (19 mm) for hexane extract in muscle, followed by *Aspergillus flaves* (18 mm) for ethanol extract in venom gland and *Aspergillus niger* (15 mm) for ethanol extract in gills (17 mm) and least value observed in *Aspergillus fumigates*. The activity was measured in terms of zone of inhibition in mm. The results indicated that, among the six organs/tissues tested. The present study showed that, *Heteropneustes fossilis* tissues can be a potential source of an antimicrobial protein for specific fungal pathogens.

Keywords: *Aspergillus flaves*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*

Biosynthesis, characterization, antimicrobial and free radical scavenging application of silver nanoparticles using marine macro alga, *Caulerpa racemosa*

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Abstract

The present study describes the synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from *Caulerpa racemosa* (Frosk) Weber-Van-Bosses has been used. The prepared Silver nanoparticles were characterized by various techniques such as UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy, X - Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR). XRD analysis revealed the wurtzite hexagonal structure of Ag nanoparticles. FT-IR confirmed the presence of functional groups of both alga powder and Ag nanoparticles, protein acts as capping agent and terpenoids as a reducing agent. Free radical scavenging was done by DPPH, ABTS^{•+}, H₂O₂ and Hydroxyl scavenging method. The anti-microbial activity was investigated by using disc diffusion method, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) and Minimum Fungicidal Concentration (MFC). The mean zone of inhibition produced by the tested AgNPs in disc diffusion assays against bacterial and fungal strains ranged from 7.8 to 20.3 mm. The highest mean zone of inhibition was observed in AgNPs prepared from *C. racemosa* against *B. subtilis*. The MIC values ranged between 31.25 to 125 µg/mL, while the MBC & MFC values were between 62.5 to 500 µg/mL. These findings suggest that AgNPs of *C. racemosa* can be used as an antimicrobial agent for the treatment of human pathogens causing acquired infection and the antioxidant activity of the AgNPs could be the basis for health promoting potential.

Keywords: AgNPs, *Caulerpa racemosa*, EDX, FT-IR, Xray Diffraction, Free radical scavenging activity.

Extension and economics

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Abstract

For a single period of time, say a year, a firm's profits can be obtained by taking the difference between its total revenue and its total costs. Its revenue is equal to its volume of output multiplied by the price at which units of output are sold. If the market in which the firm sells its product is very competitive, the firm will need to sell at the going market price. This, for example, is likely to be the case for the sale of table oysters and for penaeid prawns on the international market. Clearly, other things being equal, the higher the price for the aquaculture product, the higher will be the profit of the business. In some cases, however, there may be few or virtually no competitors in the market for the cultured product and, up to a point, an aquaculture business selling this product will be a price-maker (as opposed to a price-taker). This has been true of the Japanese cultured pearl industry but no longer appears to be the case, and is currently true in Australia for producers of pearl-oyster seed, and was so for cultured giant clams as aquarium specimen. It should be noted that the economic concept of costs differs from that of accounting. Economic costs are based on opportunity costs, that is, the economic benefit forgone by not choosing the best alternative to the choice actually made. For example, if family labour is supplied to an aquaculture business free of charge, this would not be included in the accounting cost of the business. However, if that family labour could earn an income if employed elsewhere, the highest income which it can earn elsewhere is its opportunity cost. In order to calculate economic cost, this opportunity cost would be imputed to the family labour employed.

Optimization of pH and temperature for aquaponics

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Abstract

Aquaponics is a technique of integrated soilless plant farming and fish culture. In an aquaponic system the pH and temperature should be monitored and maintained as the nitrifying bacteria need an optimum pH and temperature for its normal functioning. Hence, the present study was performed to determine the optimum level of the physical characters of the water (pH and temperature) to get the optimal production by following aquaponics technique. The system has three groups of living organisms: fish, plant and bacteria. The natural nitrifying bacteria help in nitrogen transformation. The plants cultured were edible tomato, a fruiting crop and edible spinach, a leafy vegetable. The fishes grown were edible fish tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) and ornamental goldfish. The tank was partitioned into two compartments using a net and the fishes were reared separately sharing the common water medium. The plants lettuce and tomatoes served as the natural filtering units and absorbed the nutrients from the water which was enriched with fish excrements and bacterial action. Proper aeration was given by air pump system. Maximum growth of the fishes were observed at pH 7.3 - 7.5 and temperature 77 °F to 86 °F. It was noticed that intake and growth of the fish was much reduced when there was a drop in the level of pH below 6. These results revealed that keeping the water chemistry at safe level in terms of pH and temperature is the best way to enhance the productivity of the fishes and plants.

Keywords: Aquaponics, Edible Fish Tilapia, pH, Temperature

Aquaponics - an alternative enterprise for production of genetically improved farmed tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* and spinach

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Abstract

Aquaponics is an intensive sustainable agricultural production system that connects hydroponic and aquaculture systems to produce multiple cash crops with reduced water and fertilizer inputs. It is highly suited for small farm producers targeting local markets and economic opportunities. It has many benefits like without fertilizers or chemical pesticides, usage of non-arable land, extremely water efficient, does not require soil, two agricultural products (fish and vegetables) are produced from one nitrogen source (fish food), can be more productive economically feasible where land and water are limited. Plant species like spinach, ladies finger, tomato are well grown. In this study, Genetically Improved Farmed Tilapia (GIFT) are selected for Aquaculture, as it is a fast growing and source of animal. The spinach is grown by the nutrients observed from the nitrogenous waste. The growth of the fish and spinach are observed continuously. The system produced higher amount of fish as well as vegetable with minimum water use having no environmental pollution. The system efficiently utilized fish waste in plant production through a symbiotic relationship between the fish and plants. Media bed technique is most popular design for small scale aquaponics which is efficient with space, low initial cost. Therefore, the system could be installed in high density city areas to produce fish and vegetable from the rooftop and backyard to address the environmental problems. The aquaponics system can produce fish and vegetable from the integration of aquaculture and hydroponics vegetable production using less water and without soil and fertilizer. The main aim of the experiment is to create plant growth by using aquatic animal waste.

Keywords: Aquaponics, spinach, hydroponic, ladies finger, tomato

GC-MS analysis and prediction of bioactivities in the petroleum ether extract of *Nitophyllum marginale* (Kutzing) J. Ag.

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Abstract

In recent years, a number of novel metabolites with effective pharmacological properties have been discovered from the marine macro algae which are considered to be the richest sources of the bioactive compounds suitable for therapeutic and medical applications. Emerging trend of increasing new molecules from seaweeds promotes the marine science towards the potential research area of drug discovery. With this background, the present study was carried out for the presence of biochemicals using GC-MS analysis and prediction of bioactivities in the petroleum ether extract of *Nitophyllum mariginale* (Kutzing) J.Ag. collected from Mandapam, Ramanathapuram district, Tamil Nadu, India. The active biological components in the petroleum ether extract of *Nitophyllum mariginale* were studied using Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS), and the biological activities were predicted by Prediction Activity Spectra for Substance (PASS) technique. The analysis exposed the two bioactive compounds such as 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, Mono(2-Ethylhexyl) Ester (69.78%) and Phenytoin (30.22%). In the study, totally 1933 biological activities were predicted in 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, Mono(2-Ethylhexyl) Ester, from this 74 were highly active and their Pa score is above 70%. There were 10 different activities predicted in Pa>0.7, and in Phenytoin, 1735 biological activities were predicted. Among those biological activities, 24 were highly active and their Pa score is above 70%. The present study afforded the bioactive components present in the petroleum ether extract of *Nitophyllum mariginale* (Kutzing) J.Ag. by GC-MS analysis and the Prediction Activity Spectra for Substance (PASS).

Keywords: GC-MS, PASS, Macro Algae, Bioactive compounds, *Nitophyllum mariginale*.

Distribution and effect of algae on freshwater and marine waters of Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Algae is an important term that describes a large and incredibly diverse group of organisms vary from microscopic to macroscopic. A study was made on collections of algae from fresh waters and estuarine waters in Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu. Kanyakumari District yielded a total of 52 species of algae, out of which 4 species recorded for the first time in this area. All the species recorded in the present study are illustrated and described clearly with standard keys. Collections were made with the help of 30mm bolting silk plankton net with a mouth size of 30 cm diameter. Collections were made in the early morning to avoid algal damage. All the samples were transported to the laboratory and preserved for identification. Identification was made with the help of dissections and a camera lucida drawings. Few species were not formulated and used for further culture work. Nutrients are play an important role in algal growth. With the help of standard keys nutrients were clearly identified. Taxonomic identification is the most useful analysis in the field of Science. Due to the decline of taxonomy studies present study was planned.

Keywords: Algae, Diverse Group, Standard Keys, camera Lucida.

Comparative assessment of water quality during fall season at Ukkadam and Kurichi lakes, Coimbatore

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Abstract

Water plays very important role in our daily life and hence the water bodies that supply water to human population, flora and fauna gain paramount importance. Due to urbanization and increase in population water bodies becomes polluted by addition of foreign materials such as plants and animal matter, domestic sewage and industrial effluents. In addition, dumping of solid wastes and indiscriminate encroachments leads to the diminishing quality of water delimiting its use for human consumption and aquatic life. Therefore, it is necessary for periodical monitoring of water quality to take prevention and remedial measures. In the current study, physico-chemical characteristics involving colour, odour, pH, temperature, total solids, acidity, alkalinity, levels of nitrate, iron, chemical oxygen demand and biological oxygen demand of water from two different sites, Ukkadam and Kurichi lakes were analyzed for their sustained portability for aquatic organisms, domestic animals and human beings. Observations indicated that Kurichi lake was less contaminated than Ukkadam lake and it is necessary to prevent these lakes from further deterioration. Subsequent studies on various aquatic life including fishes will be analyzed and the compatibility for consumption of these fishes will be assessed.

Keywords: Lake, physico-chemical, biological oxygen demand, water.

Impact of monochrotophos on haemoglobin level in *Anabas scanden*

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Abstract

The fishes are profound to an extensive diversity of toxicants in water. The attainment of pesticides into normal waters occupied by fish may clue to a severe weakening in fish production. Pesticides are known to modify the progress and nourishing content of fishes and their physiology. Heavy metals and pesticides of many chemical natures disturb biologically active enzymes and further physiological parameters. While examining the haemoglobin level in the blood of the experimental animal showing with Monochrotophos displays significant decline (Hb level - lower sub-lethal concentration 4.885 to 2.167 gm/dl of blood and higher sub-lethal concentration 4.89 to 1.9 gm/dl of blood) in two sub-lethal concentration different concentrations (lower sub-lethal concentration (2.388 ppm) and higher sub-lethal concentration (4.776 ppm)).

Keywords: Monochrotophos, Lower Sub-Lethal Concentration, Higher Sub-Lethal Concentration, Haemoglobin.

A study of fish species diversity in Pechiparai reservoir, Nagercoil, Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

Fish species diversity in Pechiparai reservoir was investigated from June – November 2021. The study revealed the occurrence of 6 species of fishes in the freshwater belonging to 3 families (Cichlidae, Cyprinidae, Bagridae) and 3 orders (Perciformes, Cypriniformes, Siluriformes). Of these fishes, the highest number of fish species were found to be *Etroplus suratensis* (37%) followed by *Etroplus maculatus* (26%), *Cirrhinus mrigala* (23%), *Ctenopharyngodon idella* (7%), *Oreochromis niloticus* (5%) and *Mystus gulio* (2%). Plastics waste, detergents, home wastage entering into water body represent a heavy source of environmental pollution in Pechiparai reservoir. It affects the fresh water fauna. With competing demands on limited water resources, awareness of the issues involved in water pollution, has led to considerable public debate about the environmental effects of Plastic sewages discharged into aquatic environments. The results of the present study deals with the fish species diversity .It was concluded that the samples of fresh water were highly polluted mostly associated with Plastic sewage discharge and it affects the fish species diversity.

Keywords: BIODIVERSITY, Pechiparai reservoir, Fish diversity, Sewages, Conservation.

Water quality status of Perungulam ponds in Tuticorin district, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Ponds are important wetlands located in and around human habitations as they are generally semi-natural ecosystems constructed by man in a landscape suitable for water stagnation. In the present study, an attempt has been made to determine the physico-chemical characteristics of Perungulam pond, located in the Tuticorin district of Tamil Nadu. These ponds are used for agriculture, fisheries and partially domestic activities. Rapid industrialization and indiscriminate use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture are causing heavy and varied pollution in the aquatic environment, leading to deterioration of water quality and depletion of aquatic biota. In order to prevent these problems, an understanding of basic water chemistry and other physical parameters is necessary. So the study was conducted to analyze the physiochemical properties like color, turbidity, odor, TS, electrical conductivity, pH, alkalinity, total hardness, phosphate, nitrate and chloride of water samples collected from Perungulam ponds in Tuticorin District. It is found that, based on the WHO results, the samples fall under an excellent category and hence are not suitable for drinking and irrigation purposes.

Keywords: Physico-chemical, pond, chemical fertilizers, pollution, water quality.

Impact of mobile phone radiation in iridescent shark, *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* (Sauvage, 1878)

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Abstract

The cell phones have revolutionized our living pattern. Mobile phones use electromagnetic waves and radio waves for transmitting signals in the seconds. Recent studies shown that even very low frequency of radio waves can change the neurobehavioral pattern of brain in Zebra fishes. 10 live fish samples (Iridescent Shark) were collected from Daddy's aquarium, Kolathur, Chennai. They were reared in the fish tank for first 3 days for adapting to the new environment. The oxygen was provided by the air filters artificially. 10 sharks were separated into 2 groups namely control group and experimental group. The experimental fishes were exposed to mobile phone (Micromax A58) for 1 hour and control group was not exposed to any mobile phone radiation. 3 mobile phones were introduced namely Micromax A58, Q4202 and DE tel. The observations were recorded using mobile phone camera and photographed for one week. Morphological characteristics such as length, breadth and weight were measured using weighing device and measuring tape. The Fishes were preserved in Formalin in order to conduct study on lipid peroxidation in tissue samples such as liver, kidney and brain. The samples which had the organic layer was taken and analysed in the UV-spectrometer at 532 nm. Morphology of the control groups were compared with the experimental groups it had shown drastic changes such as weight loss, increased length and reduced metabolism. The experimental fishes showed the weight loss of 1gm daily. But in the control group there is no weight loss. The size of the experimental fishes increased daily but not in the control group. These observations had shown that the mobile phone radiation may have an effect on food intake of fishes and also reduced the metabolic rate in them. From these above studies we can conclude that the mobile phone usage may influence our own biological system to produce lipid peroxides that affect cell division and increase the oxidative stress in the cells.

Freshwater *Icthyophis* diversity with special reference to a pond in Vatanappally, Thrissur, Kerala

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Abstract

A pond is an area filled with water, either natural or artificial, that is smaller than a lake. Ponds are usually by definition quite shallow waterbodies with varying abundances of aquatic plants and animals. The study was carried out in a pond in the village Ganeshamangalam, Vatanappally, Thrissur, Kerala, India. The fish diversity and abundance of the pond were observed and analysed for the last one year. The identification of specimens were carried out using different methods. The study revealed fish diversities of 13 fish species belonging to 7 orders and 11 different families. During the study Siluriformes and Anabantiformes were the most abundantly found orders followed by Cyprinodontiformes, Cichliformes, Gobiiformes, Beloniformes and Cypriniformes. The study reveals the necessity of conservation of ponds.

Keywords: Fish diversity, ponds, conservation.

Ichthyofaunal biodiversity of village pond Khertha, Balod District, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract

Freshwater fish biodiversity especially in rural areas is very important because of employment generation and livelihood. Traditionally aquaculture is done in the rural area by the fisherman community, they do not have proper knowledge in terms of scientific perspective. So the present study aims to prepare a list of fishes found in village pond khertha. Fishes serve mankind in two ways it serves as a good source of protein and also provide a mode of employment. Fishes as a food source can combat the problem of malnutrition in the rural area. In this study, an endeavour had been made to list all species found in this pond with their local names. Village khertha is situated in the Dondilohara block of district Balod of Chhattisgarh state. A total of 17 species from different families were found. Recorded fish species were classified in 4 order and 5 families. Order Cypriniformes were found as a dominant group. The main fishes found are *Catla catla*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, *Labeo rohita*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Clarius batrachus*, and *Oreochromis mossambicus*.

Keywords: Biodiversity, village pond, malnutrition, freshwater.

Impact of aspartame on gill tissue transaminase activity in *Labeo rohita*

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Abstract

Artificial sweetener have gained a lot of attention in the present generation due to its increasing food products formulations which began to attract the consumers. So, to throw highlights on the present study was mainly focussed on the effect of aspartame, an artificial sweetener induced on freshwater fish, *Labeo rohita* under laboratory conditions for 72 hrs and also to investigate the effect of aspartame on transaminases activity, total protein in selected gill tissue. Investigations was carried out by using *Labeo rohita* fishes weighing about 100-120 gms administered by dissolving the aspartame at a concentration of 100 mM, 200 mM, 300 mM and the results were indicated. Results of our present study clearly shows that in gill tissue, total protein, AST and ALT activity increased significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) at 100 mM, 200 mM and 300 Mm when compared to the control group. However, the over uses of these food additives must be strictly restricted and properly disposed in order to avoid the ecotoxicological impacts which disturbs the physiological behaviour in aquatic organisms.

Keywords: Aspartame, ALT, AST, Total protein, *Labeo rohita*

Impact of chlorpyrifos toxicity on early embryonic development and behavior in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)

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Abstract

Indiscriminate use of pesticides in Indian agricultural fields including rice, cotton, sugarcane, groundnut and maize is a major environmental problem in India. Chlorpyrifos (CPF) is one of the most toxic pesticides in aquatic ecosystem, but its toxicity mechanisms are less understood. The zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is a small cyprinid fish from the Ganges and Brahmaputra river basins in India had become an increasingly popular and versatile vertebrate genetic model in genetics, neurophysiology, biomedicine, developmental biology and also to assess impacts of environmental threats. Here, we aim to investigate the toxic effects of Chlorpyrifos on developmental, biochemical and behavioral parameters in zebrafish. Upon CPF (100 and 300 µg/L) exposure, zebrafish showed firstly, severe embryonic development delay in attaining different developmental stages (1000 cell stage, 50% Epiboly, Gastrulation, 16 somite stage and 24 somite stage). Secondly, CPF exposure decreased hatchability (30-50%), decreased total body length in fry, reduced heart rate, and resulted in morphological abnormalities viz. spinal curvature deformities (SD), pericardial edema (PE) and heart looping in larval zebrafish. Thirdly, CPF exposure induced oxidative stress in the larval zebrafish. The malondialdehyde (MDA) levels increased and glutathione (GSH) contents decreased significantly in a concentration-dependent manner after exposure to CPF for 96 hours post fertilization (hpf). Finally, photo-response swimming and free swimming behaviors of zebrafish larvae in response to light stimulation and light to dark photoperiod transition were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced. Our findings suggest that CPF has the potential to cause developmental toxicity, behavior alterations and oxidative stress in larval zebrafish.

Keywords: zebrafish, chlorpyrifos, embryonic development, pericardial edema, oxidative stress, photo-response swimming behaviour

Larvivorous fishes controlling mosquito larvae

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Abstract

Mosquito borne diseases continue to be a major problem in almost all tropical and subtropical countries. There is growing concern of the effects of insecticide used in controlling the vectors of human diseases. A wide range of organisms helps to regulate mosquito populations naturally through predation, parasitism and competition. As biological mosquito control agents, larvivorous fish are being used extensively all over the world since the early 1900s. The position of mouth is one of the important characteristics to determine the larvivorous capability of a fish. From the point of view of their efficacy in controlling mosquito larvae, typical surface feeders such as *Aplocheilichthys* and *Gambusia* which fulfill the characteristics of features of larvivorous fish. Some surface feeders which are less efficient owing to their mode of life eg. *Oryzias*, *Labistes*, *Aphanius*, etc. Sub-surface feeders like *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Danio*, *Rasbora*, etc, column feeders like *Puntius* spp., *Colisa*, *Chanda*, *Anabas*, etc, which feed on mosquito larvae when chance permits. Fry of carps and mullets which are helpful in controlling mosquito larvae. Predatory fishes like *Wallago*, *Channa*, *Notopterus* and *Mystus* whose fry destroy mosquito larvae but whose adults may predate upon other fish including larvicidal fish species.

Keywords: Larvivorous fish, Insecticide.

Study of biological aspects of freshwater copepods and cyclopoids

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Abstract

Aquaculture farms have gained a rapid interest due to the increasing demand of finfish and shellfish as economically important and inevitable protein source for the nutrition of human being. Progress has been made in identifying the dietary requirement of the larvae of various aquaculture species. Development of low cost feed input for enhancement of farmed fish products becomes an important aspect to be studied. Rotifers, calanoids, copepods have been considered as the living capsule of nutrition for many cultivable species. In the present study an attempt has been made to elucidate the biology and culture of *Mesocyclops* species. Laboratory culture was carried out using 1 litres, 5 litre containers. Animals were harvested at the end of 10th, 20th and 30th day of culture. Further, the culture was carried out in 25 litre containers under the field conditions. Feeding experiments were also conducted on the growth of post larvae of fresh water prawn and also on the larvae of ornamental fishes which comprised of gold fish, mollies, and guppies. Improved growth for prawn larvae in terms of weight was observed when compared to the length of the larvae.

Keywords: Rotifers, calanoids and copepods

Antibacterial activity of endophytic bacteria isolated from the root nodules of *Nelumbo nucifera* against fish pathogens

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Abstract

Endophytic bacteria are the beneficial bacteria that live in plant tissues without doing substantive harm or gaining benefit other than residency, they can improve plant growth under normal and challenging conditions. This present study aimed to investigate the possible use of endophytic bacteria in the treatment of fish bacterial diseases in aquaculture practise, which is facing high yield loss, due to the increase of productivity the sector was accompanied by ecological impacts including the emergence of a large variety of pathogens and bacterial resistance. Totally 12 endophytic bacteria were isolated from the root nodules of *Nelumbo nucifera* with different colony morphology and colour; further screened for antibacterial activity using the well diffusion method against fish pathogens; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Serratia marcescens*, and *Aeromonas hydrophila*. In the preliminary screening the supernatant of two isolates NN1 and NN3 showed activity in which the isolate NN3 showed the highest level of activity against *A. hydrophila*, *E. coli*, and *S. aureus* with the zone of inhibition of 4 mm, 2 mm, and 3 mm respectively. The active strains were further solvent (ethyl acetate and petroleum ether) extracted to check the antibacterial activity of bacterial metabolites using the disc diffusion method. The ethyl acetate extract of NN3 showed prominent activity against *A. hydrophila* with an inhibition zone of 8mm. Based on the biochemical and molecular characterization the active isolate NN3 was identified as *Lysinibacillus capcisi*. This present investigation clearly shows that the root nodules of *N. nucifera* can be explored as a source of antibiotics from effective endophytic bacteria that tend to control fish pathogens.

Keywords: *Nelumbo nucifera*, Endophytic bacteria, Antibacterial activity, Fish pathogens

Observation of aquatic organisms in the relation to birds' population in the Nilgiris reservoirs

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Abstract

Wetlands are traditional zones that occupy an intermediate position between dry land and open water. These wetlands are rich in flora and fauna and birds are one of the important biotic factors which prefer to live near these wetlands. Aquatic birds are an important component of most of the wetland ecosystems, as they occupy several trophic levels in the food web of wetland nutrient cycles. The study area was selected to the Nilgiris division, Tamil Nadu. Commonly Red Wattled Lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*), Yellow Bittern (*Ixobrychus sinensis*), Indian spot-billed duck (*Anas poecilorhyncha*), Little cormorant (*Microcarbo niger*), Common kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*), Grey wagtail (*Motacilla cinerea*), Western yellow wagtail (*Motacilla flava*), White-browed wagtail (*Motacilla maderaspatensis*), pond heron (*Ardeola*), cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) was observed in water source areas like lakes, streams, river and swamp. More number of birds observed in the pond ecosystem 26% is habitually preferred by the water birds followed by lake 23%, swamp 21%, river 18% and a smaller number of birds observed in agricultural land 12%. These birds feed on lots of the aquatic animals in the wetland like lizards, frogs, crab, fish and insects. The water birds are one of the animals that are at the top of the food chain in the wetland food web.

Keywords: Wetland, Bird Diversity, Western Ghats, Habitat, Feeding.

Antagonistic activity of probiotic bacteria isolated from the gut of *Dawkinsia filamentosa* (Valenciennes, 1844) against fish pathogens

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Abstract

Gut flora has a continuous and dynamic effect on the host's gut and systemic immune response. The gut microbiota of fresh water fish, *Dawkinsia filamentosa* has been studied to isolate and identify probiotic bacteria. In the present study, a total of 15 bacteria were isolated from the intestine samples of *D. filamentosa* with different colony morphology and colour; further screened for antagonistic activity using the agar overlaying and well diffusion method against *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Vibrio cholera*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. In the preliminary screening, 3 strains showed wide range of activity against selected fish pathogens in which the isolate DF12 showed the highest level of activity with the inhibitory zone of 8 mm against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and 6 mm against *Vibrio cholerae* in agar overlaying method. In well diffusion method the isolate DF12 showed the highest activity, followed by DF 6 and DF8 showed the moderate level of activity against selected fish pathogens. The active bacterial strains were identified as *Enterococcus* sp (DF6), *Lactobacillus* sp (DF8), and *Bacillus* sp (DF12) based on morphological and biochemical characterisation. This isolates was able to survive and grow from pH 4 to 8 with the highest viability, the growth rate was neutral at pH7. In addition, the isolates tolerated 0, 0.15, and 3.0 bile salt concentration. This present investigation clearly shows that the fish gut can be explored as a promising source of antagonistic bacteria. These probiotic bacteria have warranted much research interest because of their broad specificity on antibacterial potential against fish pathogens.

Keywords: *Dawkinsia filamentosa*, Gut probiotic, Antagonistic activity and Biochemical characterization.

**A preliminary survey of wetland birds at pond, Suthamalli, Tirunelveli,
Tamilnadu**

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Abstract

Wetlands support all life forms and perform useful functions to maintenance of ecological balance. Wetlands provide a habitat for birds and birds use them for breeding, nesting, and rearing young ones. Waterfowls are one of the most significant components of biodiversity. Water birds are good bio-indicators and useful models for studying a variety of environmental problems. The study of wetland birds at Suthamalli pond, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India, revealed a total of 24 wetland bird species belonging to 11 families and 7 orders. Totally 1198 individual wetland birds were encountered during the study period from November 2020 to April 2021. The present research work has been designed to focus on their diversity with an aim to conserve these bird species.

Keywords: Wetland, Ecological Balance, Bio-Indicators & Diversity.

The efficiency of reverse osmosis and bamboo filtration systems for the aquarium fishes management

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Abstract

Water filters are now widely used around the world to provide highly purified freshwater. The quality of water is very essential for aquarium fish production and culture. The groundwater contains a high levels of toxic elements namely fluoride, chlorine, chloramines, nitrates, and phosphates for aquarium fishes. The variable major and minor ions constitutions are present in portable water which was distributed through Municipal Corporation, it will lead to aquarium fish diseases, to avoid these issues the commercial aquarium centers need to be adapted efficient filtration systems. The experiments have been conducted to estimate the filter's efficiency at the college aquarium. From the aquarium, in different frequencies, about 80 number of water samples were collected at different intervals between before and after filtration of the RO and Bamboo filters. The RO filter is highly efficient to reduce the waste levels in aquarium water. Similarly, when assessed in the Bamboo filter, the efficient level of about 60% (reduced BOD, COD, turbidity, and hardness) was observed and this filter assembling material is widely available at low cost and can be easily fabricated compared to the RO filter. During the experiment, the RO filter has efficiency for removal of 91% such paraments like turbidity, DO, nitrite, COD, and BOD was observed. The above-discussed results are clearly indicated that the differentiation of efficiency between bamboo and RO filters; it can be used in aquarium based on the volume of water recirculation with limitation parameter.

Keywords: Fluoride, chlorine, chloramines, nitrates, and phosphates

Observation of changes in body colouration and immune response using cucumber and garlic extract in aquarium fish *Pethia conchonchius* (Rosy barb)

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Abstract

Rosy barb (*Pethia conchonchius*) is a common aquarium candidate fish species. People are preferring more to keep these fishes in their home aquarium as they are prettifying and creates peace of mind. These commercially important fish species are facing less attractive coloration patterns and immune deficiency issues, leading to poor market viability and frequent occurrence of common disease. Rosy barb are omnivorous, hence there are lots of food choices for their diet. The food ingredients plays a vital role to improve the colour patterns and enhance immune system, which are prominently available in our traditional edible sources. Formulated feeds for these species are very limited. This issue can be solved by providing feed additives. This study was carried out to know about the effects of garlic extract on the colouration and metabolism. When the garlic extract and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) were given, notable differences were seen when compared to synthetic feed. Also, the findings demonstrate that immersion in garlic extract offers an effective, alternative treatment against common diseases in Rosy barb. Here, notable differences were observed in their behavior and coloration in a short duration when compared to synthetic feed. Hence, cucumber may be a good alternative feed for coloration and garlic extract was also helpful in boosting the immune system in making the fishes more active. Thus, our traditional herbal based ingredients which may be very effective therapeutic agents to maintain the high health of commercially important aquarium fishes.

Keywords: Garlic extract, *Cucumis sativus*, Fish feed, traditional & medicinal food, body colouration.

Study on the ichthyofaunal diversity of Chettuva backwaters, Thrissur, Kerala

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Abstract

Aquatic biodiversity is significant with tremendous social, economic and environmental impacts. The Kerala backwaters are a network of brackish lagoons and lakes lying parallel to Arabian Sea coast with unique ecosystem. Chettuva backwater is located in between Engandiyur panchayath and Kadappuram panchayath of Thrissur district in Kerala. This backwater start at Enamakkal lake and empties to Arabian Sea. Chettuva backwater is well known for mangrove ecosystem, islands and estuary associated with it. The present investigation dealt with ichthyofaunal diversity of Chettuva backwaters. 21 species of fin fishes belonging to 16 different families were recorded from the study site. Highest number of species were recorded from Lutjanidae family. The most abundant species reported was *Mugil cephalus* and least abundant species was *Hyporamphus xanthopterus*. From the study conducted it was analyzed that several anthropogenic activities have drastically threatened the fish diversity of Chettuva backwaters.

Keywords: Ichthyofaunal diversity, Chettuva backwaters, Lutjanidae, *Mugil cephalus*, *Hyporamphus xanthopterus*

Water quality and soil management of fish ponds

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Abstract

Maintenance of a healthy aquatic environment and production of sufficient fish food organisms in ponds are two factors of primary importance for successful ponds culture operation. It is believed that water is the primary requisite to support aquatic life where as soil is essential to withhold it. The physical conditions of water is greatly influenced with depth, temperature, turbidity and light. These constitute the more important physical parameters on which the productivity of a pond depends. Depth of a pond has an important bearing on the physical and chemical qualities of water. Depth determine the temperature, the circulation pattern of water and extent of photosynthetic activity. Light is another physical factor of importance. Availability of light energy to a fish pond greatly influences its productivity as primary production or synthesis carbohydrate is a photochemical process energized by light. Chemical parameters among the chemical factors influencing aquatic productivity, the pH value, and alkalinity, dissolved gasses like oxygen, carbon dioxide and dissolved inorganic nutrients like P, N are considered to be important.

Keywords: Photosynthesis, carbon dioxide, alkalinity, turbidity

Studies on the diversity and ecology of Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera (EPT) complexes of selected stream in southern India.

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Abstract

Aquatic insects are vital elements in the ecological dynamics of lotic environments playing an important role in the cycle of materials and in trophic transfers. Among aquatic insects Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera (EPT complexes) comprise the assemblages in low and medium order stony cobble streams. These organisms are sensitive to environmental perturbations and occur in clean and well oxygenated water. In this present study is an attempt to assess the diversity and ecology of EPT complex of selected stream in southern India. The study on the diversity and ecology will be carried out for two years for different selected streams. EPT complexes are essential ecological component of both aquatic and terrestrial food webs and contain a diversity of taxa that grade from extreme in sensitivity and tolerance pollution. Most species of EPT complexes are associated with high quality water habitats in streams and rivers because they have specific life cycle requirements, they are important indicators in applied studies where aquatic communities are used for assessment of biological integrity and overall ecological health. One of the most important factors that determine freshwater diversity is the spatial hierarchical organization of streams which has structured diversity at multiple temporal scales from species diversification to population genetic structure. Moreover, these aquatic insects show responses to a wide array of potential pollutants and are sensitive to both short-term and long-term conditions affecting water quality. In this present study is an attempt to assess the diversity and distribution of EPT complexes through the analyses of structure, scanning electron microscopic studies of selected EPT complexes egg and functioning of the complex ecosystem.

Keywords: Aquatic insects, EPT Complexes, diversity, fresh water, ecosystem

Studies on aquatic floral diversity in three perennial ponds of Midalam panchayat at Kanyakumari district

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Abstract

Pond diversity is regarded as one of the most important hotspots of plant variety in village and rural settings. Three ponds in the Midalam panchayat in Kanyakumari district were studied for aquatic plant diversity. The chosen pond was found across Kanyakumari district, stretching from the south to the north. The research region was visited five times for aquatic plant collecting. The aquatic plants that were gathered were identified and morphologically analysed. There were 21 plant species were identified, divided into 17 families. The members were falling under five ecological divisions of hydrophytes such as *Azolla pinnata*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Salvinia molesta*, *Pistia stratiotes*, and *Ludwigia adscendens*. The economic significance of these plants was investigated. All of the plants found were commercially important. During the study period, physico-chemical parameters including as colour, odour, transparency, total dissolved solids, dissolved oxygen, pH, calcium, and others were examined. Variations were found in the many parameters that were examined. To maintain these ponds, they must be monitored at several levels. The local folks can be made aware of the cultivation of some of the plants as possible therapeutic sources.

Keywords: Midalam, Physico-chemical parameters, Hydrophytes, Pond diversity.

Taxonomic features of commercially available selected ornamental fishes

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Abstract

India has a rich diversity of ornamental fish, with over 195 indigenous varieties reported from North-East Region and Western Ghats, and nearly 400 species from marine ecosystems. Indian ornamental fish trade mostly deals with freshwater fish (90%) of which 98% are cultured and 2% are captured from wild. The remaining 10% are marine fishes of which 98% are captured and 2% culture. Majority of the Ornamental Fish Breeders in India breed exotic fishes and very few breed indigenous, marine and brackish water fish. Ornamental fish farming has been an interesting activity for many and provides not only aesthetic pleasure but also financial opening. Ornamental fishes are usually attractive colorful fishes of different characteristics or of different patterns. These are also known as aquarium fishes as pets in confined spaces for fun or fancy. Ornamental fish keeping and its propagation has been an important activity for many which provide not only aesthetic pleasure but also financial openings. Chennai is blessed with more of ornamental fishes. In this paper about 15 species of commercially available ornamental fishes in Chennai are selected for their taxonomic features, and general characteristics.

A study on the existence of *Artemia parthenogenetica* in the saltpans of Kanyakumari district

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Abstract

The brine shrimp or *Artemia* is an important live feed for fin fish and shellfish larve culture. *Artemia parthenogenetica* is our native *Artemia* species. Survey reports say that an exotic species *Artemia franciscana* is present throughout our native saltpans. There is a need for confirming the existence of our native species whether mixes with the exotic population of *Artemia*. There are reports say that the exotic species when overcome the native species, the native species will vanish. Hence this study was under taken to know the existence of the native species and the reason for its disappearance. This study will help to protect our native species to some extent, if it exists with the exotic population. The cysts were collected from the selected saltpan in Kanyakumari District. The morphological characteristics features like size variation of *Artemia* cyst collected from the saltpans of Kanyakumari District during different season were studied. The present study showed that the collected cyst had three size ranges, such as 150-200, 200-250 and 250 μm and above. The largest size group 250 μm and above was selected and allowed to hatching. From these study it is concluded that there was no *Artemia parthenogenitica* present in the saltpans, because all the progeny obtained were found to be bisexual.

Keywords: *Artemia* Cyst, Hatching, *Artemia parthenogenetica*

Types of fish breeding and their importance

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Abstract

The propagation of fish by the artificial way for a commercial purpose is known as fish breeding. The breeding, rearing, and transplantation of fish by artificial means is called pisciculture or fish farming. Good atmosphere, space, temperature, pH, availability of live food, and lighting are all responsible for proper breeding. There are many fish farming methods for propagation, such as cage systems, open net-pen systems, irrigation ditch or pond systems, composite fish culture, traditional fry farming, and indoor fish farming. As we all know, fish is a cold-blooded animal that can adjust its body temperature according to the surrounding atmosphere. The major freshwater fishes cultured in India are- Major carps (*Catla*, *Labeo*, Mrigal), Minor carps (*Labeo calbasu*, *Labeo bata*), Murrels (*Channa punctatus*, *Channa striatus*, *Channa marulius*), Catfishes (*Clarias batracus*, *Heteropneustes fossilis*, *Clarias macrocephalus*, *Anabas testudineus*, *Etroplus suratensis*, *Wallago attu*, *Mystus seenghala*), Exotic fishes (*Cyprinus carpio*, *Osphronemus goramy*, *Ctenopharyngodon idella*, *Hypothalamichthys molitrix*, *Tilapia mossambicus*) Coldwater fishes (*Salmo giardneri*, *Tor tor*, *Tor khudree*, *Tinca tinca*). We all know that fishes are a rich source of nutritious food and highly rich in proteins, vitamins (A, D and K), fats, minerals, and carbohydrates. In most fishes, the flesh contains about 13 to 20 % of protein and has a food value of 300 to 1600 calories per pound. The scrap from the entire fish is called fish meal and is used as artificial food for poultry, pig, and cattle. The fish meal contains about 60% protein and a high percentage of calcium phosphate, which is valuable for cattle and poultry. The refined oil from the liver of fishes has medicinal use and is a rich source of vitamin A, and D. Liver oil contains 55-75% fat, 5-10% protein, and the rest is water. At present, aquaculture increases the number of possible jobs in different sectors. Sustainable, productive fisheries improve food and nutrition security, increase income, and improve livelihood. In addition to serving as an essential food item, fishes provide several byproducts to us. Fish breeding is necessary for the world's growing demand for food.

Keywords: *Labeo calbasu*, *Labeo bata*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Osphronemus goramy*

Acute toxicity of heavy metal, zinc chloride in Indian major carps

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Abstract

The major threat to aquatic animals and the entire aquatic ecosystem is the anthropogenic input of heavy metals. The pollutants which are the main sources of industry, domestic sewage and agricultural waste contaminate the aquatic ecosystem. The main aspiration of this study is to investigate the acute toxicity effects of Zinc chloride on Indian major carps like *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita* and *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Fish samples were exposed to different concentrations (2 ppm, 5 ppm, 10 ppm, 15 ppm and 20 ppm) of Zinc chloride at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, 72 hrs and 96 hrs. In the present investigation, the 96hrs LC50 and lethal concentration of Zinc chloride were determined under controlled conditions. The sublethal exposure causes severe physical and physiological effects. Acute toxicity determines the toxicant concentration, causing 50% mortality in the population within the defined time interval, usually 48 to 96 hours. The present study evaluates the maximum dose that may be tolerated by the fishes. All three Indian major carps showed significantly higher sensitivity. At 96 hrs LC50 the lethal concentration of Zinc chloride varied significantly.

Keywords: heavy metals, acute toxicity, Zinc chloride, Indian major carps, sublethal.

Effect of different dietary inclusion levels of blue green algae, *Spirulina* (*Spirulina platensis*) on the food utilization *Cirrhinus mrigala* fingerlings

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Abstract

Spirulina species are most commonly used in nutritional supplements. It is cheaper feed ingredient than other animal origin. A 60 days experiment was done with a view to analyze the effects of probiotic *Spirulina* diets on the growth of *Cirrhinus mrigala* fingerlings. Results proved that the *Spirulina* feeds elicited the beneficial effect and it can increase the survivability of fish and accelerates the growth of *Cirrhinus mrigala* fingerlings. Feeding on spirulina helped to improve disease resistance of fish resulting in an improvement in their survival rate. At the end of the experiment (60 days), fish fingerlings from all treatments were weighed, based on which the growth parameters like weight gain (%), Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR), Specific Growth Rate (SGR) and Survival (%) were calculated. Supplementing 9-11% spirulina in the diets of both the fishes resulted increased weight gain (WG- 254 & 216%, respectively), specific growth rate (SGR-2.0 for both the species) and decreased food conversion ratio (FCR-1.2 for both the species) in comparison to control (T0) group (WG 88 %; SGR 1.0 % and FCR 3.4). Results revealed that supplementing 7-10% of *Spirulina* in fish diet results higher growth rate, decreased FCR with higher survival rate, leads to higher return from the fisheries business.

Keywords: fresh water fish, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, Fingerlings, Growth, Survival, FCR

**Bactericidal activity of epidermal mucus extracts of fresh water spiney eel fish
(*Mastacembelus armatus*)**

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Abstract

The aquatic environment is rich in pathogenic organisms, and the aquatic fishes are highly prone to the invasion of these pathogens. The skin of many fish species is covered with a layer of mucus that acts as a barrier between the fish and environment. Fish skin mucus has been reported to prevent colonisation of pathogenic bacteria. The objective of the present study was to explore the antibacterial activity of epidermal mucus extracts from fresh water spiney eel fish *Mastacembelus armatus* against human bacterial pathogens. The crude (without solvents), aqueous (0.85% physiological saline), acidic (3% acetic acid), organic (ethanol+dichloromethane), extracts of skin mucus were prepared and tested for antibacterial activity by agar well method against two gram positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus albus*, *Bacillus cereus*) and two gram negative (*Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae*) bacteria. In this present study highest antibacterial activity was observed from crude mucus extract against all four human pathogenic bacteria. The crude (15 mm), aqueous (15 mm), acidic (17 mm), and organic (14 mm) extracts showed a maximum zone of inhibition against *Vibrio cholerae*. The present result suggests that the mucus extracts of spiney eel fish *Mastacembelus armatus* may be a potential source of antibacterial agents for human pathogens.

Keywords: Epidermal mucus, zone of inhibition, *Mastacembelus armatus*

Bioinformatics - the next big thing in aquaculture

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Abstract

Bioinformatics deals with the development of computational methods for studying the structure, function and evolution of genes, proteins and whole genomes. User convenience and availability are the determining factors of these tools being widely used in bioinformatics research. BLAST, FASTA (FAST-All), EMBOSS, ClustalW, RasMol and Protein Explorer, Cn3D, Swiss PDB viewer, Hex, Vega, Bioeditor etc. are commonly operated bioinformatics software tools in fisheries and aquaculture research. Aquaculture scientists can use bioinformatics for genomic data manipulation, genome annotation and expression profiling, molecular folding, modeling, and design as well as generating biological network and system biology. Therefore, they can contribute in specified fields of aquaculture such as disease diagnosis and aquatic health management, fish nutritional aspects and culture-able strain development. Bioinformatics has been a revolution in the field of science and in recent times it has been associated with various fields of sciences due to the explosion of publicly available genomic information resulting from the Human Genome Project. The goal of this project was determination of the sequence of the entire human genome (approximately three billion base pairs) and it was completed in April 2003. If Bioinformatics could do such a wonder in humans what could be in store in aquaculture. This paper discusses varieties of avenues for Bioinformatics in the field of aquaculture.

Keywords: BLAST, FASTA, ClustalW, RasMol

A study on the diversity of brachyuran crabs in Tiruchendur coast

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Abstract

The diversity and abundance of marine crabs from a collapsible crab trap fishery were observed from August 2021 to November 2021 at Manapad, Alanthalai and Singadurai sampling stations. The results showed that there were 13 species belonging to 8 families (Portunoidae, Cancridae, Liocranidae, Majidae samouelle, Calappoideae, Aethridae, Parthenopidae, Dorippidae) under 2 orders (Araneae and Decapoda). Out of the three stations, Alanthalai has rich biodiversity of 53 crabs this may be due to the availability of suitable substratum such as coral rocks. Crab species belonging to family Portunidae were dominant followed by families Majidae samouelle and Parthenopidae over all the families recorded in the study. Seasonal factors influenced the abundance of some crabs, for example, the abundance of *Scylla serrata* was correlated with temperature. The maximum diversity indices value was recorded during August whereas the minimum value during November. The study thus reveals that Alanthalai serves as a good feeding and breeding ground of crabs among the selected coastal areas.

Keywords: Brachyuran crabs, Species Diversity, Abundance, Tiruchendur coast

Synthesis and characterization of fish mucus nanoparticles and its antibacterial activity

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Abstract

Nanotechnology has become an extensive field of research due to the unique properties of nanoparticles which enable novel applications. Nanoparticles have found their way into many applications in the field of medicine including diagnostics, vaccination, drug and gene delivery. Simple Methodology was developed to synthesis Copper Sulphate (CuSo₄ Np) using mucus of Indian major carp, rohu, *L. rohita*. The biological properties due to the presence of numerous proteins and amino acids were studied. The mucus of *L. rohita* was used as stabilizing agent for CuSo₄ NPs synthesis from copper sulphate/sulfate. CuSo₄ NPs were used as an antibacterial agent against bacterial pathogens like *E. coli*, *Bacillus* sp, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Fish mucus NP exhibited significant activity against pathogens. The result clearly indicated that synthesized CuSo₄ NP could be served as a biomaterial for antibacterial treatment.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, antibacterial, pathogens, *L. rohita*.

***Aeromonas* infection and its preventive measures in fish farming**

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Abstract

In the present scenario of aquaculture practices, diagnosis and prevention of diseases have become a challenge for a sustainable production and management of seafoods. Over pollution, population explosion, nutritional deficiencies, poor sanitation, intensive and semi-intensive farming and emerging new diseases pose a serious threat in the fish production to meet the consumers demand. Over use of antibiotics and powerful chemical based therapeutic drugs to treat these diseases eventually lead to antibiotic resistant bacteria and other new diseases. *Aeromonas* infection in fish is one such bacterial disease which causes fatal hemorrhagic septicemia forming lesions and ulcers which demands a serious attention for its effective control and prevention as it is more susceptible in economically important fresh water fishes. Alternate therapy like oral administration of humus extract, phytochemicals enriched fish feed, vaccines and other strategies like stocking levels, sanitation water quality are found to be more effective against *Aeromonas* infection by induced immune response in fish and this article encompasses various methods of diagnosis, prevention and treatment for the same.

Keywords: Nutritional, Lesions, Ulcers.

Identification of *Vibrio* species in the diseased *Penaeus monodon* along the coastal system of Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Aquaculture is a booming sector on all over the world especially south Asian countries (India, China, Japan, Indonesia etc.). Many microbial diseases outbreaks lead to severe economic loss in shrimp industry particularly the *Vibrio* infection. In the present study we selected ten different sampling sites and collected diseased wild species of *Penaeus monodon*. The infected part was plated on TCBS agar and the isolated colonies were identified using standard Bergey's manual of determinative bacteriology. We identified that two sampling sites Samiyarpettai and Parangipettai showed high mortality rate of *Vibrio* species level and also we found that *Vibrio paraheamolyticus* was most dominant species than other *Vibrio* sp.

Keywords: *Vibrio* sp, *Penaeus monodon*, Parangipettai, *Vibrio paraheamolyticus*

Studies on suitability of ornamental fishes and spinach in the aquaponics system

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Abstract

The goal of the aquaponic system was to establish a self-sustaining herbs production in an applied research environment based on an ornamental aquarium as a nutrient source for the plant. This study aims to expose the performances of growth parameters, both in terms of quantity and quality for the varieties of spinach (*Coriandrum sativum* and *Trigonella foenum*) produced in a aquaponic integrated system along with ornamental fishes (koi carp, goldfish, molly, barbs and silver shark). The experimental design consists of a recirculating aquaculture system with 7 growing units, mechanical and biological water treatment units, and two aquaponic units. The plant's initial and final biomass was taken and a series of periodic measurements were noted. Chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids, ash, and dry matter were determined from spinach leaf. The plant biomass gains registered good values and the quality of final products given by the chlorophyll a, b, carotenoids, and dry matter content were in the optimal variation interval, compared to market spinach. In this study, it can be concluded that the differences were recorded in terms of growth performance and crops quality, between the experimental variants. Also, the quality of spinach grown in aquaponic conditions, by using an aquarium is similar to that of the marketable spinach, growth conventional.

Keywords: Aquaponics, Ornamental aquarium, Spinach, Koi carp and Chlorophyll

Fish toxicology - hazardous phenomenon

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Abstract

Toxicology, a branch of science which deals with the study of causes, effects, statistics and consequences of various types of anthropogenic as well natural chemical and physical agents which enters the aquatic ecosystem and harm the entire marine or freshwater organisms. The organism which are more prone to toxin materials are various fishes, crabs, aquatic insects and other organisms. It is very important to understand the adverse and diverse effects of toxins on aquatic organisms like fishes as it provides a greater platform to study about the toxins and mechanisms of action in the host, so that we could prevent the usage of such compounds to avoid harming the aquatic ecosystem. Study of aquatic toxicology also paves the way to use the aquatic resources like fishes, crabs and others beings as model organisms to study their neurological, behavioral and endocrinological reactions towards the toxins which can be useful in future aspects which in turn can help the scientists to work on these particular areas aiming to be health, nutritional and developmental aspects of fishes. This paper focuses on the effects of toxins on fish and few applications of fish toxicology in field of studying human disorders.

Keywords: aquatic toxicology, neurological, behavioral and endocrinological changes.

Copefloc based nursery rearing of *P. vannamei* and its comparative growth performance during grow-out farming

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Abstract

Nursery rearing of *P. vannamei* was carried out at a density of 1000, 2000 and 3000 and 4000 nos/ton in triplicate in copefloc and compares its growth, survival and quantity of feed with control tanks. Copefloc generated inoculated with 3 species of copepods added to each treatment on alternate days stocked with post larvae of *P. vannamei* of 0.012 g at 23 ppt salinity. Significant growth and survival were observed in copefloc system compare to control and highest growth (0.8 to 1.2 g) and percentage survival of 96 and 100% was observed in the treatment with stocking density of 2000 and 4000 nos/ton respectively in copefloc system with 30 days of culture. The amount of feed required during the nursery was significantly less ($20 \pm 1.1\%$) in copefloc system compare to the control. During the grow-out culture (Stocking density 12 nos/m²), highest growth was observed in copefloc based farming with an average growth of 20.4 ± 0.8 g with survival of $89 \pm 1.8\%$ compare to control with an average growth of 12.6 ± 0.81 g with survival of $86 \pm 1.8\%$ with FCR of 0.94 and 1.2 respectively. Copefloc reared juvenile's shows significant growth performance and survival with lower FCR during grow-out culture direct the potential of copefloc technology during shrimp farming.

Keywords: *P. vannamei* , growth, survival, FCR

Chlorpyrifos induced stress mediated protein expression, elevated metabolic enzyme changes and mortality in rainbow fish, *Poecilia reticulata*

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Abstract

Chlorpyrifos is a commonly used organophosphate insecticide that causes toxicological effects in aquatic organisms especially in fish. This study determined the effects of chlorpyrifos on the biochemical and enzymatic changes of freshwater fish, *Poecilia reticulata*. In the present study chlorpyrifos was used to induce stress in rainbow fish and the impact of pesticide mediated stress was analyzed. At sub lethal and lethal concentration of chlorpyrifos, behavioural changes were registered and oxygen consumption rate fluctuated. Rainbow fish was exposed to sub lethal concentration of chlorpyrifos to induce stress and biochemical changes were registered. Total protein content of gill and muscle decreased, whereas, elevated level of free amino acid was found. Lipid content was also decreased considerably in the muscle. Sub lethal concentration of chlorpyrifos showed elevated level of serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase and serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase in the liver and gill. Histopathological analysis revealed that chlorpyrifos induced damage in the liver, gills and gut. Chlorpyrifos induced the synthesis of stress proteins. In the present study, lipid content was decreased considerably in muscle of chlorpyrifos exposed rainbow fish after 96 h. Compared with lipid from the muscle, the lipid content of gill was dramatically depleted. Chlorpyrifos treated rainbow fish affected catalase activity in the liver. In the present study sub lethal concentration of chlorpyrifos treated rainbow fish showed elevated level of SGPT and SGOT in the liver and gill. The elevated level of these enzymes showed damage in the liver cells due to chlorpyrifos toxicity after 96 h of incubation at room temperature.

Keywords: Pesticide; Chlorpyrifos; Fish; Toxicity

Isolation and identification of probiotic bacteria *Bacillus* species from gut of Indian major carp *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton, 1822)

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Abstract

The aim of the present study is to isolate and characterize endogenous microbiota *Bacillus* species from the gut of freshwater fish *Labeo rohita*. Ten bacterial cultures were isolated from fish gut. Among these, only three bacterial cultures are considered as a probiotic depending on the morphological characters, gram staining, biochemical and molecular technique. The isolated probiotic *Bacillus* species properties were isolated and characterized by using the 16s rRNA sequence method. The probiotic were identified to be such as *Bacillus oleronius*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis* respectively. *Bacillus* species characterization were tests for antimicrobial activity and antibiotic test were determined by using the agar disc diffusion technique. *Bacillus* species were used in inhibitory activity against tested fish pathogen of *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Finally the isolated probiotic *Bacillus subtilis* were used for the fish culture technique.

Keywords: *Bacillus* species, 16S rRNA Sequence, *Labeo rohita* and *Aeromonas hydrophila*.

Studies on growth and management of Indian major carps in Periyakulam Thoothukudi district

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Abstract

Indian major carps are commercially cultured in India and the Indian sub-continent Catla (*Catla catla*), Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and Mrigal (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) are considered the three carps of India. The main aim of this study was to assess the effect of different feed supplement on the growth performance (length and weight) of Indian major carp (*Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita*, and *Cirrhinus mrigala*) fishes. The ponds were supplemented with 2 g /per body weight fertilizer and supplementary feed, the sources of which were different. Various water quality parameters such as water temperature, dissolve oxygen, transparency, and pH were also recorded. The treatments were cow manure, Cow manure + Rice bran, Cow manure + Supplementary feed, Rice bran + Supplementary feed and Cow manure + Rice bran + Supplementary feed. The highest gross fish production of all the fishes was recorded as 1000 kg/ha/yr in Cow manure + Rice bran + Supplementary feed amongst the treatments. The growth performance in terms of average body weight, specific growth rate and total fish production of these fishes for one year. Thus for getting optimal fish production the fertilization of pond with supplementary feed is recommended

Keywords: Carps, Rice barn, Supplementary feed and Fish production.

Antibacterial activity of seaweed collected from Perumanal, Tamil Nadu against human and fish pathogenic bacteria

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Abstract

Seaweeds are one of the important living resources of the marine and have given valuable bioactive compounds. It plays an essential role in controlling antibiotic resist in fish and human bacterial pathogens. The selected seaweeds were extracted by three different in solvents, namely diethyl ether, ethanol, and ethyl acetate. The antibacterial screening of seaweeds, *Ulva lactuca* and *Gracilaria folifera* against ten human pathogenic bacteria: *E.coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Beta strepta*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Bacillus cereus* and three fish pathogens *via.*, *Aeromonas* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Vibrio* sp. by disc diffusion method was done. Here, the best activity was recorded in ethyl acetate extracts, which showed the inhibition zones against all the pathogens tested. The *G. folifera* extracted by ethyl acetate exhibited high antibacterial activity against *Serratia marcescens* 14 mm, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* of (12 mm), and (11 mm) in *K. pnemoniae*. The extract obtained using diethyl ether from *U. lactuca* showed maximum level of activity against *S. aureus* (12 mm) and *P. aeruginosa* (12 mm). In the prevention and management of bacterial fish and human infections, these seaweed bioactive components could be employed as an alternative to existing commercial ineffective antibiotics.

Keywords: Ethyl acetate, *Ulva lactuca*, Antibacterial activity, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Effect of dietary supplementation of aquatic weed *Pistia stratiotes* on specific and non-specific immunity in tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila*

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Abstract

Profitable fish culture requires unfailing supply of fish feed as a source of protein for growth nutrient and energy currency. Because of rising cost and scarcity of fish meal, it is necessary to replace the traditional fish meal by locally available cheaper ingredients of either animal or plant origin. The aquaculture industry depends worldwide on the availability of low cost, high quality feeds. This study discusses the ability of *P. stratiotes* to enhance growth, serum biochemical indices, haemato-immunological responses in tilapia, *Oreochromis mossambicus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Four experimental feed were formulated by replacing 0% (T1, Control), 25% (T2), 50% (T3) and 75% (T4) of *P. stratiotes*. Fingerlings of tilapia *O. mossambicus* were reared on these feed for eight weeks. The results showed that growth, daily retention of protein and nutrient deposition in *O. mossambicus* were significantly higher in *P. stratiotes* supplemented feed as compared to control. The maximum neutrophil activity, lysozyme activity, antirprotease activity were observed in T3 treated groups. The maximum relative percent survival was recorded in T3. It was concluded that *O. mossambicus* could utilize limited amount of carbohydrate in the feed, there by sparing protein to render better growth and immunity of the fish.

Keywords: *Pistia stratiotes*, *Oreochromis mossambicus*, growth, biochemical indices

**Assessment of zooplankton diversity at Setti lake, Idappadi in Salem district,
Tamilnadu, India**

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Abstract

Planktons are the basic food source of aquatic ecosystem. Zooplanktons diversity is one of the most important ecological indicators for assessment of water quality. This study was designed to identify zooplankton diversity of Setti lake, Idappadi in Salem District, in relation to the diversity of zooplanktons from the period of October to March 2022 and the results were recorded periodically. The populations of zooplanktons were positively correlated. Total 34 species of zooplanktons were identified. Among zooplankton, 6% Protozoa, 41% Rotifera, 18% Cladocera, 20% Copepoda and 5% Ostracoda were recorded. Rotifera was found to be the most dominant group and Protozoa was the least dominant group. Zooplanktons are also very useful as biological indicators of water quality.

Keywords: Zooplankton, Water quality, Biological indicator

Isolation and characterization of bacteria from tannery effluent treatment plant and their tolerance to heavy metals

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Abstract

Based on the method used, tanneries produce various contaminants. In Erode, district and biologically treated, tannery effluent specimens were obtained from leather tannery. The present thesis deals with the evaluation of the treatment tannery effluent's physicochemical parameters. It was studied after the treatment in order to understand the various physical and chemical properties of the sample effluents. This study was carried out with the analysis of physicochemical parameters of effluents produced by the tanneries to find out the characteristics of handled tannery effluents. Different physical and chemical properties, such as color, odor, alkalinity, acidity, temperature, pH, turbidity, with excessive organic and inorganic compounds showing high Electrical Conductivity (EC), Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Solids (TS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total Hardness, Oils and Grease. The chemical parameters are sodium (Na), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), chloride (Cl), nitrite (NO), magnesium (Mg), phosphate, fluoride, sulphate and chromium, which have been tested and matched to the standard levels recommended by the Indian Standards Bureau (BIS).

Keywords: Treated Effluent, Heavy metals, Tanneries, Physicochemical parameters.

A study on physico chemical characteristics and biodiversity of the Vaniyar dam at Venkatasamuthiram, Dharmapuri district, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

A study was carried out to assess the water analysis of Vaniyar dam in Dharmapuri District, Tamilnadu, India. The study period was December 2021 to March 2022 ongoing. The Vaniyar dam water quality and plankton diversity were analyzed. This study was carried out with the analysis of physicochemical parameters find out the characteristics of handled Vaniyar dam. Different physical and chemical properties, such as pH, aalkalinity, acidity, temperature, turbidity, Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), total hardness, the chemical parameters are sodium (Na), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), ron (Fe), chloride (Cl), nitrite (NO), and phosphate. The phytoplanktons and zooplanktons were positively correlated. The results revealed that the diversity of total 21 species of phytoplanktons and 17 zooplanktons were identified. The planktons are also very useful as biological indicators of water quality.

Keywords: Water quality, Physico-chemical parameters, Phytoplankton and Zooplankton, Vaniyar dam.

**Assessment of phytoplankton diversity at Periyasadayampalayam pond, in
Erode district, Tamil Nadu, India**

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Abstract

Planktons are basic food source of aquatic ecosystem. The phytoplankton diversity is one of the most important ecological indicators for the water analysis. This study was designed to identify phytoplankton diversity of Periyasadayampalayam pond in Erode District, in relation to the diversity of phytoplankton from the study period May to October 2017 and results were recorded periodically. The population of phytoplanktons were positive correlated. The results revealed that the diversity of total of 64 species of phytoplankton were identified. Among phytoplankton belongs to 32 species of 39% of Chlorophyceae, 29% of Cyanophyceae, 17% Bacillariophyceae, 3% of Euglenophyceae and 2% of Spirotrichea 2%, Xanthophyceae 5% and Cryptophyceae 2% were observed. Out of these Chlorophyceae was the most dominant group and Zygnematophyceae was the least dominant group during the study period. The phytoplanktons are also very useful as biological indicators of water quality.

Key words: Water quality, Periyasadayam palayam pond, Phytoplankton, Biological indicator

Comparative study on unsaturated fatty acid in fresh and marine water fishes

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Abstract

Human body have essential saturated and unsaturated fatty acids must be consumed in the diet but our body cannot synthesize certain fatty acids. Aquatic foods are known to be the main source of unsaturated fatty acid (omega 3). The unsaturated fatty acids are found in marine and fresh water fish. A comparative study on the fatty acids contents of three marine fishes – mackerel (Atlantic), dogfish (spiny), salmon (Atlantic formed) and three fresh water fishes - trout (lean lake), catfish (brown bull head) carp (river) were carried out. Marine fishes show more unsaturated fatty acids compared to fresh water fish. Omega-3 fatty acids may help to lower blood pressure, reduce the chance of abnormal heart rhythm, reduce the likelihood of heart attack and stroke. Omega 3 is very highly demanded one that is found in marine fishes.

Keywords: fatty acids ,Omega-3 fatty acids, carp, marine fishes

Growth performance of white molly, *Poecilia sphenops* fed with natural sources of carotenoid pigments from *Tagetes erecta*

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Abstract

Pigmentation is one of the important quality attributes of the fish for consumer acceptability. Carotenoids are responsible for pigmentation of muscle in food fish and skin colour in ornamental fish. As fish is not capable of synthesizing carotenoids *de novo* there is a need to incorporate carotenoid in the diet of cultured species. Since synthetic carotenoids are known to have deteriorating effects on the environment, there is a great demand for inclusion of natural carotenoids in aqua feed to achieve bright coloration of fish. Marigold botanically identified as *Tagetes* (Compositae) genus is ethnobotanically known drug, used from ancient times in the Indian system of medicine for the treatment of rheumatism, cold, bronchitis, eye diseases, ulcers, etc. This genus has been investigated for various biological activities like antimicrobial, antiplasmodial, antioxidant, insecticidal, food colorants, feed additives, possess anticancer and anti aging effects, etc. The *Tagetes* oil has been mainly used for the compounding of high-grade perfumes and also acts as anti haemorrhagic, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antispasmodic, astringent, and diaphoretic. The fine dark yellow powder is currently used worldwide as a colouration and nutritive source for numerous species. Hence, the present attempt has been made to evaluate the different concentrations such as 0%, 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% of marigold petals incorporated diets on the growth parameters of white molly, *Poecilia sphenops*.

Keywords: Carotenoids, coloration, metabolism, *Poecilia sphenops*

Ichthyofaunal biodiversity of village pond Khertha, Balod District, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract

Freshwater fish biodiversity especially in rural areas is very important because of employment generation and livelihood. Traditionally aquaculture is done in the rural area by the fisherman community, they do not have proper knowledge in terms of scientific perspective. So the present study aims to prepare a list of fishes found in village pond khertha. Fishes serve mankind in two ways it serves as a good source of protein and also provide a mode of employment. Fishes as a food source can combat the problem of malnutrition in the rural area. In this study, an endeavour had been made to list all species found in this pond with their local names. Village khertha is situated in the Dondilohara block of district Balod of Chhattisgarh state. A total of 17 species from different families were found. Recorded fish species were classified in 4 order and 5 families. Order Cypriniformes were found as a dominant group. The main fishes found are *Catla catla*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, *Labeo rohita*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Clarius batrachus*, and *Oreochromis mossambicus*.

Keywords: Biodiversity, village pond, malnutrition, freshwater.

Investigation of *in vivo* toxicity analysis of reduced graphene oxide nanomaterials in zebrafish

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Abstract

Nanomaterials is one of the widely used industrial applications such as sterilization of ponds, water treatment and antifouling in fishing and aquaculture. Due to their wide range of application in nanomedicine Reduced Graphene Oxide (RGO) and graphene oxide (GO) have gained popularity in wound healing, drug delivery, tissue engineering and biosensors are just a few of the possibilities. The toxicity of RGO nanocomposite was assesst using the zebrafish embryo model in this study. SEM, XRD, AFM and UV were used to characterise the RGO composites that were created. The bioavailability of the RGO nano composite has been discovered in a sequence of tightly controlled studies. Zebrafish body length, heartbeat count and survival % were methodically measured. The RGO nano composites in contrast, showed very minimal toxicity to zebrafish embryos at a dosage of 12.5 g/mL. Moreover the toxicity of nano composites rises with increasing levels higher to 125 g/mL. At higher concentrations, RGO nanocomposites produces Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) which causes tetratogenicity and cardiotoxicity. RGO toxicity is concentration dependent, according to the finding, the results of this study will help to further the usage of RGO composites in nanomedicines.

Keywords: Graphene oxide, nanocomposite, toxicity, zebrafish

A study on collected seaweeds from Rasthakadu coast near Kanyakumari district, Tamil nadu, India

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Abstract

The present study area was carried out from December 2021 to February 2022 in Rasthakadu coast, Kanyakumari, India. During the study period eleven seaweed species were collected from the coastal area. These samples were detaching a definite portion of seaweed bed and kept it in a pre-cleaned polythene bags and transported to the laboratory. The seaweeds were identified using the taxonomic keys and the nomenclature. Epiphytic plants are important components of the forest ecosystem and aquatic ecosystems since they can be highly productive in all types of water systems. These epiphytes have the potential to furnish drug lead compounds, especially for treating cancers, and thus warrant in depth investigations. This information may provide important tools to explain oceanographic, ecological and biogeographically phenomena in the area.

Keywords: Seaweeds, Epiphyte, Drug, Rasthakadu coast.

FRESH WATER ICTHYOPHIS DIVERSITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO A
POND IN VATANAPPALLY, THRISSUR, KERALA

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A pond is an area filled with water, either natural or artificial, that is smaller than a lake. Ponds are usually by definition quite shallow waterbodies with varying abundances of aquatic plants and animals. The study was carried out in a pond in the village Ganeshamangalam, Vatanappally, Thrissur, Kerala, India. The fish diversity and abundance of the pond were observed and analysed for the last one year. The identification of specimens were carried out using different methods. The study revealed fish diversities of 13 fish species belonging to 7 orders and 11 different families. During the study Siluriformes and Anabantiformes were the most abundantly found orders followed by Cyprinodontiformes, Cichliformes, Gobiiformes, Beloniformes and Cypriniformes. The study reveals the necessity of conservation of ponds.

Key words: Fish diversity, ponds, conservation.

Noxious effects of herbal syrup [nivaran90] on ornamental fish common molly *Poecilia sphenops*

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Abstract

Herbal medicine is a practice that includes herbs, herbal material, and preparations that contain parts of plants or combination thereof as active Ingredients like Seenthil, Vetiver, Ashwagandha, Peyputtal. The essential oil of vetiver is a well-known sedative. It sedates nervous irritations, afflictions, convulsions and emotional outbursts such as anger, anxiety, epileptic and hysteric attacks, restlessness, and nervousness. Large doses of Ashwagandha might cause stomach upset, diarrhea, and vomiting. Rarely, liver problems might occur. After expiry of such products/satchet containing such compounds are dumped in the water bodies, they become a threat to the ecosystem. So the study undergoes about the change in consumption of dissolved oxygen on common molly *Poecilia sphenops*, an ornamental fish which is widely reared for its simple color in fish tanks is used. The effect of such herbal product on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular herbal cough syrup {Nivaran 90}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of activated herbal compounds for a time period of 1/2 hour and multiplied with 2 and the result is tabulated and discussed

Keywords: Herbal syrup, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*.

A short experimental study of detergents on common molly *Poecilia sphenops*

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Abstract

Water pollution caused by detergents is now a big concern in the global context. The per capita detergent consumption in India is around 2.7 kilogram per year. It is around 3.7 kg in Philippines and Malaysia and 10 kg in the United States of America. Nonylphenol, a hazardous chemical present in detergents, is known to enter water bodies and the food chains. It bio-accumulates and can pose serious environmental and health risks. It has been detected in human breast milk, blood and urine, and is associated with reproductive and developmental effects in rodents. It is recommended to find substitutes of Nonylphenol. The Bureau of Indian Statistics (BIS) has set the standard of phenolic compounds in drinking water {0.001 milligram per litre (mg/L)} and surface water (5.0 mg/L). The detergents contain suspected carcinogens, and ingredients that do not fully biodegrade. Detergents are widely used for the cleansing of clothes and they are washed off in water and get mixed with nearby water bodies. But pollution of these water bodies has created physiological stress on its aquatic fauna. Among various forms of pollution in water bodies, detergent pollution has an immediate and detrimental effect on the aquatic fauna. *Poecilia sphenops*, ornamental fish was used in our study to determine the effect of detergent pollution on the fish's breathing. Three different concentrations of a popular brand of detergent {Surf excel}, were prepared and the amounts of Dissolved Oxygen consumed by fishes exposed to the detergent were determined using Winkler's method. Our study demonstrated that Dissolved Oxygen consumption in *Poecilia sphenops* increases in the presence of detergent. This is due to the stress caused by the detergent on the normal physiological activities of the fish. Draining of domestic sewage containing detergents into water bodies adversely affect its aquatic fauna.

Keywords: *Poecilia sphenops*, Detergent, Dissolved Oxygen, Ornamental fish, Stress

A short experimental study on impact of hair dye in ornamental fish

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Abstract

Around 1.43 billion units of hair dye are sold per year in the United States alone, and 75% of women use hair dye regularly, compared to only 7% in 1950. Around a decade ago, concerns began to be raised around the link between artificial dye and diseases (including liver disease and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma). Today, the effect of hair dye chemicals on the world's oceans is just as big a cause for concern. These chemicals, when poured in the falls and lakes, can persist in water even after it is treated, making their way back to our oceans, causing fish stress, less oxygen level in water and totally collapse in aquatic system. Population growth and industrial development are the major causes of contamination of water resources. In developing countries, pollution of water resources has become a serious problem which leads to ecological disorders and causes many physiological as well as biological changes in aquatic animals. Hair dyes and other colourant have been around for a quite long time. Wide spread use of such added colorificants cause anomaly and abnormalities on the water surface, affecting aeration and quality of fresh water. *Poecilia sphenops*, a common ornamental fish selected in the present study to determine the effect of Hair dye on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular Hair dye {Black rose}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of hair dye for a time period of 1 hour. All these results clearly indicate a severe impact of hair dye on the aquatic ecosystem.

Keywords: Hair dye, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*.

**Adverse results of coconut oil [VVD] studied on ornamental fish common molly
*Poecilia sphenops***

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Abstract

Coconut oil comes from the nut (fruit) of the coconut palm. It contains medium-chain fatty acids, including capric acid, caprylic acid, and lauric acid. About 52% to 85% of coconut oil is made up of specific saturated fats, called medium-chain fatty acids. It has a moisturizing effect when applied to the skin. People commonly use coconut oil for eczema and growth in premature infants. It is also used for psoriasis, obesity, breast cancer, heart disease, and many other conditions, but there is no good scientific evidence to support these uses. The initially produced coconut oil is actually white solid highly saturated fatty with added characteristic colourants. Fraction coconut oil contains lauric acid, while other significant saturated fats are myristic acid, palmitic acid, and caprylic acid. After taking bath from water sources, that applied in the head is washed away, Major quantity of such practice is un-negligible. The chemical composition present in such oils shows a slight change of action in normal behavioural activities in fishes. For studying such effects the ornamental fish *Poecilia sphenops*, common molly is used. The present study to determine the effect of such softeners on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular brand of Coconut oil {VVD}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of coconut oil for a time period. All these results clearly indicate an impact of oils on the aquatic ecosystem.

Keywords: Coconut oil, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*

Effect of body soap on oxygen consumption in ornamental fish *Poecilia sphenops*

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Abstract

Soap is a product formed by the process of 'saponification', which includes a reaction between alkali and oil (fatty substance). When this reaction takes place, glycerine is formed as a by-product and is present in the soap itself and gives the soap its moisturizing property. So, the ultimate product called 'soap' is actually a salt. Body soap and other TFM soap's have been around for a quite long time. Wide spread use of such water soluble sodium/potassium salts cause decreased surface tension of water surface so the water, they don't completely biodegrade and contaminate water resources with toxic heavy metals like cadmium and arsenic affecting aeration and quality of fresh water. *Poecilia sphenops*, a common ornamental fish selected in the present study to determine the effect of shampoo on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular soap {Lifebuoy}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of shampoo for a time period of 1 hour. All these results clearly indicate a severe impact of detergents on the aquatic ecosystem.

Keywords: Body soap, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*.

Deleterious effect of fabric softeners [comfort] on *Poecilia sphenops*

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Abstract

A fabric softener is a liquid composition added to washing machines during the rinse cycle to make clothes feel better to the touch. These products work by depositing lubricating chemicals on the fabric that make it feel softer, reduce static cling, and impart a fresh fragrance. The first fabric softeners were developed by the textile industry during the early twentieth century. At that time the process that was used to dye cotton fibers left them feeling harsh. In the early 1900s, preparations known as cotton softeners were developed to improve the feel of these fibers after dyeing. A typical cotton softener consisted of seven parts water, three parts soap, and one part olive, corn, or tallow oil. With advances in organic chemistry, new compounds were created that could soften fabric more effectively. These improved formulations soon found their way into the commercial market. Now all are used world widely and the aftermath of this substance which are washed away in water resources are been under study. A fabric softener or fabric conditioner is a conditioner that is applied to laundry during the rinse cycle in a washing machine to reduce harshness in clothes that are dried in air after machine washing. In contrast to laundry detergents, fabric softeners may be regarded as a kind of after-treatment laundry aid. Fabric softener's and other cleansing agents have been around for a quite long time. Wide spread use of Fabric softeners can cause excess frothing and growth of floating aquatic weeds (eutrophication) on the water surface, affecting aeration and quality of freshwater. *Poecilia sphenops*, a common ornamental fish selected in the present study to determine the effect of such softeners on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular brand of fabric softener {Comfort}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of fabric conditioner for a time period of 1/2 hour, and the result indicates that the washed water after the use of fabric softener stresses the fish and its behaviour.

Keywords: Fabric softener, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*

**Studies on the effect of shampoo on oxygen consumption in ornamental fish
*Poecilia sphenops***

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Abstract

Pollution of water resources has become a serious problem, which leads to ecological disorders and causes many physiological as well as biological changes in aquatic animals. Shampoo and other cleansing agents have been around for a quite long time. Wide spread use of shampoo cause excess frothing and growth of floating aquatic weeds (eutrophication) on the water surface, affecting aeration and quality of fresh water. *Poecilia sphenops*, a common ornamental fish selected in the present study to determine the effect of shampoo on the oxygen consumption capacity of the fish in three different concentrations of a popular brand of shampoo {Dove}. The amount of dissolved oxygen consumed by fishes was determined using Winkler's method. It is evident from the present study that the samples treated with 10 ppm, 20 ppm, 30 ppm of shampoo for a time period of 1 hour. All these results clearly indicate a severe impact of shampoo on the aquatic ecosystem.

Keywords: shampoo, Dissolved Oxygen, Fish, Pollution, *Poecilia sphenops*.

Effects on hematological and immunological parameters to ammonia exposure in *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* of aquarium fishes

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Abstract

The ammonia is one of the major risk factors when culturing freshwater aquarium fishes; it may lead to responsible for the growth and survival. To avoid this high risks factor of ammonia toxicity, the present experiment studies, the following hematological, immunological, and their growth performance were observed in the *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* fish at aquarium water. An experimental setup was carried out around 90 days without a water change. During the experiment, the fishes were released a higher level of ammonia waste. The different concentrations of ammonia levels will cause lethal effects on fish. Different concentration of ammonia was analyzed in the aquarium fish water to study the impact on hematological and immunological parameters. Due to the ammonia exposure the fish growth, feeding rate, and survival rate were affected. The present study emphasizes the effects of ammonia and its leads to the significant changes of hematological parameters like Red Blood cell count (RBC), White Blood cell Count (WBC), Hemoglobin, and Hematocrit. The immune response of enzymatic activities (IgM, C3, C4, NOS, and LSZ) also decreased when at the different concentrations of ammonia present in the aquarium water. During the experimental studies could observe the growth performance of feed conservation ratio, weight gain, and survival rate was significantly reduced at 0.089 mg/L of the ammonia level, it clearly indicated the negative impacts when the ammonia concentration at above optimum level. From these studies, the ammonia stress may affect the digestion and absorption of aquarium fishes can be avoided when maintaining of low level (below 0.05 mg/L) with an effective filtration system.

Keywords: *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* , Immune response, White Blood cell Count

Diversity and distribution of eel in Indian waters

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Abstract

Along with their ecology, freshwater eels have fascinated biologists for centuries. However, eels are a globally consumed species that has good demand as a food fish as having high nutritional value. In India, the eels are considered as poor man's food whereas in other countries like Greek, Roman, German, Japanese and people of several Asian and European countries are considered as a luxury food and used as a medicine. It has been reported as Near Threatened species in the IUCN list. Day by day, the eels are threatened to extinction like pollution, habitat modification and degradation, environmental degradation, overfishing and barrier effects of dams, etc. The Indian Government has taken steps to conserve diversity. So, there are over 800 species of eel, 13 Orders, 34 families, 93 genera, and 226 species. In India, there are some different types of Indian eel species like Indian Mottled Eel, Indian conger eel (*Conger cinereus*), Indian blind swamp eel, Indian mud moray eel, and Indian short fin eel. These species are widely distributed in Western and Eastern Ghats of India. Still now, many of the researchers are still discovering the new eel species in India, which will be in terrestrial and aquatic. These species can be seen in pond, river stream, tropical and marine water. The present study has been prepared with the aim to sum up the available information on different aspects of Indian eel species along with the possible measures for its conservation.

Keywords: diversity, environmental degradation, Indian short fin eel

Observation of *Spirulina platensis* as bio-stimulator in the raft aquaponics system for food security

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Abstract

Aquaponics is an emerging technological innovation system, integration of algal and Aquaponic technology is an excellent tool in producing protein and foods for personal consumption (food security) and/or for sale to others (wealth generation) all countries of the world are now taking note of food security issues. The introduction of algae technologies in the aquaponic food production system with that algae in aquaponics is reasonable and it can further increase the nutrient efficiency and growth of aquaponics crops. Evaluation of aquaponics based-food system nutrients on the growth and yield of onion (*Allium cepa L.*) and found the potential of organic effluents as an alternative source of bio-fertilizers. *Spirulina* contains a wide spectrum of nutrients that include proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, beta carotene, and antioxidants apart from trace elements. The optimum range of temperature and Dissolved Oxygen (DO) were recorded in all components that included fish tanks, algae, and onion plants in the raft aquaponics system that would be helpful for the process oxidation of organic matter by microbial activity to stimulate the growth of onion plants along with algal culture. Further, the foliar application of algal extracts resulted in higher growth of onion plants in the raft aquaponics system, the spirulina species has contained micro, macro and growth promoters when applied algae extract for greenish matured onion plants, the high chlorophyll contents ($31.01 \pm 1.1/g$) were observed, which indicates the efficiency of *Spirulina platensis* to stimulate the growth of onion plants in the raft aquaponics system. From these results, could understand the algal extract as an efficient bio-stimulant, and additional that can be used as a live feed to rearing high health fishes for aquarium fishes. These aquaponics systems are sustainable, provide food security, livelihoods to poor people and are also economically feasible for the business sense.

Key words: *Allium cepa L*, *Spirulina platensis*, bio-stimulator and Raft aquaponics .

Studies on Phytal Faunal Diversity in Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

The marine system includes coral reef systems, mangroves, seaweeds, seagrasses, planktons, and the meio and macrofaunal communities of biogeographical regions. Algal beds are one of the most productive habitats in the marine environment and frequently support high densities of mobile invertebrates, including small crustaceans, gastropods, copepods, and polychaetes. The term "phytal" describes the coastal marine surroundings dominated by macrophytes and also the organisms related to them. In the present investigation, an attempt was made to find out the phytal faunal diversity associated with *Chaetomorpha aerea*, (Chlorophyta), *Gracilaria corticata* Padina pavonica Linnaeus Thivy, 1960 (Phaeophyta) and *Ulva fasciata* Delile, 1813 (Chlorophyta). Total of 32 species from five groups, such as, Mollusca, Amphipods, Isopods, Crustacea, Polychaeta, and Crabs, were recorded. The phytal faunal density is also dependent on the morphology of the algae structure, texture, color, and contour and their sediment retentive capacities, as well as macroalgal species, which structure suitable habitat for these living organisms.

Keywords: Macroalgae, phytal fauna, and species diversity.

Anneuxres-1(ICRTA-2022)
(List of species)

<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	<i>Etroplus maculatus</i>	<i>Puntius spp</i>
<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i>	<i>Etroplus suratensis</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
	<i>Exiguobacterium mexicanum</i>	
<i>Anabas scandens</i>		<i>Salvinia molesta</i>
<i>Anabas testudeneus</i>	<i>Gerres erythrourus</i>	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>
<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	<i>Glyphis gangeticus</i>	<i>Spirulina platensis</i>
<i>Artemia franciscana</i>	<i>Gracilaria corticata</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
<i>Artemia parthenogenetica</i>	<i>Isochrysis galbana</i>	<i>Stolephorus indicus</i>
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	<i>S.lamarrii</i>
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	<i>Salmo trutta</i>
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Lactococcus garvieae</i>	<i>Sperata aorides</i>
<i>Azolla pinnata</i>	<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
		<i>Stocheospermum marginatum</i>
<i>Anguilla bengalensis</i>	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>	<i>Tilapia mossambicus</i>
<i>Anoxypristis cuspidate</i>	<i>Hypothalamycthis molitrix</i>	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>
<i>Carcharhinus hemiodon</i>	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>
	<i>Lacto bacillus</i>	<i>Vibrio alginolyticus</i>
<i>Chaetomorpha antennina</i>	<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i>	<i>Vibrio harveyii</i>
<i>Channa striatus</i>	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>	<i>Priestia megaterium</i>
<i>Circumonchobothrium hemlatae</i>		
	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	<i>Pseudolaguvia</i>
<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	<i>Weissella confusa</i>
<i>Clarias garipepinus</i>	<i>M. rosenbergii</i>	
<i>Codium arabicum</i>	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	
<i>Codium decorticatum</i>	<i>Mystus gulio</i>	
<i>Codium tomentosum</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	
<i>Ctenopharyngoden</i>	<i>Nitophyllum marginale</i>	
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i>	
<i>Channa marulius</i>	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	
<i>Channa punctatus</i>	<i>Pangasianodon hypophthalmus</i>	
<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	<i>Pethia conchonchius</i>	
<i>Clarius batrachus</i>	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	
<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	<i>Poecilia sphenops</i>	
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	<i>Pempheris vanicolensis</i>	
<i>Danio rerio</i>	<i>Penaeus indicus</i>	
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i>	<i>Penaeus vannamei</i>	

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ABOUT THE COLLEGE

St. Xavier's College was established at Palayamkottai in 1923 by Jesuit Fathers of the Jesuit Madurai Province with an aim of preparing generations of students for a happy, healthy and harmonious life. The motto of the college is Veritate Lumen et Vita (Light and Life through Truth). It is a grant-in-aid institution recognized by the UGC Act under sections 2(f) and 12(B). The College is affiliated to the Manonmaniam Sundaranar University. In recognition of its service and excellence, the College was granted autonomy in 1987. The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) in 2019 at A++ grade with a CGPA of 3.66 out of 4 in IV Cycle. The UGC awarded the status of "College with Potential for Excellence" to our college in 2004 and again in 2010 and 2014. STAR College scheme has been awarded by DBT, Govt. of India. In the ranking conducted by the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF), our college got 50th rank in College Category in 2020. Today more than 4000 students study in 14 Postgraduate and 15 Undergraduate departments. Ph.D. Research is carried out in 12 departments.

ABOUT THE DEPARTMENT

The Department of Zoology of St. Xavier's College, Palayamkottai was started in 1927 when the subject was taught to the intermediate students. Rev. Fr. Foreau S. J., was the first Lecturer and Mr. Krishnasamy Iyengar assisted him. B.Sc. Degree course was started in 1957 and was upgraded to M.Sc. in the year 1979. The Department was recognized as a Research Department in 1985 and M.Phil. course is being offered since 1986. In the year 2003 and 2018 the Department was recognized as DST-FIST sponsored Department. In 2014, the department was recognized and included under Star College Department Scheme offered by Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, Govt. of India. The Department celebrated its Diamond Jubilee in 2018. At present, the faculty members are concentrating on the basic and the applied aspects of Aquaculture Zoology, Agriculture Zoology [Pestiferous Insects, Phytopathogens and their management], Medical Entomology [Vector Biology and Management], Insect Immunology, Wild life Biology and Phytochemistry and Pharmacology.

ABOUT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

- 'International Conference on Recent Trends in Aquaculture 2022 (ICRTA-22)' invites you to become a part of HYBRID EVENT – which is scheduled on March 25, 2022 at St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Tamil Nadu, India.
- 'Aquaculture 2022' is conducted in Blended mode with both offline and virtual versions. We believe that our decision will enable broad participation.
- This Conference enlightens on the theme "Recent developments in aquaculture" which acknowledges the recent advancements, newest updates, innovations and challenges that impact the field of fisheries, and aquaculture. In the post-pandemic era, feeding the world faces new impediments. This emphasizes the importance of fisheries and aquaculture as viable solutions for supplying high-quality food and nutrition to the world's growing population. Aquaculture continues to be the world's fastest-growing food production sector, despite the fact that capture fish production has remained largely stable in recent decades. However, increasing the scale of aquaculture intensification has resulted in a number of concerns that will require long-term solutions. As a result, it's critical to disseminate information on technological advancements and new modern approaches to sustainable fisheries and aquaculture around the world. This scientific gathering is a positive move in the right direction.
- This prestigious conference will serve as an intuition for international researchers, scientists, academicians, aquaculture experts, marine biologists and industry giants to present their research findings to the international community. The environment will be vibrant, with open and cordial interaction between attendees, with representatives from academia and industry.
- We hope to see you at 'Aquaculture 2022' with a firm belief that it will provide the most beneficial outcomes to the aquaculture and fisheries industry.